

HARMONISED PRACTICES, REGULATIONS AND STANDARDS
IN WASTE MANAGEMENT AND DECOMMISSIONING

Deliverable D2.1

**Work methodologies: Methods
for identification and
prioritisation of topics**

Norbert Maes

SCK CEN

Boeretang 200, B-2400 Mol, Belgium

e-mail: nmaes@sckcen.be

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- **Contributing author(s):** Elke Jacops (SCK CEN), Liz Harvey (GSL limited), Tim Harrison (GSL limited), Féderica Pancotti (Sogin), David Oxberry (Studsvik), Anthony Banford (NNL), Linda Fowler (NNL).
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ABSTRACT

The 3-year HARPERS project aims to establish and clarify the benefits and added value of more aligned and harmonised regulations, practices and standards in decommissioning and radioactive waste management between Member States (MS), with regard to cross border services/facilities, moving to a circular economy and implementation of advanced technologies. The project will identify relevant regulatory differences across MS, assess the rationale for the identified regulatory differences and establish the potential for their harmonisation.

In the first phase (Phase 1) of the project we focus on engaging with Stakeholders to assess needs and pros/cons for harmonisation and identify priority areas for deeper analysis in Phase 2 of the project.

This report describes the methodologies used to identify priority areas (gap analysis), how the stakeholder community was built and how we engage with the stakeholders (via workshops) in order to fine tune the identified priority areas enabling a selection of priority topics that will be investigated in Phase 2 of the project.

Administrative coordinator contact:

Elke Jacops

SCK CEN Belgian Nuclear Research
Centre

Boeretang 200, 2400 Mol, Belgium

Email: elke.jacops@sckcen.be

Tel 0032 485 274196

Technical coordinator contact:

Réka Szőke

IFE Institute for Energy Technology

Os Alle 5, NO-1777 Halden, Norway

Email: reka.szoke@ife.no

Tel 0047 452 85963

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V1.0	26/04/2023	Norbert Maes	Final version after internal review

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1 Introduction

The 3-year HARPERS project aims to establish and clarify the benefits and added value of more aligned and harmonised regulations, practices and standards in decommissioning and radioactive waste management between Member States (MS). Specifically, with regard to cross border services/facilities, moving to a circular economy and implementation of advanced technologies. The project will identify relevant regulatory differences across MS, assess the rationale for the identified regulatory differences and establish the potential for their harmonisation.

In the first phase (first year) of the project we focus on engaging with stakeholders to assess drivers for and the pros and cons of harmonisation and identify priority areas for deeper analysis in Phase 2 of the project. The different steps conducted in Phase 1 of the project are depicted in Figure 1.

This report describes the methodologies used to *identify priority areas* (gap analysis), how *the stakeholder community was built* and how we *engage with the stakeholders* (via workshops) in order to fine tune the identified priority areas enabling a selection of priority topics that will be investigated through open calls in Phase 2 of the project.

The report is split into four sections, explaining the methods used for:

- Building the HARPERS stakeholder community (Section 2).
- Performing a gap analysis to identify priority areas for detailed study (Section 3).
- Engaging with the stakeholder community to reflect on priority topics (Section 4).
- Selection of topics which will be studied in detail in Phase 2, and the launching of open calls that provide the opportunity for external Stakeholders to contribute to Phase 2 (Section 5).

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Figure 1: Timeline presenting the different steps during Phase 1 of the project.

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2 Building a Stakeholder community

The outcome of the project greatly depends on the interaction with the Stakeholder (SH) community. One of the first priorities of the project was to establish a Stakeholder community.

At the start of the project, networks and relevant organisations that have inherent interest in optimisation of decommissioning and waste management activities through improved harmonisation and establishment of a common regulatory framework were identified. The activities targeted include decommissioning, waste treatment solutions and predisposal operations, interim storage facilities and final repository operations and safety aspects. An optimal use of existing networks was made for building a Stakeholder community.

To identify and map Stakeholders, an excel file (Milestone MS4) on the internal website (SharePoint) was created which compiled a list of possible interested networks which may be or may contain Stakeholders (Euradscience, NEA, SNETP, IGD-TP, IAEA, EURAD, PREDIS, SHARE, ERDO, WENRA, ETSON, SITES, SSH-SHARE, DigiDECOM,...) and individual Stakeholders (organisations) known to the partners of the project (see Figure 2). This Excel file lists following items for the networks: i) name of network, ii) country/region, iii) short description, iv) website and v) logbook (to indicate when and by whom they have been contacted) and for the individual organisations: i) name of organisation, ii) country/region, iii) actor type, iv) short description, v) website, vi) consortium partner with contact, vii) categorisation of importance as a Stakeholder (“must have”/“nice to have”/“not relevant”), viii) logbook and ix) registered as stakeholder Y/N.

All HARPERS participants have been asked to check the list for i) their own country and ii) other countries from which we have no partners. For each Stakeholder in the list, following items are listed:

- the consortium partners who is responsible for the contact
- an indication of the relevance of this Stakeholder for the project (must have/nice to have/not relevant)

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Excel stakeholders harpers - Saved

Search (Alt + Q)

File Home Insert Draw Page Layout Formulas Data Review View Help Editing

Comments Catch up Share

Undo Redo

Clipboard: Cut, Copy, Paste, Format Painter

Font: Calibri, 11, Bold, Italic, Underline, Paragraph, Text Color, Fill Color

Alignment: Wrap Text, Merge & Center

Number: General, Currency, Percentage, Date, Time, Text, Fraction, Decimals, Accounting

Styles: Conditional Formatting, Format As Table, Insert, Delete Format

Editing: AutoSum, Clear, Sort & Filter, Find & Select

Spain

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
	Organisation	Country/Region	Actor type	Short description	Website	logbook					
1				in atomic energy, encourage the construction of nuclear-power installations, establish safety and health regulations, encourage the free flow of information and the free movement of personnel, and establish a common market for trade in nuclear equipment and materials	https://ec.europa.eu/energy/topics/nuclear-energy_en						
6	EC EURATOM	EU	Owner								
7	EC EURATOM national contact points	EU	Owner								
8	EDRAM	World	WMO	International association for environmentally safe disposal of radioactive materials	www.edram.info						
9	ENEF	EU	All	The European Nuclear Energy Forum gathers all relevant stakeholders in the field: governments, nuclear industry and regulators, electricity consumers and civil society	https://ec.europa.eu/energy/topics/nuclear-energy/european-nuclear-energy-forum-enef_en						
10	ENS	EU	All	European Nuclear Society, brings together 12000 professionals from academic world, research centres, industry and authorities.ENS promotes the development of nuclear science and technology and the understanding of peaceful nuclear applications	www.euronuclear.org						
11	ENTRAP	EU	RE	European network of testing facilities for the quality checking of radioactive waste packages	http://www.en-trap.eu/						
12	ERDO	EU	WMO	Multinational working group to study the feasibility of implementing a shared geological repository in Europe	www.erdo-wg.com						
13	EUR organisation	EU	UT	European utility requirements for LWR NPPs	www.europeanutilityrequirements.org						
14	EURADSCIENCE	EU	RE	International network of research organisations in the field of RWM. Independent, cross-disciplinary, inclusive network ensuring scientific excellence and credibility to RWM.	none						
15	FinNuclear Association	Finland		promote Finnish companies' general preconditions, cooperation, competences, international profile in manufacturing, construction and service activities in the nuclear energy field.	https://finnuclear.fi/en/home-2/						
				Trade association for nuclear energy industry in Europe. Membership is							

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	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
	Organisation	Country/Region	Actor type	Short description	Website	Consortium Partner with contact	must have	nice to have	not relevant	sent out the email to whom -	registered as stakeholder Y/N
1				technology							
5											
6	BMK Federal ministry of climate action, environment, energy, mobility, innovation and technology	Austria	government	ministry of environment	https://www.bmk.gv.at/en.html						
7	Friends of the Earth Europe	Austria	Environmental NGO	International environmental network	https://friendsoftheearth.eu/						
8	NUCCON gmbh	Austria									
9	Nuclear Engineering Seibersdorf (NES)	Austria	WMO	Nuclear Engineering Seibersdorf GmbH (NES). Collection, processing, conditioning and storage of radioactive waste and the decontamination and decommissioning (dismantling) of nuclear facilities	https://www.nes.at/			x			
10	Women in Nuclear	Austria	nonprofit	Women in Nuclear Global (WiN Global)	https://win-global.org/						
11	Belgonucléaire	Belgium	Fuel producer	Former Belgian production plant for nuclear fuel, producer of MOX nuclear fuel	not available		x				
12	Belgoproprocess	Belgium	Nuclear Services, operator, waste processing	Industrial daughter company of NIRAS (WMO)	https://www.belgoproprocess.be/eng/index.htm	sck cen	x				
	Bel-V	Belgium	TSO	TSO, subsidiary of FANC	https://belv.be/index.p	sck cen	x				

Figure 2: screenshot of the excel with identified stakeholder networks (top) and individual organisations (bottom).

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A general email template (Figure 3) was created which was used to i) contact individual Stakeholders and ii) to send to representatives of Stakeholder networks to further disseminate into their network. The email shortly introduced the project and the opportunity to register as a Stakeholder through a webform (<https://www.harpers-h2020.eu/stakeholder-engagement.html>) (see Figure 4) on the [HARPERS website](#) (Milestone MS3).

Partners were encouraged to tailor the template email to the Stakeholder being contacted. Any alterations made have not been centrally recorded.

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Dear,

With this letter, we would like to introduce a new Euratom/Horizon Europe project which might be of interest for you and your organisation. The project is named "HARPERS: HARmonised PracticEs, Regulations and Standards in waste management and decommissioning". We hope you will register to be part of the voluntary group of stakeholders, to guide the direction of the project. Registration as a stakeholder is possible through the [HARPERS website \(https://www.harpers-h2020.eu/stakeholder-engagement.html\)](https://www.harpers-h2020.eu/stakeholder-engagement.html).

The 3-year HARPERS project aims to establish and clarify the benefits and added value of more aligned and harmonised regulations, practices and standards in decommissioning and radioactive waste management between Member States. Specifically, with regard to cross border services/facilities, moving to a circular economy and implementation of advanced technologies. The project will identify relevant regulatory differences across Member States, assess the rationale for the identified regulatory differences and establish the potential for their harmonisation.

The HARPERS project has a two-phase approach: the first phase/year will be focused on engaging with Stakeholders to assess needs and pros/cons for harmonisation and identify priority areas for deeper analysis in Phase 2 over the next two years. The final selection of these priority areas will be based on a transparent approach considering stakeholder prioritisation, relevance for the European community (economic potential, volume of waste, number of countries involved) and achievability. The second phase will pursue deeper engagement with Stakeholders to further assess the highest ranked priority areas (identified in Phase 1) in Work Packages (WP) focusing on (i) cross border services and cooperation (WP3), (ii) circular economy (WP4), and (iii) advanced technologies (WP5). These WPs will review (inter)national practices, capture lessons learned, and assess opportunities. WP6 on Regulatory Framework will identify regulatory differences between MS and evaluate strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats associated with harmonisation, while quantifying the benefits of aligned regulations and proposing harmonisation methodologies.

To supplement the strong consortium expertise, the project also includes a mechanism to provide financial support to third parties (in the stakeholder community) through open calls to contribute in Phase 2. Being part of the stakeholder group will give you access to these potential funding opportunities.

As the outcome of the project will greatly depend on the interaction with the stakeholder community, it is key for the project to establish this stakeholder community early in the project. As you or your organization are listed as stakeholder of one of the projects/networks (PREDIS, EURAD, SHARE, SNETP, NEA, IGDTP, IAEA, ENSREG, ERDO, DigiDecom, ...) which is in close contact with HARPERS, we would like to draw your attention to the opportunities presented by this project, and we kindly request that you consider participating in the project as a stakeholder.

Interested stakeholders can opt for active participation in the project, which entails joining webinars, discussion sessions, surveys ... to help define in Phase 1 the priority areas which will be further developed in Phase 2. Active participation as third party in Phase 2 is possible as well. The project can also be engaged with less actively by staying informed on its progress through newsletters and access to public deliverables. All of these options will be available to registered stakeholders.

We anticipate a series of 3-6 free webinars with stakeholders starting in October 2022, thus it is critical to get your registration during the next few weeks. Registration can be done very simply and easily via the [HARPERS website \(https://www.harpers-h2020.eu/stakeholder-engagement.html\)](https://www.harpers-h2020.eu/stakeholder-engagement.html) with no additional steps required. If you would like us to join one of your meetings for a short presentation on the HARPERS project and gathering your feedback, just let us know when and where. We hope to welcome you as a stakeholder during one of the upcoming HARPERS events!

Figure 3: template email used to send to potential Stakeholders asking to register as Stakeholder.

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Stakeholders can register either:

- to be kept informed,
- to actively participate in discussions on identification and prioritisation of topics for the different “technical” work packages,
- interested 3rd party to contribute in Phase 2.

ENEA manages the registration of stakeholders and disseminates on a regular basis a list of the registered stakeholders to the project partners, taking account of GDPR rules (a SH list with all details is stored in a restricted area on Sharepoint to comply with GDPR rules).

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You are here: Home / Stakeholder Engagement

Stakeholder Engagement

The HARPERS project aims to establish and clarify the benefits and added value of more aligned and harmonised regulations and standards for prioritised topics related to decommissioning and initial phases of radioactive waste handling, including shared processing facilities between Member States (MS).

The project has a two-phase approach: first engaging with stakeholders to assess needs and pros/cons for harmonisation and identify priority areas for deeper analysis (WP2). Phase 2 will pursue deeper engagement with Stakeholders to further assess the highest ranked priority areas (defined in WP2 in the phase 1) in Work Packages (WP) focusing on

- (i) cross border services and cooperation (WP3),
- (ii) circular economy (WP4), and
- (iii) advanced technologies (WP5).

These WPs will review (inter)national practices, capture lessons learned, and assess opportunities. Third parties will be able to contribute to the selected topics through open calls.

WPG on Regulatory Framework will identify regulatory differences between MS and evaluate strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats associated with harmonisation, while quantifying the benefits of aligned regulations and proposing harmonisation methodologies.

This form aims to establish the stakeholder community with which the project will further engage to assess needs and pros/cons for harmonisation and identify priority areas for deeper analysis.

What is the nature of your business? (*)

- waste producer
- waste owner
- waste management organization
- regulator
- research entity
- supply industry
- international organisation
- other

Organisation (*)

First Name (*)

Last Name (*)

Email address (*)

- We prefer to be informed (= receiving the newsletter and access to public deliverables)
- We prefer to be actively involved in the project (discussing the topics and their prioritization for Phase 2) for following work packages
- We are interested in contributing as third party to the technical WP's through the open calls
- Consent to the processing of personal data. [More details about the Privacy](#)

(*)

This project has received funding from the Euratom research and training programme 2021-27 under grant agreement No 101060028.

Figure 4: Screenshot of the stakeholder engagement form on the HARPERS website (<https://www.harpers-h2020.eu/stakeholder-engagement.html>).

3 Performing a gap analysis to identify priority areas

Parallel to the development of a stakeholder community an analysis of drivers and barriers towards the optimisation of decommissioning and waste management activities on a Europe-wide basis was made in order to define priority areas.

This process is done in 4 steps and in collaboration with the leads of the technical work packages (WP3/4/5) as depicted in the scheme in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Schematic representation of the different steps in the development and analysis of the survey to identify priority areas.

The first 3 steps are performed by the project partners and serve as a basis for the engagement with the stakeholder community.

3.1 Gap analysis

In order to identify priority areas related to the objectives of the project, we started by performing an extensive “gap analysis” by consulting available relevant documentation like Strategic Research Agenda’s (SRA), State of the Art reports (SOTA), position papers, surveys,... that find often their origin in the networks and organisations identified as potential stakeholders.

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As a first step, a list of potential information sources is compiled (through a spreadsheet on SharePoint, Figure 6), presenting relevant organisations, associations, projects, initiatives with links to published reports/documentation.

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N
N°	Organisation	Country/Reg.	Size/Weight	Actor type	Short description	Notes / context	Website	Link to SRA / related documents	Relevant to HARPERS gap analysis?	Priority for HARPERS gap analysis	Assignment of HARPERS partner for gap analysis review	Sharepoint link to gap analysis review	Sharepoint link to reviewed document(s)
68	SCK,CEN/ONDU lessons learned report	Global	M	TSO	on communication related to decommissioning of NPP This internal report is OK to be analysed by SCK/CEN International network of research organisations in the field of RWM. Independent, cross-disciplinary, inclusive network ensuring scientific excellence and credibility to RivM.	for communication of D&D from existing projects and a dedicated workshop	ROMA (SCK,CEN)	none?	Y	M	SCK CEN & MERIENCE		
4	EURADSCIENCE	EU	H	RE	International network of research organisations in the field of RWM. Independent, cross-disciplinary, inclusive network ensuring scientific excellence and credibility to RivM.	RE actor group in EURAD. "Birthplace" of PREDIS consortium.	none	none	Y	H	SCKCEN	HARPERS gap analysis EUR SRA RE draft 0_4.docx	
9	H2020 EURAD	EU	M	AI	European Joint Programme on Radioactive waste management	Predisposal strongly influences several aspects of the GDF	https://www.epc-stcr.nl/	https://www.epc-stcr.eu/sites/default/files/2020-01/2020-01-20_eurad_sra.pdf	Y - recommendations emerging from individual work packages should be captured, so these are also listed separately	H	SCKCEN	HARPERS gap analysis EUR 2_eurad_sra.pdf	
45	H2020 JORRAD	EU	M	AI	Joint Programming on Radioactive Waste Disposal	brought together concern geological disposal of spent fuel and other high activity long lived radioactive waste, including waste management	http://www.jorrad.eu/	http://www.jorrad.eu/zhainma/Document/JORRAD_Deliverable/JORRAD_WP4_D4.4-Programme_Docum	have already been factored into subsequent joint programming /	M	SCKCEN	JORSAD-2017-12-D4.4-Programme_Document_Final.pdf	

Figure 6: Screenshot of the Excel file where potential sources for relevant documentation for the gap analysis was gathered.

The partners of the HARPERS project were engaged in i) populating the list and ii) performing the analysis of the sources. Over 50 sources were identified as warranting review.

Assignment to review the sources was based on: i) familiarity with the source (e.g., through involvement in associated projects), ii) spreading review efforts across all partners, iii) anticipate differences in level of effort required for reviewing different sources (volume of source material and relevance), iv) related sources, likely to give rise to similar or overlapping recommendations.

A template was created to gather in a consistent way the review of documents (Figure 7).

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Source <i>from spreadsheet Column B</i>	Document title <i>e.g., from spreadsheet Columns H / I</i>	Document reference	URL link <i>(if available)</i>	Document type <i>e.g., SRA, final report, deliverable, website,....</i>	Reviewer name	Reviewer organisation	Date reviewed

Source material		Interpretation					
Document section	Recommendation, need, observation or opportunity <i>Copy and paste in original form</i>	Summary of recommendation <i>For onward consideration in HARPERS</i>	Type of driver(s) <i>Technological, regulatory, economical, societal, legal, environmental, and/or harmonisation</i>	Relevance score for HARPERS <i>(High/Medium/Low)</i>	Basis for relevance score	Relevant HARPERS WP(s) <i>(3-6)</i>	Other comments

Figure 7: Layout of template used to gather the reviews by partners of identified sources for the gap analysis.

The reviewers were provided with following guidelines:

Introduction: This template is to be used by partners to record inputs to the HARPERS gap analysis of recommendations and needs relating to:

- Drivers and barriers to alignment and harmonisation of regulations, practices and standards in decommissioning and waste management across Europe.
- Opportunities for, and obstacles to, shared waste processing, storage and disposal between Member States.

Scope: HARPERS aims to establish and clarify the benefits and added-value of more aligned and harmonised regulations and standards for prioritised topics related to decommissioning and initial phases of radioactive waste handling, to identify the relevant regulatory differences across Member States, assess the rationale for the identified regulatory differences and establish the potential for their harmonisation relative to cross-border services / facilities for radioactive waste management, moving to a circular economy in RWM and implementation of advanced technologies in RWM.

With this in mind, recommendations and needs relating to the following are in scope:

- All classes of radioactive waste (and also spent fuel, since this is considered a waste in some countries).
- Decommissioning.
- Pre-disposal.
- Long-term management (storage and disposal – both near-surface and at depth).

Consideration of conventional waste falls outside the scope of the project. However, challenges associated with the non-radiological properties of radioactive wastes would be in scope; for example, issues relating to chemotoxicity, and conflicts between regulatory requirements applicable to radioactive waste and those more broadly applicable to all wastes.

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Approach to review: A list of sources for the gap analysis has been produced, and partners have been assigned to review each source.

The list identifies obvious documents for review where they were immediately apparent during its compilation. However, many entries are for projects, associations or initiatives, and do not always identify specific documents for review. Where this is the case, the reviewing partner(s) should decide upon the most appropriate materials to draw on (e.g., deliverables, final reports, websites, ...) in order to identify any recommendations of relevance to the forward HARPERS work programme. In some cases, it could be useful to correspond with project representatives / coordinators in order to confirm the best approach.

Reviewers should identify relevant documents or other materials associated with the sources they are reviewing, extract recommendations and needs pertaining to the HARPERS project scope, and copy them into the accompanying template. A separate template should be completed for each document reviewed, with a separate entry being made in the template for each section extracted and copied. The fields above are to be completed as follows:

Source: Enter the organisation, project, association or other initiative listed in Column B of the spreadsheet listing sources for the gap analysis.

Document title: Enter the title of the document or other material from which recommendations and needs have been extracted. In many cases, this may be drawn from Columns H or I of the spreadsheet listing sources for the gap analysis.

Document reference: Enter the reference number of the document reviewed.

URL link: If available, provide a web address indicating where the document or other material can be found online.

Document type: Enter the type of document or other material being reviewed, e.g., SRA, roadmap, deliverable, website etc.

Reviewer name: Enter the name of the person(s) reviewing the document.

Reviewer organisation/affiliation: Enter the name of the organisation(s) for the person(s) undertaking the review.

Date reviewed: Enter the completion date of the review.

Document section: Enter the section number from the document being reviewed for the specific text being extracted.

Recommendation, need, observation or opportunity: Copy and paste the relevant text from the document, in its original form. This will allow wider partners to refer back to this, if needed, in subsequent analysis.

Summary of recommendation: Briefly summarise (one sentence, if possible) the recommendation / need in a manner suitable for dissemination and onward consideration in HARPERS.

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Type of driver(s): Indicate the type of driver(s) underpinning the recommendation / need, e.g., technological, regulatory, economical, societal, legal, environmental, and/or desire for harmonisation.

Relevance score for HARPERS (High/Medium/Low): Enter H, M or L depending on how relevant the recommendation / need is to the aims of the HARPERS project. This is a subjective assessment based on the opinion of the reviewer.

Basis for relevance score: Briefly indicate why the above relevance score was assigned.

Relevant HARPERS WP(s): Indicate the HARPERS Work Package(s) (3-6) for which the recommendation / need has greatest relevance. This may be used to help direct its integration in WP-specific stakeholder engagement activities.

Other comments: Enter any other comments you wish to make (e.g., basis for the extracted text being selected; any limitations on applicability in different countries, whether the recommendation / need is also being captured elsewhere, outside of HARPERS...).

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69 sources from 38 projects were reviewed. The outputs of the reviews were compiled in a master document (>80 pg., see Annex I). Shorter tables for each WP were also produced, containing only the outputs deemed by the reviewer to be relevant to that WP. The master document and shorter tables were made available to the partners on SharePoint.

In step 3 of the process, the outcome of the gap analysis is analysed by the WP3 (Cross border service/facility), WP4 (Circular Economy) and WP5 (Advanced Technologies) leads who combined/integrated this input with an initial list of “needs and opportunities” that formed the basis of their respective WP description during development of the project.¹

3.2 Preparation of list of thematic questions and topics

As mentioned above, some challenges and needs were identified during the proposal phase of the HARPERS project. These challenges and needs were all directly related to particular WPs.

A final list of thematic questions and topics was prepared for each WP, based on the recommendations of the gap analysis and the suggestions of project partners obtained during internal discussions within the WP. This is presented in terms of what the challenge/need is, why it is needed, any additional comments and the origin of the topic (audit trail) and if they were considered to move/exclude from further discussion with SH community. Topics were also grouped into categories.

These lists were published internally as Milestones MS 8-9-10.

¹ HARPERS proposal Template Part B (correct name to be checked)

Work methodologies: Methods for identification and prioritisation of topics

3.2.1 WP3 Cross border services/facilities - List of thematic questions for Phase 1

Work package 3 aims to identify the most important needs and challenges for Cross Border Services/Facilities for radioactive waste management activities across Europe.

Task 3.1 is focused on the prioritisation of needs and opportunities for cross-border service/facility considerations (Phase 1a) to define themes to be proposed for deeper analysis in Phase 2.

The challenges and needs identified in the proposal phase were discussed with the WP3 team members in November 2022. In addition, the Gap Analysis was conducted within the framework of WP2, as discussed above.

The first list of challenges and needs has been integrated with suggestions and comments from WP3 Partners and with the recommendations extracted from the gap analysis.

The final list was then grouped in 3 main topics covering *Best Practice/Harmonisation*, *Technical Challenges*, and *Geological Disposal Facility (GDF)* that are summarised in Tables 1-3, where the different challenges/needs/issues/recommendations are reported together with their origin.

The topics were discussed within WP3 and for each of them it was agreed to include or to exclude it from the further discussion with the Stakeholder community (as reported in the last column of the table). Feedback from the Stakeholders will be used alongside a selection methodology to define the Needs/Challenges to be taken forward in the HARPERS project. This will help to ensure that the topics are well defined and take consideration of any specific areas/activities in their execution in the project such as technical/technology, regulatory, social sciences and other aspects needed.

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Best Practice/Harmonisation

WHAT (Challenge/Need)	WHY?	Comments	Origin	To discuss with Stakeholders
Harmonisation of Individual EU and international countries Problematic waste inventory	Provides EU with data to produce a strategy to efficiently treat problematic wastes before long term storage. This should focus on problematic or challenging wastes that do not have a treatment solution already.	Review found is needed/relevant in general. Benefits might be magnified for smaller waste forms (e.g., Problematic waste). The "ROUTES" work package of the EURAD task 2 deliverables might be useful. Deliverable 9.12 of EURAD ROUTES might provide quantitative data.	Proposal	Yes
Harmonise the application of international and EU safety standards between Member States (MS)	MS have local rules and regulations over and above Euratom requirements and in understanding the differences we can identify opportunities to increase Trans-frontier EU waste treatment.	This challenge crossed over with WP6 and it is best suited for inclusion that that WP. Waste Acceptance Criteria (WAC) data from disposal sites could be useful for the challenge. Radiological impact of the waste must be comparable to the starting radiological properties/characteristics of the waste before treatment. With that said, each MS must have the right to undertake trans-frontier waste treatment. The differences in safety standards will also be demonstrated through the different disposal solutions and local conditions in MS. It is important to keep this Challenge/Need focused and it is suggested that it covers Characterisation or recycling/release elements only.	Proposal	No
What services are wanted/what is the benefit of	Inventory harmonisation can lead to increased treatment opportunities.	The waste hierarchy needs to be used across MS and in addition the need for sustainability provides a guideline for the	Proposal	Yes

Work methodologies: Methods for identification and prioritisation of topics

WHAT (Challenge/Need)	WHY?	Comments	Origin	To discuss with Stakeholders
centralised treatment facilities.		utilization of centralised waste treatment facilities/services. Analysis is required to demonstrate this need vs building smaller local facilities covering environmental, public benefit, service provides and financial drivers.		
Economical: Centralised vs decentralised characterisation and waste treatment review.	Harmonisation of packaging or treatment across EU will lead to economic and storage benefits.	<p>Funding cycles in the MS are diffident and therefore it is harder to justify/fund one off buildings (e.g., waste treatment facilities). In addition, waste arisings/inventory will provide return on investment challenges for MS's for the smaller waste producers/owners.</p> <p>This is an issue where the smaller amounts of waste are concerned and where there are fewer nuclear activities in a MS. Where these conditions are present this challenge/need brings more value.</p> <p>If a standard approach to characterisation data can be adopted, then this will bring economic benefits to MS and improve cross border waste treatment. Noting that this is only if there is the possibility for centralized facilities as some MS cannot have their own facilities, so it is not possible to compare centralized vs decentralized (e.g., incineration).</p>	Proposal	Yes
Standardisation of quality control of suppliers and waste packages	If a standard QC process for waste packages is agreed across the EU, this will reduce mis consignments etc.	QC standardization is different in each MS and QC can sometimes target different things. Transport regulations between MS are well understood and work well enough,	Proposal	Yes

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WHAT (Challenge/Need)	WHY?	Comments	Origin	To discuss with Stakeholders
		however each MS asks for different information regarding the waste.		
Reducing the barriers in export and transportation	Not all MS implement the transport regulations in the same way, and this causes delays due to administration burden etc.	Following a discussion with the WP3 team, it was noted that the documentation required for export and transportation is not prohibitive and all have learned, or can learn, to abide with these.	Proposal	No
MS approach to dealing with radioactive contaminated hazardous waste differs	Emerging Radioactive contaminated hazardous waste streams may require cross border technical solutions.	Radioactive waste streams which also have hazardous waste properties can prove challenging to identify management solutions for all MS. This topic excludes conventional wastes. This is a particular issue where the smaller amounts of waste are concerned and where there are fewer nuclear activities in a MS. Where these conditions result in a small inventory of challenging waste to be managed this need brings more value.	Proposal	Yes
Share operational/regulator feedback (both good and bad) from waste treatment facilities.	Gathering data from waste management facilities will improve new facility or services lines.	Regulator feedback which gives rise to learning from past projects is positive. There are two elements to this work: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Sharing feedback – key to all challenges/needs 2) Exploring what are the platforms/forums for sharing information between the MS/ waste treatment organisations. <p>Element 2) links into EURAD and these are valuable to all MS.</p>	Proposal	Yes

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WHAT (Challenge/Need)	WHY?	Comments	Origin	To discuss with Stakeholders
<p>To align wastes with treatment technologies in a manner acceptable to all stakeholders.</p>	<p>A common understanding of the suitability of treatment options for different waste types is required to establish new shared waste processing opportunities. Noting that stakeholders may have differing views on the suitability of treatment options for certain wastes.</p>		<p>Gap Analysis</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>A need for a common approach for defining reference protocol and experimental conditions on assessment of the durability and stability of conditioned waste.</p>	<p>Standardization of test protocols for determining conditioning matrix performance could lead to increased used of specific conditioning technologies.</p>	<p>This need/challenge is more focused on technology and not necessarily supporting cross border services/facilities. Therefore, we propose it is included in WP5's activities as required.</p>	<p>Gap Analysis</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>A need for a common system for waste classification.</p>	<p>Developing a common system for waste classification is a preliminary harmonization action. Could lead to implementation of potential cross-border services.</p>		<p>Gap Analysis</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Encouragement in cooperation to improve the</p>	<p>Public perception of cross border waste treatment varies between MS</p>	<p>There is a need for encouraging technical cooperation and public involvement. The cultural factor may impact</p>	<p>Gap Analysis</p>	<p>Yes.</p>

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WHAT (Challenge/Need)	WHY?	Comments	Origin	To discuss with Stakeholders
safe management of radioactive wastes through building public trust and confidence in the decision-making process for hosting waste treatment facilities.	and the benefits to the community that cross border services facilities can bring could result in further cultural benefits to society.	harmonisation efforts. Applying recognized techniques facilitates harmonisation allowing common benefit.		

Table 1 – WP3 identified topics related to Best Practice/Harmonisation Needs and Challenges

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Technical Challenges

WHAT (Challenge/Need)	WHY?	Comments	Origin	To discuss with Stakeholders
Modernisation of waste transfer and export processes (e.g., Digitalisation).	Current process is slow and inefficient causing delays and cost increases.	Whilst digitalization will improve record keeping, it is not deemed as a prohibitive step for cross border waste treatment facilities/services.	Proposal	No
Methods of waste characterisation for declaration (transportation, treatment).	Declarations are sometimes unclear or not trusted, harmonisation of approaches/standards could be used to overcome this.	<p>Visibility of waste characterization data before and after treatment are important in establishing cross border treatment facilities/services.</p> <p>For most MS there appears to be a need for a common understanding (or even better acceptance) of which nuclides are of importance for different activities. In addition, it would be beneficial to harmonise what uncertainty in data for those can be accepted without violating WACs, transport, treatment, disposal etc. This would provide substantial value and remove lengthy discussions, that currently, are ongoing in many organizations.</p> <p>How the data is presented in the forms for characterisation.</p> <p>Challenge is more to harmonise the data/forms used.</p>	Proposal	Yes
Identify gaps & opportunities in current treatment facility	Holistic review of existing facilities will demonstrate a need for additional facilities and identify possible locations based on inventory and possible	Problematic waste forms would be suitable for these areas of study. Issues include how you go about considering a candidate country for hosting the waste treatment facility, identification of possible locations.	Proposal	Yes

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needs/operations (Cross-border or mobile/modular).	provision of common treatment and conditioning schemes.			
Identify common EU challenging materials and waste streams.	Country by Country review of waste streams will underpin a strategy for future cross border treatment facilities.	Identifying the common waste forms, will then lead us to be able to present possible solutions to MS and thereby develop activities to ensure that MS and the public are engaged to resolve challenging waste treatments.	Proposal	Yes

Table 2 – WP3 identified topics related to Technical Needs and Challenges

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Geological Disposal Facility (GDF) and Waste Storage Facilities

WHAT (Challenge/Need)	WHY?	Comments	Origin	To discuss with Stakeholders
Collate MS GDF strategies/needs and data to identify possible shared solutions/facilities.	GDF consideration on a national scale may be inefficient depending on countries waste forecast and alternative cross border strategies might provide benefits.	This challenge/need does not bring anything new to existing EU initiatives, for example the ROUTES project for EURAD.	Proposal	No
Standardise GDF and interim costing approach across MS.	Underpinning of GDF budgets necessary to standardise the EU GDF approach and requirements and might sign post to centralised facility needs.	<p>A common understanding of costs related to waste, both interim and final disposal cost as well as decommissioning costs could improve the accuracy and drive cost efficient solutions for the MS.</p> <p>Different MS have different financial solutions (how to finance) to waste and decom activities. This may need to be reflected.</p> <p>Although national GDF solutions are more economically demanding than centralized solutions, they also help maintain the capacities of highly qualified workplaces and specialists in the countries. This is a key element of work for any future development of this need/challenge.</p>	Proposal	Yes
Sharing of intermediate waste storage facilities between MS.	Not all MS will/should have intermediate storage facilities if their inventories are small or there are additional benefits for all MS to share intermediate storage facilities.	<p>This might not be required for all MS, but for MS with smaller inventories this could be a realistic opportunity. Therefore, we would need to review the related standards, approaches, and requirements applied in the relevant MS.</p> <p>An example of shared waste disposal sites in Slovenia which have reviewed and established the necessary characterisation works to</p>	Gap Analysis	Yes

Work methodologies: Methods for identification and prioritisation of topics

		allow for the accurate definition of WAC's suitable for the nuclide present, which in turn has established suitable waste storage facilities for both Slovenian and other counties wastes.		
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Table 3 – WP3 identified topics related to GDF Needs and Challenges

Work methodologies: Methods for identification and prioritisation of topics

3.2.2 WP4 Circular economy - List of thematic questions for Phase 1

Work package 4 aims to identify the most important conditions and opportunities for promoting circular economy when managing materials and waste coming from nuclear decommissioning across Europe.

Task 4.1 is focused on the prioritisation of needs and opportunities for circular economy considerations (Phase 1a) to define themes to be proposed for deeper analysis in Phase 2.

The challenges and needs identified in the proposal phase were discussed with the WP4 team members. In addition, the Gap Analysis was conducted within the framework of WP2, as discussed above.

The first list of challenges and needs has been integrated with suggestions and comments from WP4 Partners and with the recommendations extracted from the gap analysis.

The final list (table 5) was then grouped into 8 main topics that are summarised in the following table where the different challenges/needs/issues/recommendations are reported together with their origin.

The topics were discussed within WP4 and for each of them it was agreed to move on or to exclude it from the further discussion with the Stakeholder Community (as reported in the last column of the table).

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TOPIC	WHAT (Challenge/Need)	WHY	Origin	To discuss with SH
INVENTORY	Common waste and radioactive materials recyclable or reusable	Surveying to find common issues for harmonised approach	Proposal	YES
	Classification and management of hazardous waste - link with European Green Deal (Circular Economy Action Plan) and the Waste Regulation	Maintain clean recycling streams and increase the confidence in using secondary raw materials	WP4 discussion	
	Harmonised system to classify waste to promote circularity Inventory management as a prerequisite for circular economy	Optimising the routing of the material towards re-use and recycling will minimise the radioactive waste inventory and preserve natural resources as well as reduce the environmental impact	Gap Analysis	
CLEARANCE	Free release of waste and materials arising from decommissioning (framework for clearance and regulatory discrepancies)	Minimise waste to be disposed of. Optimising the routing of the material towards re-use and recycling will minimise the radioactive waste inventory and preserve natural resources as well as reduce the environmental impact	Proposal	YES
	Framework for clearance Harmonised regulations to enable recycling Unconditional clearance: use of general limits Conditional clearance: no international guidance but only national and site-specific Clearance of very lightly contaminated liquids	Promote reuse (for free release) Promote recycling in nuclear and non-nuclear field for conditional clearance	Gap Analysis	
SUSTAINABLE MATERIALS	Identification of materials that could be replaced with alternative materials	Promote and develop sustainable and bio-friendly materials	Proposal	NO <i>Not relevant for WP4 scope</i>
	Reduction of raw material consumption	Promote resource efficiency and more competitive and sustainable economy	Proposal	
	For new design reactors Recycled materials (e.g. geopolymers) for waste conditioning		Gap Analysis	
RECYCLING AND REUSE	R&D for new technologies for recovery, recycling and reusing of materials	Increase efficiency / reduce cost	Proposal	YES
	Material recycling	Improve environmental sustainability (preserve natural resources). Create a system for by-products and raw materials exchange between nuclear facilities' waste generators and potential end-users (industrial symbiosis approach).	Proposal + WP4 discussion	

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TOPIC	WHAT (Challenge/Need)	WHY	Origin	To discuss with SH
	Create markets for recycled materials	Further promote recycling of materials and reduce costs	Proposal + WP4 discussion	
	Reuse of structure, systems and components (including reuse of the site)	Minimise waste and recover and reuse valuable materials	Proposal	
	Available technologies and circular economy approaches already implemented in non-nuclear field	Gain information and lessons learned for a more sustainable decommissioning	Proposal	
	Identification of criteria for material reusing (e.g. quality, durability, ...) - focused on material physico-chemical characteristics	Promote material reusing and reduce generation of waste	WP4 discussion	
	Recycled materials traceability	Harmonised systems to track and manage information on recycled materials	WP4 discussion	
	Quality assessment of recycled materials (in comparison with a new one)	Promote use and create market for recycled materials	WP4 discussion	
	Public expectation / constraint, transparency and engagement around reusing and recycling	Raising public awareness on circular economy issues + societal engagement to enable recycling	WP4 discussion	
	Reuse and recycle issues: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regulatory and licensing: compliance of the option with the applicable regulation (including clearance and specific criteria for recycling); Technical and operational: availability of technology and facilities to process waste; Safety and ALARA; Economic and schedule: costs, duration of implementation of solutions; Public acceptance and stakeholder Reuse of available infrastructure Enable routes for cleared wastes (e.g. metals) Benchmarking of technology for recycling and reuse		Gap Analysis	
TECHNOLOGIES FOR MATERIAL AND WASTE TREATMENT	Benchmarking of technologies and facilities for radioactive material and waste treatment	Create a widespread and structured system of technologies/facilities to be more effective	Proposal	YES
	Mobile system to reduce environmental impact and enable reuse and recycling Optimisation of treatment technologies (e.g. decontamination) to minimise waste and facilitate reuse and recycling		Gap Analysis	

Work methodologies: Methods for identification and prioritisation of topics

TOPIC	WHAT (Challenge/Need)	WHY	Origin	To discuss with SH
MULTI CRITERIA ANALYSIS OF STRATEGIES	Digital tools and advanced technologies to support decision making processes and circular economy principles	Facilitate quick decision making and optimise decommissioning, waste management and radiation protection.	Proposal	YES
	Socio-economical assessments of the different strategies envisaged (linear vs circular)	Cost-benefit analysis to evaluate the option of reuse and recycle and facilitate decision making	WP4 discussion	
	Multicriteria decision making for final end-state Cost-benefit in reuse and recycle		Gap Analysis	
CHARACTERISATION	Prerequisite for circular economy Facilities for free release Conservative clearance standards can still be a challenge Regulatory requirements could consider different approaches: e.g., statistical approaches	Enhance flexibility on characterisation approaches to be used for material clearance	Gap Analysis	YES
TRANSVERSAL	Societal/Public constraints/expectation Sharing good practices Regulatory engagement Knowledge Management and Training Various Stakeholder integration		Gap Analysis	YES <i>To be considered for all the topics</i>

Table 4 – WP4 identified priority areas and topics

Work methodologies: Methods for identification and prioritisation of topics

3.2.3 WP5 Advanced Technologies - List of thematic questions for Phase 1

Work package 5 aims to:

- evaluate the regulatory implications of using advanced technologies in waste management and decommissioning,
- identify opportunities for harmonisation of standards across MS
- and investigate and conclude on the needs and benefits of the adoption and standardisation of advanced technologies to enhance waste management and decommissioning operations in Europe.

Task 5.1 is focused on the prioritisation of needs and opportunities in advanced technologies (Phase 1a) to support increased acceptance and use of existing cutting-edge technologies and tools. Top priority themes will be selected through expert discussions, analysis of information and engagement with stakeholders for future detailed analysis in Phase 2.

The list of challenges and needs identified in the proposal phase were discussed with WP5 Partners. This list was then updated to address comments from Partners and then integrated with the results of the gap analysis performed in WP2.

The resulting thematic topics are summarised in Table 6. This is presented in terms of what the challenge/need is, why this is the case, any additional comments and the origin of the topic. Topics were also grouped into three categories: Waste Treatment, Automation and Robotics, Digitalisation.

Other cross-cutting issues noted from the Gap Analysis were:

- The level of understanding/knowledge regarding complex and new technologies by different stakeholders is a potential barrier to their use.
- Harmonisation of regulatory standards and procedures for D&D may be a barrier for flexibility and innovations, therefore it may be more important to harmonise on general principles.

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	What? Challenge/Need	Why?	Comments	Origin
Waste treatment				
1	New technologies for decontamination of buildings and environmental restoration	To optimise and reduce the volume and categories of waste generated by concrete structures to be decontaminated and soils to be excavated		Proposal + Gap Analysis
2	Adoption of advanced manufacturing techniques including additive manufacturing	The use of rapid prototype /manufacturing techniques to allow for the early adoption of innovative solutions in the production of wasteforms		Proposal + Gap Analysis
3	New waste treatment and immobilisation technologies	To reduce waste volumes and enhance waste-form performance. To handle difficult to treat wastes		Proposal + Gap Analysis
4	Harmonised waste-form assessment protocols	To streamline innovation in and adoption of new waste processing technologies.		Proposal + Gap Analysis
5	Remote in-situ characterisation / non contact or non-destructive evaluation	To understand the nature of plant and waste. To reduce uncertainty in inventory, informing waste management & decommissioning strategies, decisions and appropriate automated material sentencing, including clearance of materials.		Proposal + Gap Analysis
6	Standards for mobile treatment systems	To allow cross-facility and cross-border use of treatment technologies. Supporting small inventory users. Enable cost-effective and flexible systems.		Gap Analysis

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	What? Challenge/Need	Why?	Comments	Origin
Automation and Robotics				
7	'Standardised' DTw and BIM technology, to predict the performance of systems, plant, processes and packages	To enable virtual engineering to optimise decommissioning and waste management activities, through predictive modelling. To keep relevant data up to date taking into account the real progress of decommissioning works.		Proposal + Gap Analysis
8	Adoption of robotics in decommissioning planning, dismantling and waste management – new technology in nuclear environments e.g. (semi) autonomous systems, AI focused technologies, exoskeletons, wearable technology, augmented reality, are new regulatory challenges	Removing workers from hazardous exposure. Automation to reduce cost and schedule.		Proposal + Gap Analysis
9	Automation of waste sorting, segregation, sentencing and packaging.	To enhance safety and deliver efficiency gains through automation. Reduced worker exposure - ALARP.	Links into understanding of plant and wastes	Proposal + Gap Analysis
10	Automation of waste stores, learning from advanced digital logistics practice.	To enhance efficient waste and inventory management and safeguarding.	Links into PREDIS WP7	Proposal
11	Smart decontamination techniques - targeting contamination through sensing, local decontamination and removal of the hazard from the system.	To remove the hazard from the plant, allowing safe, but more flexible, faster, cheaper approaches to dismantling	Links with new decommissioning technologies. Brings together decontamination and characterisation technologies.	Proposal

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	What? Challenge/Need	Why?	Comments	Origin
Digitalisation				
12	Application of advanced building information management systems to nuclear plants	To facilitate lifetime plant and waste operations, knowledge management and data retention.		Proposal + Gap Analysis
13	Standardisation of protocols for security of data and data transfer, including cyber security and segregation	To enable use of new IT solutions, and data transfer between smart devices		Proposal
14	Standardisation of digital architecture and frameworks - common human machine interface (HMI)	To allow for the cross connectivity of digital and automation tools – ‘plug and play’ and to allow and transfer between software packages. Standard HMI also aids mobility of staff between activities.		Proposal
15	Automation of site mapping – coupling the use of sensors, Geographical Information Systems (GIS) and deployment methods (UAV, land based automated vehicles etc).	Provides data for management and regulatory oversight. To facilitate efficient site mapping for radiological contamination, interpretation through modelling including Enhanced Natural Attenuation models.		Proposal
16	Standardisation of 3D modelling protocols	To allow easy transition between platforms (platform independent)		Gap Analysis

Table 5 – WP5 identified priority areas and topics

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3.3 Selection criteria for prioritisation

A further selection/prioritisation will be done from the defined Priority areas and topics (Tables 1-6), for future detailed analysis in Phase 2 of the HARPERS project. This will be done through expert discussions, analysis of information and engagement with stakeholders. Discussions held between the work package leads for Work Packages 2, 3, 4 and 5 concluded that prioritisation will be undertaken by the individual work packages, taking account of the findings of the stakeholder engagement sessions planned for January – March 2023. It was agreed that topics would be prioritised by each work package, based on the evaluation of a common set of selection criteria which correspond to drivers for implementation in decommissioning and waste management (Table 7). These relate to societal, actor-specific, scientific and financial impacts. These drivers are being used in the development of the Strategic Research Agenda for the PREDIS project² and were based on work undertaken in the SHARE project³. While a common set of selection criteria is defined for use across Work Packages 3-5, it is recognised that each work package will determine which drivers are the most relevant to their scope.

Prioritisation of topics will also account for importance, urgency and feasibility.

² PREDIS, 2021. M2.3: Baseline Strategic Research Agenda. Version 1, August 2021. The final version of the PREDIS Strategic Research Agenda will be published in May 2024 and subsequent dissemination activities implemented

³ SHARE, 2021. D1.3: Definition of implementation qualifiers and instruments for implementation. Version 4, March 2021.

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Driver	Description
<p>Societal: Societal impacts address higher level area economics, perspectives of people, environmental protection and the overall trust and well-being of the society. These can be viewed at a local, municipality, regional, country or EU level.</p>	
<p>Economic renewal and growth</p>	<p>Leads to a sustainable increase in the number of work force/jobs and services needed, allowing existing companies to expand their offering or for new companies to enter the market. Provides economic benefits to a region, which can impact the quality and availability of societal public services in the area.</p> <p>Also linked to financial impacts.</p>
<p>Protection of citizens and environment</p>	<p>Leads to improved protection of citizens and the environment by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supporting the reduction of radioactive waste volumes, including between classes of waste (e.g., reduction in HLW to lower levels of waste) • Improving waste classification • Supporting the conservation of the environment • Reducing hazards • Applying the waste hierarchy to prevent, minimise, re-use and recycle wastes • Reducing secondary waste production • Enables safer treatment, packing and storage of wastes, reducing the risk of human exposure (worker and public) and environmental accidents
<p>Public trust and confidence</p>	<p>Engenders public trust and confidence through good planning, implementation and communication of programmes; good communication and transparency of decision making by regulators and governments; and timely and efficient policy formulation and implementation.</p>
<p>Actor-specific: Actor-specific impacts reflect individual company or industry advances relating to processes, products and services, efficiency, competences and skills, and networks.</p>	

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Processes, products and services	Supports the development of new / improved and innovative processes, products and services to address pre-disposal management, which in turn leads to the creation and expansion of companies. Provides solutions that create a competitive advantage, such as cost reduction or resource efficiency. Provides new products and innovations developed to higher Technology Readiness Levels (TRL 7, 8 and 9).
Capacity to improve performance	Provides improved performance by increasing the efficiency of tasks (e.g., by reducing the required labour and minimising the generation of secondary waste) and by reducing lead times for pre-disposal management by reducing the time needed for each task. Supports the reduction in regulatory review times by integrating this with the planning phases and using standardised processes.
Contribution to competences and skills development	Supports the development and maintenance of a skilled and competent workforce for the duration of pre-disposal management programmes. Provides training, education and certification of the workforce, and services/tools for knowledge management, helping to increase efficiency and manage risks effectively, thus reducing accidents.
Improvement of national/international networks	Provides benefits to research and business communities through participation in research networks and business networks. Supports mobility between companies and combining expertise from multiple disciplines.
Scientific: Scientific impacts relate to technology development and innovation to drive improvements.	
Quality in science and technology development	Builds competences and skills in state-of-the-art technologies, practices and developments, through research collaboration and publication of work to assess research quality. Advances technology through TRL.
Innovation capacity	Develops innovation capacity to both introduce new products, services and processes to the market, and to develop in-house solutions.
Financial: Financial impacts relate to business solutions (linked to company growth and performance) and funding schemes.	

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Revenue and turnover	Increases revenue and turnover of a company, leading to increased company growth and improved performance through demonstrating high quality services, tools and success in delivery. Dependent on market potential and funding schemes, as well as ability to reduce liabilities.
Sufficient investment	Promotes adequate funding for predisposal management, and investment in the required supporting infrastructure and facilities.

Table 6 – List of selection criteria for prioritisation process.

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4 Stakeholder engagement

The ultimate aim of Phase I of the HARPERS project is to produce a reduced list of topics (~10 in total, to be distributed evenly among the WP) that are considered of priority interest for further development in the 2nd phase of the project through open calls to which small teams of experts, consortium and external partners, can subscribe. These teams will further engage with the Stakeholder community.

In previous steps, the Stakeholder community was built, an in-depth gap analysis was performed to define priority needs and opportunities (thematic questions) and criteria were identified that can help in setting up priority topics/projects based on drivers related to implementation. These inputs are now combined in an engagement process with the Stakeholder community where the list of identified topics is discussed in order to take their inputs into a further fine-tuning and down-selection of priority topics. This to ensure the highest prioritisation in project focus and greatest impact of the project outcomes.

Each WP, organises two online workshops spread over a period of 2-3 months providing possibilities for project partners (internal Stakeholders) and external (registered) Stakeholders to take part in one of the sessions in the engagement process.

Based on the most recent list of registered Stakeholders (managed by ENEA), invitations for two Stakeholder engagement sessions per WP are sent by email together with a short information package containing the intro and scope of the workshop, list of topics (challenges/needs defined per WP), agenda, and introduction to the online tool for polling/voting (Slido) that is used in the engagement process.

Dates of the Stakeholder engagement workshops (2023):

- WP3: 19/01 & 08/03
- WP4: 16/01 & 22/02
- WP5: 18/01 & 02/02

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Each Stakeholder session is planned to take 2 hrs and follows a common agenda:

- Workshop opening by WP leader
- General introduction of HARPERS project by project coordinator
- Participants self introduction
- Part 1 WP introduction + slido Polls (WP lead)
- Q&A – open discussion (WP lead + supports)
- Break
- Part 2 identified needs & opportunities (topics) introduction + Slido Polls (WP lead)
- Q&A – open discussion (WP lead + supports)
- Closure of the Workshop (WP lead)

The outcomes of the Stakeholder engagement sessions will be documented in milestone MS5 (internal, May 2023), deliverable D2.2 (public, May 2023) and a joint workshop/webinar with the Stakeholder community will be organised (May 2023) where we will present the consolidated outcome of the Stakeholder engagement process.

4.1 WP3 Cross border services/facilities – engagement questions through SLIDO

- What are the main benefits of cross border services/facilities for radioactive waste → Slido word cloud
- What is the single most difficult barrier stopping cross border services, as you see it. One short statement → Slido word cloud
- What is the single most important need for you? Can be your current topic or a new one. One or two short statements → Slido word cloud
- Harmonisation → Slido poll
 - Harmonisation of individual EU and international countries problematic waste inventory
 - What services are wanted/what is the benefit of centralised treatment facilities
 - Standardisation of quality control of suppliers and waste packages
 - To align wastes with treatment technologies in a manner acceptable to all stakeholders
 - A need for a common system for waste classification
 - Not/very low interest in this category

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4.2 WP4 Circular economy – engagement questions through SLIDO

- Why Circular economy is important for nuclear decommissioning and radioactive waste management? → Slido word cloud
- What are the main drivers for implementing Circular Economy in radioactive waste management? Select top 3 drivers → Slido Poll
 - Economical renewal and growth
 - Protection of citizens and environment
 - Public trust and confidence
 - Processes, products and services
 - Capacity to improve performance
 - Contribution to competences and skills development
 - Improvement of national/international networks
 - Quality in science and technology development
 - Innovation capacity
 - Revenue and turnover
 - Sufficient investment
- What are the most IMPORTANT themes to be further analysed within HARPERS project for promoting circular economy when managing materials and waste coming from nuclear decommissioning? Select 1 or 2 → Slido poll
 - Inventory
 - Recycling and Reuse
 - Technologies for materials and waste treatment
 - Clearance
 - Characterisation
 - Multi criteria analysis of strategies
 - Transversal (knowledge sharing/good practices, education and training)
- What are the main challenges (barriers) for reuse and recycling? → Slido poll
 - Regulatory (legal framework/licensing)
 - Societal (public constraints, stakeholder issues)
 - Technological and operational (availability of technologies/facilities)
 - Economical (cost/benefit)
 - Safety and ALARA issues (doses to workers during waste processing)
- What are the main challenges/needs associated with clearance of waste and materials arising from decommissioning? → Slido poll
 - Regulatory (legal frameworks)
 - Public perception on cleared materials
 - Availability of guidance for clearance
 - Technologies and approaches for characterisation
 - Cleared materials traceability
- What are the most URGENT themes to be further analysed within HARPERS project for promoting circular economy when managing materials and waste coming from nuclear decommissioning? Select 1 or 2 → Slido poll
 - Inventory
 - Recycling and Reuse
 - Technologies for materials and waste treatment

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- Clearance
- Characterisation
- Multi criteria analysis of strategies
- Transversal (knowledge sharing/good practices, education and training)

4.3 WP5 Advanced technologies – engagement questions through SLIDO

- What do you see as the major opportunities for advanced technologies in decommissioning and waste management in the next 10/15 years? - Short answer (1 to 3 words) → SLIDO word cloud
- What are the main drivers for adopting advanced technologies? Select top 3 drivers → Slido poll
 - Economical renewal and growth
 - Protection of citizens/environment
 - Public trust and confidence
 - Processes, products and services
 - Capacity to improve performance
 - Contribution to competences and skills development
 - Improvement of national/international networks
 - Quality in science and technology developments
 - Innovation capacity
 - Revenue and turnover
 - Sufficient investment
- What do you consider are the most important topics under 'Waste treatment' to be further analysed within the HARPERS project? Select top 3 from the list → Slido poll
 - New technologies for decontamination of buildings and environmental restoration
 - Adoption of advanced manufacturing techniques including additive manufacturing
 - New waste treatment and immobilisation technologies
 - Harmonised waste-form assessment protocols
 - Remote in-situ characterisation/non contact or non-destructive evaluation
 - Standards for mobile treatment systems
- What are the main challenges (barriers) associated with these topics (Waste treatment)? Select top 2 from list → Slido poll
 - Technological and operational (availability and accessibility)
 - Regulatory (licensing, safety, security, regulatory confidence)
 - Safety and environment (safety case, dose)
 - Economic (cost/benefit)
 - Societal (public trust/confidence, stakeholder issues)
 - Competence and skills (experience)
- What do you consider are the most important topics under 'Automation and Robotics' to be further analysed within the HARPERS project? Select top 3 from the list → Slido poll

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- Adoption of robotics in decommissioning planning, dismantling and waste management – new technology in nuclear environments
- Automation of waste sorting, segregation, sentencing and packaging
- Automation of waste stores, learning from advanced digital logistics practice
- Smart decontamination techniques – targeting contamination through sensing, local decontamination and removal of hazards from the system
- What are the main challenges (barriers) associated with these topics (Automation and Robotics)? Select top 2 from list → Slido poll
 - Technological and operational (availability and accessibility)
 - Regulatory (licensing, safety, security, regulatory confidence)
 - Safety and environment (safety case, dose)
 - Economic (cost/benefit)
 - Societal (public trust/confidence, stakeholder issues)
 - Competence and skills (experience)
- What do you consider are the most important topics under 'Digitalisation' to be further analysed within the HARPERS project? Select top 3 from the list → Slido poll
 - 'Standardisation' digital twin and advanced building information management technology and their application
 - Standardisation of protocols for security of data and data transfer, including cyber security and segregation of data
 - Standardisation of digital architecture and frameworks – common human machine interface (HMI)
 - Automation of site mapping – coupling the use of sensors, geographical information systems (GIS) and deployment...
 - Standardisation of 3D modelling protocols
- What are the main challenges (barriers) associated with these topics (Digitalisation)? Select top 2 from list → Slido poll
 - Technological and operational (availability and accessibility)
 - Regulatory (licensing, safety, security, regulatory confidence)
 - Safety and environment (safety case, dose)
 - Economic (cost/benefit)
 - Societal (public trust/confidence, stakeholder issues)
 - Competence and skills (experience).

5 Selection of topics to launch through open calls

After concluding the Stakeholder engagement webinars, the WP's will further internally discuss the list of priority topics and in view of the visions expressed by the Stakeholders and the list of defined selection criteria, a final selection of 3-5 priority topics per WP will be made. Key considerations for this final are:

- Transparent selection approach (to be documented),
- take into account the input of the Stakeholder engagement process (Slido Polls, remarks)
- use the selection criteria defined before (“drivers”).

The WP leaders will use a semi-quantitative approach to rank the priority topics. This can be achieved by applying weighing factors to categories, drivers, challenges & needs, impact of topics on main drivers, ...based on the outcome of the Slido surveys held during the stakeholder engagement sessions. This can differ from one WP to another. This “quantitative” ranking will be further discussed within the WP with consortium partners and if needed further down selection can be made using qualitative analysis tools like importance/urgency, impact/effort matrices (not limited).

This will be documented in upcoming deliverables D2.2 (Analysis of results: analysis of engagement results and definition of priority areas) and D3.1/4.1/5.1 (Prioritisation of identified topics) due respectively by month 12 (May 2023) and 13 (June 2023).

Based on the outcome of the process, open calls will be organised allowing small teams (~3 partners) of partners, both project and external partners, to apply for further development of the final selected priority topics. These open calls will be launched by July 2023 and after selection of the teams/topics the actual work of the “refinement phase” can start (November 2023). In this refinement phase the teams will investigate more in detail the issues associated with the selected topic. This also entails a deeper engagement with Stakeholders relevant to the topic.

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6 Annex I – HARPERS Gap analysis compilation

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Source Material					Interpretation					
Source Project	Source Document	Document Type	Document Section	Recommendation, need, observation or opportunity	Summary of recommendation	Type of driver(s)	Relevance score for HARPERS	Basis for relevance score	Relevant HARPERS WP(s)	Other Comments
ANCCLI										
ANCCLI	Documentation d'orientation et de justification préliminaire pour l'élaboration d'un guide de l'ASN sur les plans de démantèlement des installations nucléaires de base (March 2022)	Report	Objectives of the decommissioning guide	L'ANCCLI pense que l'évolution des plans de démantèlement doivent également prendre en compte les échanges et résultats de consultation de la société civile, du territoire, des CLI et de l'ANCCLI sur les dossiers de démantèlement. <i>ANCCLI thinks that the evolution of the dismantling plans must also take into account the exchanges and results of the consultation with civil society, the territory, the CLIs and ANCCLI (own translation)</i>	Civil society and local communities in nuclear areas should be taken into account when developing decommissioning guides or strategies.	Societal	H	Engaging with stakeholders since the start is crucial to gain trust and confidence.	2, 6	
ANCCLI	Documentation d'orientation et de justification préliminaire pour l'élaboration d'un guide de l'ASN sur les plans de démantèlement des installations nucléaires de base (March 2022)		Provisional plan and content of the guide	L'ANCCLI souhaiterait qu'une partie du guide puisse formaliser de manière concrète : L'obligation d'information des CLI concernées par les installations en démantèlement notamment lors de la révision du Plan et/ou de sa modification Les étapes d'information de la société civile, notamment des CLI concernées, Les étapes qui seront soumises à consultation publique, L'incitation à discuter avec les acteurs territoriaux du devenir du site après son déclassement, Les perspectives de suivi du site après le déclassement en INB (installations nucléaires de base). <i>ANCCLI would like that a part of the guide would include the following: Obligation to inform the CLIs concerned by the facilities being dismantled, in particular when revising the Plan and/or modifying it The stages of information to civil society, in particular the CLIs concerned, The steps that will be subject to public consultation Encourage the debate with the territorial actors about the future of the site after its decommissioning, Prospects for monitoring the site after decommissioning.</i>	Include in the documentation on decommissioning the obligation to inform and engage local communities, describing when and how and taking into account that one of the expected topics for discussion is the future development of the site (including monitoring).	Societal	H	Better and more sustainable decisions can be reached through stakeholder involvement. Thus, stakeholders need to be engaged in the developed of decommissioning guides or strategies.	2, 6	
CLEANDEM										
CLEANDEM	CLEANDEM – Cyber physical Equipment for unManned Nuclear DEcommissioning Measurements	Website	CLEANDEM - Cyber physical Equipment for unManned Nuclear DEcommissioning Measurements - CAEN - Tools for Discovery	The CLEANDEM project, with its collaboration of 11 partners from 4 different EU countries, proposes a technological breakthrough for dismantling and decommissioning (D&D) operations of nuclear sites, employing an Unmanned Ground Vehicle (UGV) Platform equipped with innovative radiological sensing probes. The aim of the project is to deliver a cyber physical system which will support the endusers' operations, initially performing a radiological assessment of the area and then monitoring D&D	Need of standardisation >> Standardization of dismantling step	Standardization Economic Technological	H/M		3, 4	

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				operations throughout the final characterization of the plant.						
EBRD										
EBRD	https://www.ebrd.com/nuclear-safety.html	Website		There is different understanding, interpretation of limits values and practical enforcement of the technical and administrative requirements that a waste must meet (WAC), to be accepted at a storage, treatment, or disposal facility. This raises difficulties for the involved stakeholders.	For clarify the WAC and practical enforcement, there are varied factors that need to be considered: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regulatory and licensing issues: • Technical and operational issues: • Safety & Security issues • Economic issues: • Public acceptance and stakeholder issues. 	Harmonisation & regulatory economic & environmental & technological	M	.	3, 4, 5, 6	
EBRD	https://www.ebrd.com/nuclear-safety.html	Website		Stimulate stakeholders to exchange/share expertise and experience at a detailed level both within the implementation of decommissioning and associated handling of radioactive waste in the decommissioning phase.	Countries with active programs on decommissioning usually conduct some level of exchange/share expertise and experience. However, there is a potential to enhance the dissemination/sharing between stakeholders inside a country, but also between countries. For practical implementation, there are varied factors that need to be considered: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regulatory issues: • Safety & Security issues • Economic issues: • International and National law issues. It is often difficult for policy makers to understand the magnitude and value of sharing this type of expertise and experience There is also a commercial aspect by sharing experience/ expertise that must be considered.	Economic & Environmental & Regulatory & Legal & Technological	M		3, 4, 5, 6	

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EBRD	https://www.ebrd.com/nuclear-safety.html	Website		Stimulate stakeholders to exchange experience within practical applications of new methodologies and digital technology in the decommissioning process	<p>Countries with active programs on decommissioning usually conduct some level of exchange/share expertise and experience within practical applications and use of digital technology. Anyhow, there is a potential to enhance the dissemination/sharing between stakeholders inside a country, but also between countries. For practical implementation, there are varied factors that need to be considered:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regulatory issues: • Safety & Security issues • Economic issues: • Technical and operational issues. <p>It is often difficult for policy makers to understand the magnitude and value of sharing this type of expertise and experience</p> <p>There is also a commercial aspect by sharing this experience/ expertise that must be considered.</p>	Technological & Economic & Regulatory	H		3, 4, 5, 6	
EDRAM										
EDRAM	www.edram.info	Website	https://www.edram.info/about-us/activities-and-views/edram-views	<p>Views on the concept of multinational approaches to the management and disposal of nuclear waste: Countries can agree to share storage or disposal solutions, provided that they comply with international obligations and internationally accepted safety standards.</p> <p>The ethical considerations to be taken into account in the case of a shared or multinational repository must be the same as those applying to national repositories. International organisations can play an important role to promote RD&D cooperation between member</p>	EDRAM (network of WMO) supports multinational management and disposal facilities as long as international safety standards (but also ethical aspects of radioactive waste management) are complied with.	Regulatory and societal drivers. Indirectly, it can be expected that harmonized national regulations would easier the development of shared facilities.	M/L	While the views of EDRAM falls completely in HARPERS scope, it provides no objective way to achieve such a view, does not discuss obstacles, solutions, etc. Should be outlined that most EDRAM members are identified in HARPERS stakeholders lists, except for DoE (USA),	3	

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				countries and to support progress in national programmes.				NUMO (Japan) and NWMO (Canada).		
EPG										
European Pilot Group (EPG)	REPORT ON THE EUROPEAN PILOT STUDY ON THE REGULATORY REVIEW OF A SAFETY CASE FOR GEOLOGICAL DISPOSAL OF RADIOACTIVE WASTE The following paper presenting the results of the above mentioned report has been used for the review: <i>European pilot study on the regulatory review of the safety case for geological disposal of radioactive waste</i>	Report	N/A	It is now widely accepted that development of a disposal facility and its safety case should take place in a step-by-step manner with well-defined decision points. The degree to which a step-by-step process is implemented in regulations varies from country to country, and so do the requirements concerning the involvement of regulators and licensing authorities at various decision points. The Working Group considers, however, that it is important to keep regulatory and licensing authorities and their technical support organisations informed about the state of development at each step and to involve them in the major decisions (e.g. about the disposal facility concept or about R&D priorities), no matter whether or not there is a formal requirement for doing so.	Development of a disposal facility and its safety case should take place in a step-by-step manner with well-defined decision points. Common understanding about these key steps is important.	Regulatory, Societal	L	The step-wise approach is already well defined and harmonized at the international level (IEAA etc)	6	
European Pilot Group (EPG)	REPORT ON THE EUROPEAN PILOT STUDY ON THE REGULATORY REVIEW OF A SAFETY CASE FOR GEOLOGICAL DISPOSAL OF RADIOACTIVE WASTE	Report	N/A	The safety case presenting the arguments and supporting information and assessment related to the above aspects will have to be comprised of clear information, from the very beginning of a disposal project, covering the design options and the key elements upon which safety relies, together with a description of the preferred strategy to acquire progressively enough knowledge of the factors governing the containment and isolation capacity of the disposal system.	Development of a mutual understanding about the expected content of a safety case for a waste repository.	Regulatory, Societal	L	There are already several international guidelines about what such a safety case should contain.	6	
European Pilot Group (EPG)	REPORT ON THE EUROPEAN PILOT STUDY ON THE REGULATORY REVIEW OF A SAFETY CASE FOR GEOLOGICAL DISPOSAL OF RADIOACTIVE WASTE	Report	N/A	Evaluation of compliance with safety requirements in the presence of uncertainty. Although the approach for compliance evaluation differs considerably depending on the country, the issue remains that many uncertainties in the post-closure safety case cannot reliably be quantified. Calculated doses or risks can only be regarded as broadly conservative indicators rather than anything more definite or concrete and, accordingly, the post-closure safety case needs to be based on multiple lines of reasoning.	Defining a common understanding about how to manage uncertainties in programmes for radioactive waste disposal is important.	Regulatory, Technological, Societal	M	The EURAD-UMAN Work Package is ongoing and address this topic of uncertainty management.	3, 6	
ERDO										

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ERDO	Shared solutions for spent fuel and radioactive wastes responding to EC Directive 2011/70/EURATOM	SRA	2 The 2011 EU Council Directive	It should be an ethical obligation of each Member State <u>to avoid any undue burden on future generations</u> in respect of spent fuel and radioactive waste, including any radioactive wastes expected from decommissioning of existing nuclear installations.	A more aligned and harmonized standard and regulatory framework between EU countries could be the <u>driver</u> to contribute to reduce the undue burden for future generations.	Regulatory	L	Low score assigned because the topic is very general.	3	
ERDO	Shared solutions for spent fuel and radioactive wastes responding to EC Directive 2011/70/EURATOM	SRA	2 The 2011 EU Council Directive	Prior to the shipment to a third country, the exporting Member State shall take reasonable measures to be assured that: the country of destination has radioactive waste management and disposal programmes <u>with objectives equivalent to those established by this Directive</u> ; (...)	A harmonized standard and regulatory framework between EU countries could be an <u>opportunity</u> to favour the shipment of radioactive waste abroad, that today is in part rejected by some countries.		H	High score assigned because the transport of radioactive waste towards other countries is fundamental for the future possible shared solution in disposal.	3	
ERDO	Shared solutions for spent fuel and radioactive wastes responding to EC Directive 2011/70/EURATOM	SRA	2 The 2011 EU Council Directive	Member States, while retaining responsibility for their respective policies in respect of the management of their spent fuel and low, intermediate or high-level radioactive waste, should include planning and implementation of disposal options in their national policies.	The primary goal of (pre)planning of disposal options in the national policy is to effectively manage the waste, and at the same time to prepare the public and obtain their approval for a possible national repository.	Regulatory, societal	L	Low score assigned because the recommendation is a general one.	6	
ERDO	Shared solutions for spent fuel and radioactive wastes responding to EC Directive 2011/70/EURATOM	SRA	2 The 2011 EU Council Directive	The Directive requires each Member State to have a clearly defined and operational radioactive waste management programme ... and acknowledges that while each MS is responsible for organising safe disposal of its radioactive wastes, this need not be done within the State - shared disposal of wastes can be a part of a national programme.	The possibility of adopting a multinational approach to the disposal of radioactive wastes needs to be examined, especially with a view to determining the parameters involved in creating such a cooperative system.	Regulatory & environmental & legal	M	Medium score assigned because to date, multinational cooperation on radioactive waste disposal has been intensive, but has been largely limited to the area of R&D.	3, 6	
ERDO	Shared solutions for spent fuel and radioactive wastes responding to EC Directive 2011/70/EURATOM	SRA	3 The Dual-Track Approach	Running a national R&D programme on geological disposal as part of a dual-track approach not only ensures that a national alternative might be available should sharing fail, but also provides a solid basis of competence and knowledge for each country that is involved in a sharing project. In a well-organised partnership, moreover, <u>sharing expertise and knowledge can significantly reduce the resources required by each country.</u>	Shared waste management and disposal could be an <u>opportunity to</u> share not only expertise, knowledges, competencies, etc. but also a common approach to standardization, practices, regulations, etc.	Regulatory, legal, societal, economic	M	Medium score assigned because the first step towards a more aligned and harmonized standard and regulatory framework regards the opportunity of member states collaboration.	6	
ERDO	The ERDO Association Roadmap. Routes to Shared Disposal Solutions in Europe.	Roadmap	1 The ERDO mission	The aim of the ERDO Association is to work together to address the common challenges of safely managing the long-lived radioactive wastes in our countries and to carry out the necessary groundwork <u>to enable the</u>	In the context of possible future shared repository, the lack of a harmonized regulatory framework (<u>barrier</u>) will lead to an	Regulatory	H	High score assigned to underline the great importance of an harmonized regulatory framework to favour a	6	

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				<u>establishment of one or more operational, shared multinational waste management solutions.</u>	additional commitment of resources (to manage different regulatory schemes and their relationships/differences; e.g., the WACs between different countries).			shared solution for the waste management.		
ERDO	The ERDO Association Roadmap. Routes to Shared Disposal Solutions in Europe.	Roadmap	4 The twin pathway concept	The concept of the RD&D Path is that there are similar issues facing smaller-inventory programmes where a <u>common approach would improve efficiency and effectiveness</u> , as well as facilitating adoption of shared disposal solutions.	The common approach to favour the efficiency and effectiveness must not only be limited to the technological sector (i.e., waste management techniques) but also to the regulatory and standard framework. Work in parallel on the technological and regulatory front at the same time, could be a, <u>opportunity</u> to gain a more aligned and harmonized regulatory and standard framework.	Regulatory	M		5-6	
ERDO	The ERDO Association Roadmap. Routes to Shared Disposal Solutions in Europe.	Roadmap	4 The twin pathway concept	The concept of the RD&D Path is that there are similar issues facing smaller-inventory programmes where a <u>common approach would improve efficiency and effectiveness</u> , as well as facilitating adoption of shared disposal solutions. These includes: (...)demonstration of novel disposal concepts; (...).	The RD&D path should favour the implementation of new and <u>advanced technologies</u> , that could be adopted as common approach.	Technological & environmental	M		5	
ERDO	The ERDO Association Roadmap. Routes to Shared Disposal Solutions in Europe.	Roadmap	4 The twin pathway concept	All countries, large or small, that make use of nuclear technologies must have credible strategies and access to technologies to ensure safe management, treatment, conditioning, storage and disposal of their radioactive wastes. Developments in these areas could mean that <u>common standardised packaging and characterisation</u> would meet common disposability requirements for a shared MNR.	Aligned/Harmonized approach for the waste management techniques (i.e., waste characterization, packaging, etc.) and for the standard and regulatory framework would ease the exchange of practices, information, research activities, better understanding between different 'actors' involved in decommissioning and waste management, etc. Working on a common approach for the waste management techniques	Technological & regulatory	M	Medium score assigned because the adoption of a common technological approach may be strictly related to the different types of waste.	3, 5, 6	

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					could be a <u>driver</u> to start a similar development of a common regulatory and standards framework.					
ERDO	The ERDO Association Roadmap. Routes to Shared Disposal Solutions in Europe.	Roadmap	4 The twin pathway concept	Identifying the <u>minimum set of WAC</u> (physical-chemical-radiological) to be respected by legacy VLLW-LLW or ILW packages for envisaging possible retreatment/ reconditioning processes and disposability to a National or Multinational Disposal Facility.	Harmonized and shared WACs would be useful for the storage/disposal of waste in a multinational shared repository. In some countries WACs are not yet available. This could be an <u>opportunity</u> to realize aligned and harmonized WACs.	Regulatory	M	Medium score assigned because the shared WACs depends on the different types of waste and repository.	6	
EU DG ENER										
EU DG ENER	Radioactive Waste Management in the European Union State of play and strategic prospects	Presentation in EURADWAS TE 2022	Responsible & Safe Management of SPENT FUEL and RADIOACTIVE WASTE	A unique regional binding legislation aiming at ensuring safety in the backend of nuclear life cycle without undue burden to future generations and with the necessary public information and participation	Need for a harmonised regulatory framework for spent fuel and radioactive waste management	Regulatory Harmonisation	H	This recommendation is the whole purpose of Harpers project and a demand from EU and related legislation	6	
EU DG ENER	Radioactive Waste Management in the European Union State of play and strategic prospects	Presentation in EURADWAS TE 2022	Safety aspects activities of ENSREG Working Group 2	Review of regulation and management of radioactive waste arising from non-energy uses	Lesson drawing from regulation from a different source than nuclear energy production. Identification of gaps	Technological Harmonisation	M	Compare and contrast of regulation from another field of radioactive waste production might be a source of lessons learnt to implement within the nuclear sector.	5, 6	
EU DG ENER	Radioactive Waste Management in the European Union State of play and strategic prospects	Presentation in EURADWAS TE 2022	Safety aspects activities of ENSREG Working Group 2	National Programmes Key Performance Indicators	Develop harmonised KPIs for radioactive waste management national programmes	Regulatory Harmonisation	H	Homogeneous KPIs for national programmes will enable the comparison between country's schemes performance and will support EU in funding and technical support allocation to laggard countries.	3, 5, 6	
EU DG ENER	Radioactive Waste Management in the European Union State of play and strategic prospects	Presentation in EURADWAS TE 2022	National inventories	Radioactive waste classification is used to report national inventories, but not systematically for all reported wastes. In various Member States, the reporting is done for some waste families through values used onsite (number of sources, number of drums, number of bags...), without specifying the waste categories.	The need to support a systematic use of the waste classifications in National reports	Harmonisation	H	A harmonised system to classify waste in National reports will allow for thorough and realistic waste inventories. Robust inventory information is key to assess performance among countries and design a proper management system along with its regulatory framework.	4	

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EU DG ENER	Radioactive Waste Management in the European Union State of play and strategic prospects	Presentation in EURADWASTE 2022	Cost assessment "Methodologies of cost assessment for radioactive waste and spent fuel management"	To build a reference list of activities and cost items relating to radioactive waste and spent fuel management	High-level taxonomy for cost items related to nuclear waste management	Economic	M	This will increase the cost-effectiveness of management measures and will enhance business development across countries	3	
EU DG ENER	Radioactive Waste Management in the European Union State of play and strategic prospects	Presentation in EURADWASTE 2022	Cost assessment "Methodologies of cost assessment for radioactive waste and spent fuel management"	To develop meaningful cost assessments indicators for radioactive waste and spent fuel management	Harmonised cost assessment indicators	Economic	M	This will increase the cost-effectiveness of management measures and will enhance business development across countries	3	
EURAD CORI										
EURAD-CORI	Deliverable 3.1 State-of-the-art report on cement-organic-radionuclide interactions Work Package 3, CORI	Deliverable	Section 1	Organic materials are present in some nuclear waste and as admixtures in cement-based materials and can potentially influence the performance of a geological disposal system, especially in the context of low and intermediate level waste disposal. This potential effect of organic molecules is caused by the formation of complexes in solution with radionuclides of interest (actinides and lanthanides, but also other metal cations like Ni) which can (i) increase the radionuclide solubility and (ii) decrease the radionuclide sorption. Organic substances require increased attention since a significant quantity exists in the waste and in the cementitious materials, with a large degree of chemical diversity.	Need of a common organic waste inventory in order to harmonise waste management practices	Technological, Harmonisation	M	There are already common practices to handle certain wastes but it might be new advances in the field that should be considered for the future	5	
EURAD-CORI	Deliverable 3.1 State-of-the-art report on cement-organic-radionuclide interactions Work Package 3, CORI	Deliverable	Section 1	Issues of interest at the repository scale are identified: ☐ Improved scientific basis for the Safety Case for L/ILW waste repositories featuring relevant organics content. ☐ Co-storage of waste: support decisions regarding the question whether or not a mix of various wastes (organics, soluble salts, exothermic waste) can be foreseen. ☐ Optimization of vault design: limitations of interactions between the vaults regarding their content. CORI will provide information on the organic plume by characterizing the transfer behavior in cement-based materials. ☐ Optimization of concrete formulations as regards the potential effect of superplasticizers on radionuclide transfer properties.	Co-storage of wastes, facilities design optimization, barrier formulations optimization	Technological, regulatory framework, economic	H	The objectives highlighted in CORI are in line with some of the objectives already included within HARPERS (Optimization)	3, 5, 6	
EURAD-CORI	Deliverable 3.1 State-of-the-art report on cement-organic-radionuclide interactions Work Package 3, CORI	Deliverable	Section 2.3.2	Production of gas through the radiolysis of organic material is a process that occurs already from the manufacturing of the packages. It diminishes over time due to the decreasing radioactive decay and hence activity of the waste, and the changes in the materials under radiation.	Common approach to tackle the gas generation due to radiolysis	Technological	L	Not a top priority as it's much related to RD issues	5	
EURAD GAS										

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EURAD GAS	Initial State of the Art on Gas Transport in Clayey Materials (D6.1)	Deliverable	Executive summary	Increasing the understanding of gas transport through low-permeability porous materials such as clayey materials is so considered as a high priority in the EURAD Roadmap, within the geoscience theme	Need for increase the understanding of gas transport through low-permeability porous materials	Technological Economic Environmental	H	A high priority in the EURAD Roadmap	5	
EURAD GAS	Initial State of the Art on Gas Transport in Clayey Materials (D6.1)	Deliverable	Executive summary	Even though the gas production processes are generally slow, it is possible that gas could be generated at a faster rate than it can be removed through the engineered barrier components and the host rock without creating discrete, gas-specific pathways (e.g. fracturing or pathway dilation)	Need for solutions how to not effect engineered barriers and host rocks due to repository gas	Technological Economic Environmental	M	Related to optimization between environmental impact and repository cost	5	
EURAD GAS	Initial State of the Art on Gas Transport in Clayey Materials (D6.1)	Deliverable	Executive summary	In several disposal concepts, the potential for the release to the biosphere of gas containing volatile radionuclides is an area that requires consideration and therefore robust underpinning knowledge	Need for solution for environmental safety	Technological Economic Environmental	M	Related to knowledge management	5, 6	
EURAD GAS	Initial State of the Art on Gas Transport in Clayey Materials (D6.1)	Deliverable	Executive summary	The raison d'être of this WP is to provide answers to two key end-users' questions: • How can gas migrate within the repository and which water soluble and volatile radionuclide transport could be associated with it? • How and to what extent could the hydro-mechanical perturbations induced by gas affect barrier integrity and performance?	Need for scientific research and arguments before providing answers to the main questions of end-users'	Technological Economic Environmental	M	Identified as raison d'être of GAS WP	5	
EURAD GAS	Initial State of the Art on Gas Transport in Clayey Materials (D6.1)	Deliverable	Executive summary	The compilation of all the research on the transport of gas in clayey materials detailed in this SOTA reveals a great diversity of experimental results in terms of observed phenomena and processes.	Need for decrease the diversity of experimental results	Technological Harmonisation	M	Related to harmonisation of experimental results	5, 6	
EURAD GAS	Initial State of the Art on Gas Transport in Clayey Materials (D6.1)	Deliverable	2.2.7 Uncertainties and knowledge gaps	Knowing the dependency of gas diffusion to these parameters would provide relevant information for generic disposal concepts and would make the existing data more widely usable by different end-users.	Need for experimental research how mineralogy and density influence on gas diffusion coefficient	Technological	M	Identified as a need	5	
EURAD GAS	Initial State of the Art on Gas Transport in Clayey Materials (D6.1)	Deliverable	2.2.7 Uncertainties and knowledge gaps	However, the effect of desaturation on the diffusivity of gases has not yet been studied and is therefore considered as a knowledge gap.	Need for experimental research how desaturation influence on diffusivity of gases	Technological	M	Identified as knowledge gap	5	
EURAD GAS	Initial State of the Art on Gas Transport in Clayey Materials (D6.1)	Deliverable	2.3.4 Uncertainties and knowledge gaps	There is a need to develop robust protocol for H2 isotherm measurements as a function of temperature, pressure and relative humidity. In addition, the contribution of the claystone organic content to H2 uptake has not been evaluated either.	Need for experimental research how temperature, pressure and RH influence on H2 sorption	Technological	M	Identified as a need	5	
EURAD GAS	Initial State of the Art on Gas Transport in Clayey Materials (D6.1)	Deliverable	2.4.4 Uncertainties and knowledge gaps	Agreed geotechnical workflows are required to gain confidence with regards to adequate sample preparation techniques and reliable basic characterisation of material properties (index properties).	Need for harmonised geotechnical workflows for experimental work	Technological Harmonisation	M	Related to harmonisation of experimental results	5, 6	
EURAD GAS	Initial State of the Art on Gas Transport in Clayey Materials (D6.1)	Deliverable	2.4.4 Uncertainties and knowledge gaps	Furthermore, benchmark exercises are needed to confirm the reliability and comparability of various techniques for water retention measurements (e.g. static vs. dynamic; axis translation vs. vapour transfer	Need for benchmark exercises to confirm the reliability and comparability of various experimental techniques	Technological Harmonisation	M	Related to harmonisation of experimental results	5, 6	

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				techniques) and effective gas permeability testing along well-established loading paths.						
EURAD GAS	Initial State of the Art on Gas Transport in Clayey Materials (D6.1)	Deliverable	2.5.5. Uncertainties and knowledge gaps	The modelling of gas transfer in saturated clayey materials is still a challenging task. Some models have been proposed but they fail in being predictive.	Need for development of numerical models based on experimental data	Technological	M	Identified as challenged task	5	
EURAD GAS	Initial State of the Art on Gas Transport in Clayey Materials (D6.1)	Deliverable	3.1.6. Uncertainties and knowledge gaps	Phenomena and features associated with gas-induced damage evolution in clayey materials are difficult to predict. This is an inherent issue with many localisation phenomena in geoscience and structural mechanics.	Need for development of phenomena and features associated with gas-induced damage evolution	Technological	M	Identified as difficult to predict	5	
EURAD GAS	Initial State of the Art on Gas Transport in Clayey Materials (D6.1)	Deliverable	3.1.6. Uncertainties and knowledge gaps	An improvement of conceptualisation of self-sealing mechanisms at process level is needed to be able to model and predict the self-sealing capacity of clay barriers and the host rocks under the THM-C conditions that prevail in a deep geological repository.	Need for an improvement of conceptualisation of self-sealing mechanisms	Technological	M	Identified as difficult to predict	5	
EURAD GAS	Initial State of the Art on Gas Transport in Clayey Materials (D6.1)	Deliverable	4.1.6.2. Performance assessment/safety assessment open issues	It should be remembered that it is difficult to represent experimentally the expected in situ conditions, mainly because of the long characteristic times of the involved phenomena	Need for assumptions how to represent expected in-situ conditions in experiments	Technological	M	Identified as difficulty	5	
EURAD KM										
EURAD KM	List of training needs from Research, Development and Demonstration and Strategic Studies Work Packages Approved list of prioritized topics for further guidance documents and selection process of one topic for the development of a pilot guide Screening and review of existing/available knowledge management approaches and/or tools	Deliverables (13.1, 12.3 and 11.1)	D13.1, section 3.2	Identification of training needs	Several topics of high priority to develop training as WAC	Technological, regulatory, etc.	M	Provides an overview of the status	3, 4, 5, 6	
EURAD KM	List of training needs from Research, Development and Demonstration and Strategic Studies Work Packages	Deliverables (13.1, 12.3 and 11.1)	D12.3, section 1	Common Knowledge strategy - Roadmap	To follow the same common strategy	Harmonization	H	Relevant for transferring the same information	3, 4, 5, 6	

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	Approved list of prioritized topics for further guidance documents and selection process of one topic for the development of a pilot guide Screening and review of existing/available knowledge management approaches and/or tools									
EURAD KM	List of training needs from Research, Development and Demonstration and Strategic Studies Work Packages Approved list of prioritized topics for further guidance documents and selection process of one topic for the development of a pilot guide Screening and review of existing/available knowledge management approaches and/or tools		D11.1, section 3.1	To consider that knowledge is often not static	Technologies, methods, best practices, etc. can evolve with time	Technological	M	To be considered	3, 4, 5,6	
EURAD KM	List of training needs from Research, Development and Demonstration and Strategic Studies Work Packages Approved list of prioritized topics for further guidance documents and selection process of one topic for the development of a pilot guide Screening and review of		D11.1, section 3.1	Long term sustainability of KMS	Knowledge should be kept along years		M	To be considered	3, 4, 5,6	

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	existing/available knowledge management approaches and/or tools									
EURAD KM	List of training needs from Research, Development and Demonstration and Strategic Studies Work Packages Approved list of prioritized topics for further guidance documents and selection process of one topic for the development of a pilot guide Screening and review of existing/available knowledge management approaches and/or tools		D11.1, section 3.1	Project partners engagement	To motivate people to contribute and provide incentive to do so		M	To be considered	3, 4, 5, 6	
EURAD KM	List of training needs from Research, Development and Demonstration and Strategic Studies Work Packages Approved list of prioritized topics for further guidance documents and selection process of one topic for the development of a pilot guide Screening and review of existing/available knowledge management approaches and/or tools		D11.1, section 3.1	Different ways to organize the KM system	Each organization develops their own system, if have it		L	Not so relevant	3, 4, 5, 6	
EURAD KM	List of training needs from Research, Development and Demonstration and		D11.1, section 3.1	The roles and responsibilities of the various official entities should be clearly defined in the national framework and in legislation		Economic	L	Not so relevant for Harpers	6	

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	Strategic Studies Work Packages Approved list of prioritized topics for further guidance documents and selection process of one topic for the development of a pilot guide Screening and review of existing/available knowledge management approaches and/or tools									
EURAD Routes										
EURAD – ROUTES – Task 6	7 Deliverable 9.5: Overview of issues related to challenging wastes	Deliverable In progress	4	“ Globally, Member States face difficulties when attempting characterization, which are often an important reason why wastes are regarded as challenging to manage. These difficulties are related to the representativeness of the samples, but also the techniques for detecting particular species such as activation products or complexing substances. It was pointed out that some types of waste, such as oils or orphan sources, require innovative measurement techniques. These issues, which are directly linked to ROUTES Task 3, will be further addressed in this framework. In addition to the vicious circle regarding characterization that is mentioned at the beginning of this report , another vicious circle was shared by all the Member States, which is that ‘to be characterized, waste needs to be retrieved, but in order to be retrieved, it requires a detailed inventory that needs to be characterized first”. Future progress in terms of non-destructive characterization may provide a route out of these vicious circles. Regarding treatment and conditioning, Member States are still awaiting the development of innovative techniques for a number of challenging wastes: graphite, wastes containing reactive metals, organic waste, etc. Initiatives have been implemented in some countries, and there is interest in sharing these good practices. However, these new techniques raise R&D issues about, for instance, the lifespan of the innovative matrices that could be used.”	Need a detailed inventory about the development of innovative techniques for a number of challenging wastes	Regulatory Societal Economic	M		6	
EURAD – ROUTES – Task 6	Deliverable 9.5: Overview of issues related to challenging wastes	Deliverable In progress	4	“Similarly, an interest in the sharing of mobile treatment facilities between countries has also been highlighted by some Member States, particularly regarding treatment of sludges and resins. In the case of disposal, as	Need of sharing of mobile treatment facilities between countries (been highlighted by some	Technological Harmonisation	H/M		3, 4, 5, 6	

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				mentioned in the beginning of the report, Member States are often faced with a lack of permanent solutions that prevents them from developing or using appropriate treatment and conditioning techniques, as the packages produced may not be in line with future WAC. The dilemma of early or delayed conditioning is addressed in ROUTES Task 4. Furthermore, regarding existing disposal solutions, an interesting question that could be further explored is whether certain waste types are considered to be challenging only because they are not covered by existing disposal WAC? It is also worth noting that for some challenging wastes, the question of disposal has not yet arisen, as they are not yet considered waste, e.g., PSFs or depleted uranium. For these wastes, the whole disposal strategy has still to be developed, and sharing among the countries concerned is highly encouraged in order to discuss possible solutions and common difficulties.	Member States particularly regarding treatment of sludges and resins.)					
EURAD – ROUTES – Task 6	Deliverable D9.13: Case studies on shared solution between Member states	Deliverable In progress	5.4.2	“Service exchanges of RAW processing are a majority among exchanges of solutions between MS. Particularly, sharing services of RAW processing regard: Incineration of technological waste treatment and melting of contaminated metals (including large pieces) Treatment and conditioning of RAW It has been noticed that the time needed for the paperwork to set up a first collaboration for RAW treatment between MS could be particularly long. A good teamwork and confidence between involved partners increase the success of new collaboration and decrease the difficulty of the approach. The complexity of procedures could also require a long time to set up a collaboration with an international organization. The lessons learned from the past shared solutions between MS highlight that the public consultation and acceptance are important in order to insure the durability of agreements between countries. Some collaborations of RAW processing involve an intergovernmental agreement in addition to a commercial agreement. The success of collaborations which require an intergovernmental agreement depend on the good political relationship between involved MS.”	Define or improve procedures to allow a better collaboration between countries to share solutions between MS and develop service exchanges of RAW	Regulatory, societal	M		3, 4, 5, 6	
EURAD – ROUTES – Task 6	Deliverable D9.13: Case studies on shared solution between Member states	Deliverable In progress	5.4.3	“Among past shared solutions, there are several examples of SNF reprocessing between MS. The involvement of tiers in the preparation of a collaboration about SNF reprocessing increase the international confidence about SNF transfer transparency. A regulation harmonization could be required about the return of the induced waste by the reprocessing of the SNF. Collaborations about SNF	Harmonize regulation about the return of the induced waste by the reprocessing of the SNF.	Harmonisation Regulation	M		6	

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				reprocessing are particularly subject to unpredictable stop because of political reasons.”						
EURAD ROUTES (Task 4: WAC)	Presentation on needs and opportunities for WAC-related R&D, given to PREDIS webinar on 5/10/22. This sets out draft recommendations that will be integrated into upcoming ROUTES deliverables (to be published).	Webinar Presentation	Slide 9	CH1: Sampling and characterisation methodologies to obtain representative data (particularly for challenging / legacy wastes)	Improve sampling and characterisation methodologies to obtain representative data	Technological, harmonisation	Medium	Linked to standardisation of waste management approaches	WP5	Interest expressed by five sources (Member States + PREDIS)
EURAD ROUTES (Task 4: WAC)	Presentation on needs and opportunities for WAC-related R&D, given to PREDIS webinar on 5/10/22. This sets out draft recommendations that will be integrated into upcoming ROUTES deliverables (to be published).	Webinar Presentation	Slide 9	CH2: Characterisation methods to determine compliance of particular wastes (conditioned and non-conditioned) with WAC, including: chemotoxics, complexants, chelating agents and other liquid organics, wastes with high alpha-emitting radionuclide inventory	Improve characterisation methods to determine compliance of particular wastes (conditioned and non-conditioned) with WAC.	Technological, harmonisation	Medium	Linked to standardisation of waste management approaches	WP3, WP5	Interest expressed by seven sources (Member States + PREDIS)
EURAD ROUTES (Task 4: WAC)	Presentation on needs and opportunities for WAC-related R&D, given to PREDIS webinar on 5/10/22. This sets out draft recommendations that will be integrated into upcoming ROUTES deliverables (to be published).	Webinar Presentation	Slide 9	CH3: Non-destructive analysis of conditioned waste, e.g., testing of concrete, including industrial implementation for small inventories	Non-destructive analysis of conditioned waste, e.g., testing of concrete, including industrial implementation for small inventories	Technological	Low	Linked to standardisation, but requires research / demonstrator studies that are outside the scope of HARPERS		Interest expressed by seven sources (Member States + PREDIS)
EURAD ROUTES (Task 4: WAC)	Presentation on needs and opportunities for WAC-related R&D, given to PREDIS webinar on 5/10/22. This sets out draft recommendations	Webinar Presentation	Slide 9	CH5: Mobile systems and other shared approaches to waste characterisation	Mobile systems and other shared approaches to waste characterisation	Harmonisation, Environmental, Economical	High	Strongly linked to harmonisation and sharing of approaches and facilities	WP3, WP6	Interest expressed by five sources (Member States + PREDIS)

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	that will be integrated into upcoming ROUTES deliverables (to be published).									
EURAD ROUTES (Task 4: WAC)	Presentation on needs and opportunities for WAC-related R&D, given to PREDIS webinar on 5/10/22. This sets out <u>draft</u> recommendations that will be integrated into upcoming ROUTES deliverables (to be published).	Webinar Presentation	Slide 10	TR1: Decontamination of irradiated or contaminated materials to facilitate reuse of materials with potential 'value', free release or optimised waste management (e.g., reduced waste volumes requiring geological disposal)	Decontamination of irradiated or contaminated materials to facilitate reuse of materials with potential 'value', free release or optimised waste management	Environmental, Technological, Harmonisation	High	Strongly linked to collective application of a circular economy	WP4	Interest expressed by four Member States
EURAD ROUTES (Task 4: WAC)	Presentation on needs and opportunities for WAC-related R&D, given to PREDIS webinar on 5/10/22. This sets out <u>draft</u> recommendations that will be integrated into upcoming ROUTES deliverables (to be published).	Webinar Presentation	Slide 11	CO3: Develop innovative matrices (e.g. geopolymers?) for specific wastes and evaluate their compatibility with repository safety criteria. Wastes of interest include: solvents and acids; tritiated wastes; wastes containing reactive metals, SIERS; sludges; spent fuel	Develop innovative matrices for specific wastes and evaluate their compatibility with repository safety criteria.	Safety, Technological, Environmental	Medium	Linked to harmonisation of approach and sharing of information but may require research / demonstrator studies that are out of scope.	WP5	Interest expressed by five sources (Member States + PREDIS)
EURAD ROUTES (Task 4: WAC)	Presentation on needs and opportunities for WAC-related R&D, given to PREDIS webinar on 5/10/22. This sets out <u>draft</u> recommendations that will be integrated into upcoming ROUTES deliverables (to be published).	Webinar Presentation	Slide 11	CO4: Treatment and conditioning solutions to enhance the disposability of graphite wastes	Treatment and conditioning solutions to enhance the disposability of graphite wastes	Technological, Environmental	Low	Likely to require research / demonstrator studies that are out of scope for HARPERS	WP5	Interest expressed by four Member States
EURAD ROUTES (Task 4: WAC)	Presentation on needs and opportunities for WAC-related R&D, given to PREDIS	Webinar Presentation	Slide 12	SS1: Approach to manage challenging wastes with inventories or properties that do not meet WAC for existing or planned facilities	Approach to manage challenging wastes with inventories or properties that do not meet WAC for	Harmonisation, Regulatory, Technological	High	Strongly linked to harmonisation and shared approach to address obstacles to waste management	WP3 / WP6	Interest expressed by six sources (Member States + PREDIS)

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	webinar on 5/10/22. This sets out <u>draft</u> recommendations that will be integrated into upcoming ROUTES deliverables (to be published).				existing or planned facilities					
EURAD ROUTES (Task 4: WAC)	Presentation on needs and opportunities for WAC-related R&D, given to PREDIS webinar on 5/10/22. This sets out <u>draft</u> recommendations that will be integrated into upcoming ROUTES deliverables (to be published).	Webinar Presentation	Slide 12	SB1: Chemical behaviour of specific wastes under storage and disposal conditions, including radiation-induced processes and impacts on gas generation and radionuclide mobility and retention. Wastes of interest include: SIERS; evaporator concentrates and tank sludges; cemented waste packages (particularly with respect to crack propagation); spent fuel and HLW	Chemical behaviour of specific wastes under storage and disposal conditions	Technological, Environmental	Low	Likely to require research / demonstrator studies that are out of scope for HARPERS	WP3 / WP5	Interest expressed by seven Member States
EURAD ROUTES (Task 4: WAC)	Presentation on needs and opportunities for WAC-related R&D, given to PREDIS webinar on 5/10/22. This sets out <u>draft</u> recommendations that will be integrated into upcoming ROUTES deliverables (to be published).	Webinar Presentation	Slide 13	WAC1: Benchmarking exercise for WAC development	Benchmarking exercise for WAC development	Harmonisation, Regulatory	Medium	Potentially useful knowledge transfer exercise, but challenging to make it broadly applicable.	WP6	Interest expressed by three Member States and top priority in workshop polling exercise
EURAD ROUTES (Task 4: WAC)	Presentation on needs and opportunities for WAC-related R&D, given to PREDIS webinar on 5/10/22. This sets out <u>draft</u> recommendations that will be integrated into upcoming ROUTES deliverables (to be published).	Webinar Presentation	Slide 13	WAC2: Comparison and standardisation of radionuclides (and their speciation) to account for in waste characterisation and WAC, including ¹⁴ C	Comparison and standardisation of radionuclides (and their speciation) to account for in waste characterisation and WAC	Regulatory, Harmonisation	High	Strongly linked to harmonisation of waste management approaches across Europe.	WP6	Interest expressed by five sources (Member States + PREDIS)

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EURAD ROUTES (Task 4: WAC)	Presentation on needs and opportunities for WAC-related R&D, given to PREDIS webinar on 5/10/22. This sets out <u>draft</u> recommendations that will be integrated into upcoming ROUTES deliverables (to be published).	Webinar Presentation	Slide 14	WAC12: Collaboration with other Member States to provide training and sustain competences in the field of radioactive waste management	Collaboration with other Member States to provide training and sustain competences in the field of radioactive waste management	Harmonisation, Knowledge Management	High	Strongly linked to development, maintenance and transfer of knowledge across the waste management industry workforce.	All, WP7 (and also linked to EURAD / PREDIS KM activities)	Interest expressed by four Member States
EURADSCIENCE										
EURAD SCIENCE	ResearchEntities-SRA draft version 0.4 of a SRA of European research entities	SRA	Why do European RE need a SRA - Embedding techno-scientific research in an ever more demanding society - Safeguards	In order to consider geological disposal in all its complexity, also related nuclear security and safeguards issues must be taken into account. While safety can benefit from some provisions regarding safeguards and physical protection (security), it may also be contravened by others. ⁴ Therefore, identifying both synergies in overlapping methods or techniques and differences in the requirements relative to safety, security and safeguards may help to take advantage of inherent synergies and conflicting requirements at the same time. Safety and safeguards aspects of geological disposal have been mainly investigated in different research communities, through separate national, European and international R&D programmes, while nuclear security dimensions of geological disposal have not received much attention yet. An important platform for co-operation and information exchange at the European level is ESARDA, the European Safeguards R&D Association, which addresses, inter alia, safeguards issues relating to geological disposal. On the international level, these issues have been primarily studied by the IAEA Expert Group on “Application of Safeguards to Geological Repositories (ASTOR)”, including participants from 16 countries worldwide, who have contributed to the group as part of their Member States Support Programmes to the IAEA. The IAEA generally considers safety, security and safeguards as essential elements of the design, construction, commissioning, operation, and decommissioning stages of nuclear facilities. In this context, the IAEA is issuing a guidance document aimed at informing stakeholders	Identification of synergies in overlapping methods or techniques and differences in requirements relative to safety, security and safeguards for GDS	Harmonisation, technological, regulatory	M	Mainly relates to safeguards which is not a specific topic in HARPERS	5, 6	

⁴ Management of spent nuclear fuel and its waste, EASAC policy report # 23, JRC Reference Report, June 2014, Section 5.3

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				<p>how to design facilities for nuclear waste management by early consideration of safeguards in the design so that provisions can be better integrated with other design requirements as to safety and security⁵. The implementation of this approach, also referred to as “safeguards by design” (SBD), or, as an augmented term, “safety, security, safeguards by design” (3SBD), requires further R&D for fully understanding the common and conflicting requirements relating to safeguards, security and safety. Further R &D can result in methods and technologies that would be best suited for the holistic consideration of safety, security and safeguards provisions while minimizing their impacts on the operation of geological repositories.</p> <p>The 3SBD toolbox to be developed should include, first, measurement techniques for spent fuel verification already at the encapsulation plant. Second, a set of measures based on remote monitoring, nuclear measurements, containment and surveillance for application at the encapsulation plant, the geological repository and transfers between both. Third, measures for detecting unauthorized activities, e.g. the analysis of open source information including satellite imagery, geophysical monitoring and environmental sampling.</p>						
EURAD SCIENCE	ResearchEntities-SRA draft version 0.4 of a SRA of European research entities	SRA	Why do European RE need a SRA - Embedding techno-scientific research in an ever more demanding society - Social sciences	<p>We also do acknowledge that geological disposal is not a pure techno-scientific question but also involves to a large part the civil society as a very important stakeholder. It is now recognized that 'the social' and 'the technical' dimensions of nuclear waste technology development are inter-related and co-produced. Radioactive waste governance must therefore account for the 'physical' as well as the 'social' dimensions of related risks, public values, concerns and perceptions being equally important for identifying, understanding and managing these risks. Interactions with social scientists in a structural, well-organised manner, reflecting on scientific concepts and approaches, open to concerns of society, guiding new research is an integral part of the spirit of the SRA. Social scientists can organize and mediate meaningful interactions between scientists, policymakers, publics, and other stakeholders, asking these actors to jointly address sociotechnical risks and concerns inherent to nuclear technology development.</p>	Interactions with social scientists in a structural, well-organised manner	societal	H	Social sciences aspects are integral part of the HARPERS project	2, 3, 4, 5, 6	
EURAD SCIENCE	ResearchEntities-SRA draft version 0.4 of a	SRA	Why do European RE need a SRA - Joint programming	On the other hand, among research entities, there is no common vision on the scale of the overall scientific problem related to the environmental protection and	Alignment of “practices”: joint programming of GDS related R&D to stay at the	Harmonisation	L	Too general. Not specific to HARPERS	3, 5, 6	

⁵ International Safeguards in the Design of Facilities for Long Term Spent Fuel Management, IAEA Nuclear Energy Series No. NF-T-3.1, (Final Draft)

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	SRA of European research entities		as a tool for building a European knowledge platform on waste disposal	safety case, equally not on research priorities. Research is rarely guided by a common vision of the needs of developing a scientific safety and environmental protection case but by open questions in specific knowledge fields. Each research entity understands a certain aspect of this problem to a certain degree of scientific depth without having the resources and the understanding to address the multiscale coupled overall system. This is the reason to propose to go from current project oriented research to a programmed approach allowing joining forces. We are convinced that joint programming is today the only way to address the scientific basis of the safety and environmental protection case in a serious way. Moreover, it is impossible to ask that each Member State will 1) develop all the knowledge required to be at the forefront/leading edge of all processes acting within a repository, and 2) develop the facilities needed to study all aspects related to disposal of highly radio- and chemotoxic wastes. Joint Programming can therefore be viewed as an additional tool for allowing the development of a common European Knowledge Area. This Knowledge Area also serves as a guarantee that the necessary scientific knowledge, skills and tools are present within a European common space for answering any question raised from within society and stakeholder platforms on disposal of radioactive waste. Joint programming also needs to consider the availability and development of appropriate laboratory facilities including state-of-the-art analytical and spectroscopic capabilities, which basically allow to perform cutting edge research on nuclear waste disposal issues. This comprises laboratory platforms licensed to work with relevant radionuclides and waste forms. Joint programming aiming at an enhanced involvement of member states with less evolved disposal and respective research programmes must be enabled to use such facilities for their own programmes and by this to cooperate with other scientists in this field and interdisciplinary.	edge of science, serve EU community as a whole → European Knowledge Area Establishing “cross border” state of art laboratory platforms for cutting edge R&D related to waste disposal. Optimisation of resources	Harmonisation	M	Is in line with the WP3 scope, but is mainly Pure science driven.	3	
EURAD SCIENCE	Research Entities-SRA draft version 0.4 of a SRA of European research entities	SRA	Why do European RE need a SRA - Joint programming as a tool for structured, long-term R&D commitment	Within our vision, joint programming will also become the drive and roadmap for long-term, real-scale mock-up and/or in situ testing , which is frequently beyond the financial capabilities of several individual member states, let alone research entities.	Establishing “cross border” testing environments to conduct real-scale mock-up and/or in situ testing	Harmonisation Technological	M	Is in line with the WP3 scope	3	

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EURAD SCIENCE	Research Entities-SRA draft version 0.4 of a SRA of European research entities	SRA	Draft SRA - 1 overriding issues: horizontal review activities, identification of research orientations and networking	1.1.1 Networking and sustain joint European research infrastructures with state-of-the-art investigative equipment for example for spent fuel characterisation (RBMK, CANDU, VVER). Establish a data base on partners competencies and establish conditions allowing for transnational access i.e. for advanced light sources, analytical equipment (surface/solution/solid), actinide labs, hot cells, radioanalytical labs, underground research facilities and high performance computation, considering in particular allowing access for Less Advanced Programmes	Establishing transnational access to state of art infrastructures for high end R&D	Harmonisation	M	Is in line with the WP3 scope, but is mainly Pure science driven.	3	
EURAD SCIENCE	Research Entities-SRA draft version 0.4 of a SRA of European research entities	SRA	Draft SRA - 2.2 R&D scientific basis	2.2.12 Develop and evaluate concepts and methods for of sometimes very old wastes for which a retrieval is envisaged	Alignment of “practices” (concepts and methods) for handling, treating, conditioning, storing and re-disposal of old wastes	Harmonisation Technological	H	In line with scope of WP5	5	
EURAD SCIENCE	ResearchEntities-SRA draft version 0.4 of a SRA of European research entities	SRA	Draft SRA - Social and ecology sciences/involvement of stakeholders, including citizen engagement	3.6 Investigate what the expectations/opinions/suggestions are on future/planned R&D by different stakeholders, specifically non-scientific-technical ones / Civil Society., and develop procedures for R&D feed-back responding to actual concerns of civil society, develop methods to visualize the evolution of the repository project in operational phase and to alert.	Engagement with public to help orienting R&D to respond to actual concerns → development of procedures for R&D feedback	Societal	M	Social aspects are embedded in HARPERS project, but this aspect is not specifically bound to a WP	5	
GMF										
GMF	Annex of Laraia, M. (2022) book Nuclear Decommissioning Case Studies Vol. 3. The People Side: “Communication and engagement of local stakeholders in decommissioning of nuclear facilities: the experience of GMF”	Appendix of book	A.1	[...] three factors which are key to manage the social challenges in nuclear decommissioning projects: 1) engage local stakeholders at an early and timely stage and provide the local community and their political representatives with prompt, accurate and reliable information; 2) start the planning of the decommissioning project as soon as possible, ideally when the facility is still in operation; 3) prioritize the siting of a waste storage/repository to a stage when a nuclear license has been already provided (e.g. for nuclear power production). [...] provide stakeholders with support, both in the form of financial and psychological assistance [...] [...] building partnerships and coalitions with actors beyond the local level to create economic resilience strategies; evaluate site reuse as a component of a larger strategy [...]	Engage local actors in the planning of the decommissioning process and provide them with financial and psychological support	Societal	H	The social and economic implications of the decommissioning upon the local communities can be substantial. The need for planning and engagement is paramount.	6	
GMF	Annex of Laraia, M. (2022) book Nuclear Decommissioning Case Studies Vol. 3. The People Side:		A.2 Experience with local stakeholder engagement in decommissioning projects	“Local communities are working to diversity employment” “the disposal of spent fuel [...] is still pending. The industry, the association of municipalities with nuclear facilities (KSO), and the affected municipalities have all	Establish partnerships with local communities to set out a vision for the future of the area which	Societal	H	Supporting the economic change through locally led collaborative initiatives and transformational	6	

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	“Communication and engagement of local stakeholders in decommissioning of nuclear facilities: the experience of GMF”			pointed out that a lack of a governmental decision could cause problems regarding the handling of waste from the Swedish reactors in operation and a threat to security”. “[...] general framework of collaboration and exchange of information among the parties to support a participatory process and design specific actions to ensure sustainable development, well-being and employment in the affected area” [...] local authorities in partnership with other agencies, sets out the vision for the area for the future”.	includes disposing of radioactive waste.			projects is crucial for local communities.		
GMF	Annex of Laraia, M. (2022) book Nuclear Decommissioning Case Studies Vol. 3. The People Side: “Communication and engagement of local stakeholders in decommissioning of nuclear facilities: the experience of GMF”		A.3 Local communities in media reporting and public opinion on decommissioning	“[...] media reporting about decommissioning is important since most people cannot get any direct experience or information related to decommissioning, but only learn through mass media channels”. [...] opinions, experiences, attitudes and expectations of local population may be overlooked and unnoticed in the process of decommissioning”.	Decommissioning may become a relevant public issue if there is an interest from media. More research in public opinion, expectations and interests of different stakeholders in decommissioning is needed.	Societal	H	Mass media can contribute to increasing awareness, changing perceptions and informing decision-making. It is necessary first to know the baseline opinion.	6	
GMF	Annex of Laraia, M. (2022) book Nuclear Decommissioning Case Studies Vol. 3. The People Side: “Communication and engagement of local stakeholders in decommissioning of nuclear facilities: the experience of GMF”		A.4 Lessons learned for involvement of local stakeholders: the GMF viewpoint	“municipalities [...] need co-operation of regional and national authorities as well as the nuclear industry to work on an integrated strategy. Financial resources for socio-economic development are also key to support this transition”. “Local communities [...] offer to work together with public authorities and nuclear industry through: investigating what the residents know and how they feel about decommissioning; inquiring how much they wish to be informed and engaged in the process; communicating with and engaging them in the sociotechnical process of decommissioning”.	Partnerships with authorities and nuclear industry and financial support are crucial for reorienting economic development in nuclear communities. Investigating their needs, opinions and engaging them in the process is paramount.	Societal	H	SSH research is needed to provide a critical review of decommissioning projects from the point of view of local stakeholders.	6	
H2020 Chance										
H2020 CHANCE	Synthesis of commonly used methodology for conditioned radioactive waste characterization (D2.2)	Deliverable	2.1	<i>Although the IAEA Safety Guide 111-G-1.1 [5] was replaced in 2009 by IAEA Safety Guide GSG-1 [6], the older classification scheme was accepted by the European Commission (EC) for reporting, and it is still used in the current classification schemes of many European countries.....</i> Some countries we received answers from adopted a waste classification scheme in agreement with the recent classification scheme proposed by IAEA GSG-1, while others adopted the older IAEA 111-G-1.1 classification schemes in their national recommendations.	This report includes the classification schemes used in the countries that had representatives in the CHANCE EUG as well as for other European countries for which data from NEA general reports and country specific reports was used.	Regulatory	H	Harmonisation of the waste classification schemes are important for further sharing facilities in the predisposal steps of RWM.	3	

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H2020 CHANCE	Synthesis of commonly used methodology for conditioned radioactive waste characterization (D2.2)	Deliverable	2.3	What are the waste acceptance criteria (WAC) for the storage / disposal facilities <i>CHANCE EUG members were asked to specify, for each storage / disposal option, the main parameters that have to be characterized: radiological parameters, chemical parameters, mechanical parameters, but also any other type of parameters (i.e. homogeneity, types of conditioning matrices, specifications for the container, waste accepted with restriction, forbidden waste, etc.).</i>	Many commonalities in type of parameters considered in WAC	Technical / regulatory	M		3	
H2020 CHANCE	Synthesis of commonly used methodology for conditioned radioactive waste characterization (D2.2)	Deliverable	2.4	Should WAC be harmonized across Europe? If so, how? <i>For this question, EUG members were asked to express their personal point of view regarding the opportunity for WAC harmonisation and if they consider this harmonization as opportune, to express their personal idea on how this can be done.</i>	It is largely considered that WAC harmonisation is neither possible, nor desirable in the case of site-specific criteria (safety relevant parameters), but in terms of the underlying rationale for WAC, the basic assumptions for safety studies, or the potential topics to be evaluated through WAC, harmonisation is considered appropriate and achievable.	desire for WAC harmonisation	H	For share solutions harmonized WAC is needed	3	
H2020 CHANCE	Synthesis of commonly used methodology for conditioned radioactive waste characterization (D2.2)	Deliverable	2.5	<i>EUG members were asked to provide detail on how they are dealing with historical waste and if for this waste they have to characterize more (as required by the current WAC).</i>	Differences in strategies to deal with historical waste are evidenced.	Technical	M	Historical waste represents a challenge for many countries. Harmonization of the strategies may be helpful	3	
H2020 CHANCE	Synthesis of commonly used methodology for conditioned radioactive waste characterization (D2.2)	Deliverable	2.6	<i>EUG members were asked to:</i> <i>(a) specify and give details on the methods applied for radioactive waste characterisation (including characterisation of waste before its conditioning);</i> <i>(b) how the difficult-to-measure radionuclides are correlated with easy-to-measure isotopes;</i> <i>(c) if the chemo-toxicity is correlated with radio-toxicity of the waste;</i> <i>(d) if the measured data are complemented by modeling/calculations and if yes, to specify and describe the models used and if there are any potential needs of codes' validation by National Control Authority.</i>	Commonly used characterisation parameters and challenges regarding characterization were identified.	Technical	H	Important for potential sharing characterisation facilities	3	
H2020 CHANCE	Synthesis of commonly used methodology for conditioned radioactive waste	Deliverable	2.7.	Most of the answers give some general values based on the methods applied. The approach is peculiar for each country but it seems that similar uncertainty levels can be found (about 30-50% on conditioned wastes and lower values for destructive assays depending on the representativeness of the sampling procedures).	This section gives details on the uncertainties and the source of uncertainty in the RW characterisation.	Technical	M	May be relevant for potential shared characterisation facilities	3	

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	characterization (D2.2)			Regarding the <i>target level of uncertainties</i> , generally there are no target values imposed by the authorities.... Regarding the <i>source of the uncertainty</i> , the majority of the answers indicated uncertainties related to geometry, sampling procedures and correlation factors used.... Each country has its own methodologies to decrease the uncertainty based on high quality calibration, statistical methods and sampling programmes, pre-characterization of unconditioned wastes, homogenization of the wastes.....						
H2020 CHANCE	Synthesis of commonly used methodology for conditioned radioactive waste characterization (D2.2)	Deliverable	2.9	All the organizations seem to have to deal with some waste categories that don't have yet a dedicated option for storage.	This section summarizes the RW categories in different European countries for which there is no dedicated option for storage/disposal, as well as the limits for the acceptance of these RW in the existing or future disposal facilities	Technical	M	Potential for shared storage facilities	3	
H2020 CHANCE	Synthesis of commonly used methodology for conditioned radioactive waste characterization (D2.2)	Deliverable	2.10	As is apparent from the received information, matrices and conditioning methods vary on the basis of the waste types. Therefore, depending on their origin and final form, the conditioned waste can have different chemical and radiological composition and therefore specific and different characterization methods have to be used. Despite the use of various conditioning technologies and matrices, there are common difficulties related to the characterization process of the conditioned waste packages.	This section summarizes the major technical difficulties in characterisation of conditioned radioactive waste	Technical	H	Potential for developing shared technical solutions for conditioned RW characterisation	3	
H2020 CHANCE	Synthesis of commonly used methodology for conditioned radioactive waste characterization (D2.2)	Deliverable	2.14	All but one of the respondents specified that the responsibility for the characterisation of the radioactive waste is basically with the waste producers. One respondent included also the waste conditioners and another one the owners of the interim storage facilities. In one case, the characterisation is said to be in the hands of the waste management facility. However, there seem to be different approaches to (or understandings of) the process of characterisation.	This section summarizes the responsibilities in RW characterisation and in control of the characterisation process.	Technical / regulatory	M	Harmonisation of the characterisation and control process may be of interest.	3	
H2020 CHANCE	Synthesis of commonly used methodology for conditioned radioactive waste characterization (D2.2)	Deliverable	2.17	Overall, results seem to suggest that waste characterisation is seen by most respondents as a problem mainly driven by technical considerations (Figure 2). The respondents' answers highlight <i>verification of the declared inventory</i> as the key and most important reason for waste characterisation, followed by the <i>operational safety</i> , and the <i>waste classification in view of disposal choices</i> . All respondents	This section summarises the importance of characterisation	Technical	M	May be relevant for shared characterisation facilities	3	

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				consider the regulatory requirements as a very high or highly important driver for waste characterisation. Social and political uncertainties were mentioned by several respondents as important uncertainties with potentially high impact. Conversely, half of the respondents attributed a high or very high importance to stakeholder involvement as a reason for waste characterisation, and 9 out of 12 to communication.						
H2020 CHANCE	R&D requests in the field of conditioned radioactive characterization (D2.3)	Deliverable	14.	This report summarizes the state-of-the-art in non-destructive waste characterization addressing many of these needs. Distinction can be made between passive and active measurements allowing to obtain insights into the inventory of easy-to-measure and difficult-to-measure radioisotopes and, in the case of active measurements, also of toxic elements, and imaging techniques based on low-energy (for non-conditioned, raw waste) or high-energy (for conditioned waste) X-rays to allow visualization of the inner contents of a waste drum or waste package. These techniques are complemented by recent developments which tackle specific characterization challenges frequently associated with specific waste forms.	Commonly used techniques for RW characterisation are presented in this deliverables as well as the proposed R&D activities for further shared development.	Technical	H	Shared characterisation facilities	3	
H2020 CHANCE	Synthesis of CHANCE project (D6.6)	Synthesis Report	3.1	The analysis of answers received allowed to identify some key parameters that need characterization. These parameters, which depend on the disposal/storage and country considered, can be grouped in four categories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Radiological parameters such as radionuclide activity, dose rate, surface contamination, content of fissile materials, heating power • Chemical parameters such as inventory of toxic species, complexing and chelating agents, accelerators of leaching processes, organic substances, pyrophoric, flammable, corrosive, oxidizing materials • Mechanical parameters such as compression resistance, drop resistance, matrix behaviour (swelling, diffusivity and leachability) • Other parameters such as hydrogen production, homogeneity of the waste, parameter associated to disposal container (physical dimensions and weight) 	Commonly used characterisation parameters and challenges regarding characterization were identified.	Technical	H	Important for sharing characterisation facilities	3	
H2020 EURAD										
H2020 EURAD	Strategic Research Agenda. Scientific and technical domains and sub-domains and knowledge management needs of common interest between EURAD participants	SRA	Theme 1: managing implementation and oversight of a radioactive waste management programme – p5 R&D priorities and activities of common interest	EU research infrastructure: To document the extent of European research infrastructure and competencies and establish conditions allowing for transnational access to and/or sharing of facilities and established networks (J3.15/High). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Expected outcomes and impact: Improved understanding of the breadth and depth of research infrastructure across Europe. - Cooperation and relevant past projects: possibility to explore training / mobility exchange at some sites / URLs 	Enhance sharing of facilities to conduct R&D	Technological	H	This fits within WP3 objectives.	3	

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H2020 EURAD	Strategic Research Agenda. Scientific and technical domains and sub-domains and knowledge management needs of common interest between EURAD participants	SRA	Theme 1: managing implementation and oversight of a radioactive waste management programme – p5 R&D priorities and activities of common interest	How to establish and implement a radioactive waste management RD&D programme: To develop a common guidance document to support waste management programmes, including disposal, with establishment and implementation of a RD&D programme (Originates from needs identified by the IGD-TP PLANDIS Guide. • Training and competence maintenance of skills and expertise to support safe radioactive waste management including disposal: To ensure knowledge is managed and disseminated, and that there is competence maintenance, education and training of the workforce (J3.16). • Information management: To maintain information, knowledge and records over the long lead- and implementation-timelines of geological disposal programmes, from pre-licensing through to the post-operational phase (J3.14/Medium	Developing a common guidance document to support less advanced waste management programmes to establish and implementation of an R&D plan Ensuring LT knowledge management/transfer and proper training	Harmonisation & Societal	L	Linked to HARPERS activities, but not within the primary objectives. KM oriented.	7	Past activities: link (IGD-TP Plandis Guide) EC ANNETTE project (2012-2019) On-going activities: EURAD1 WP on Knowledge Management
H2020 EURAD	Strategic Research Agenda. Scientific and technical domains and sub-domains and knowledge management needs of common interest between EURAD participants	SRA	Theme 2: radioactive waste characterisation, processing and storage (pre-disposal), and source term understanding for disposal P 8 Introduction & background	Multi-national, regional or shared facilities Some programmes across Europe consider the feasibility of regional or shared facilities (including multi-national repositories) that can provide infrastructure for all, or part, of the waste management route for a specific waste type. Planning of such facilities encompasses important and innovative developments (including the legal framework), which have been considered in work under the auspices of the EC or IAEA (See, IAEA - Developing multi-national radioactive waste repositories). Within EURAD, scope undertaken to understand waste management routes, as part of pre-disposal activities may consider aspects that are important to those national programmes that consider the use of multi-national, regional or shared facilities.	Shared facilities	Regulatory Legal Societal Technological Harmonisation	H	In line with main objectives of WP3&6	3, 6	https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCDF/Publications/PDF/TE-1658_web.pdf see also ERDO gap analysis
H2020 EURAD	Strategic Research Agenda. Scientific and technical domains and sub-domains and knowledge management needs of common interest between EURAD participants	SRA	Theme 2: radioactive waste characterisation, processing and storage (pre-disposal), and source term understanding for disposal P 9 -10 RD&D priorities and activities of common interest	Identifying good practice in the management of inventory data and uncertainty treatment. - Expected outcomes and impact: Improved understanding of those species that dominate the transport, operations and post-closure safety cases and targeted fit-for-purpose assay that can enable cost-effective data quality improvements (J1.1.1/High). - Cooperation and relevant past projects: EC FIRST Nuclides project	Identifying good practices for management of inventory data and uncertainty treatment	Harmonisation	L	Related to harmonisation practices, but not directly linked to any of the major WP objectives	3	Relevant past projects: EC FIRST Nuclides project Link to on-going projects: UMAN?
H2020 EURAD	Strategic Research Agenda. Scientific and technical domains and sub-	SRA	Theme 2: radioactive waste characterisation, processing and	Developing novel conditioning technologies for non-mature and problematic waste.	Sharing good practices for conditioning technologies for problematic waste	Technological /Harmonisation	H	Links with objectives of different HARPERS WP's.	3, 4, 5, 6	On-going project:

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	domains and knowledge management needs of common interest between EURAD participants		storage (pre-disposal), and source term understanding for disposal P 9 -10 RD&D priorities and activities of common interest	- Expected outcomes and impact: Identification and sharing of good practice and in waste conditioning and packaging approaches for problematic wastes (J1.1.3/High). - Cooperation and relevant past projects: Check for EU-wide waste producers forum?						EURAD1-WP ROUTES
H2020 EURAD	Strategic Research Agenda. Scientific and technical domains and sub-domains and knowledge management needs of common interest between EURAD participants	SRA	Theme 2: radioactive waste characterisation, processing and storage (pre-disposal), and source term understanding for disposal P 9 -10 RD&D priorities and activities of common interest	Developing reliable and affordable technologies for the radiological characterization and segregation of historical preconditioned radioactive waste. - Expected outcomes and impact: Develop and demonstrate enhanced and/or novel non-destructive assay techniques (which maintain waste package integrity and containment) to provide quality assurance of packages being stored, transported or received at a disposal facility (J1.1.2/Medium). - Cooperation and relevant past projects: EC CHANCE project	Development of reliable and affordable non-destructive characterisation methods that enables quality check against Waste Acceptance Criteria	Technological	H	In line with objectives of HARPERS	3, 4, 5	relevant past projects: EC CHANCE project
H2020 EURAD	Strategic Research Agenda. Scientific and technical domains and sub-domains and knowledge management needs of common interest between EURAD participants	SRA	Theme 2: radioactive waste characterisation, processing and storage (pre-disposal), and source term understanding for disposal P 9 -10 RD&D priorities and activities of common interest	Optimisation of radioactive waste treatment techniques where there is potential for volume/hazard reduction and potential cost savings. - Expected outcomes and impact: Optimisation of waste treatment options leading to potential benefits in terms of Waste Acceptance Criteria, safety demonstration, volume and hazard reduction and cost savings (J1.1.8/Medium). - Cooperation and relevant past projects: EC projects CAST, Carbowaste and THERAMIN	Optimisation of radioactive waste treatment techniques leading to potential benefits in terms of WAC, safety demonstration, volume and hazard reduction, cost savings	Technological	H	In line with objectives of HARPERS	3, 4, 5	past projects: EC projects CAST, Carbowaste and THERAMIN On-going project: EURAD1-WP ROUTES?
H2020 EURAD	Strategic Research Agenda. Scientific and technical domains and sub-domains and knowledge management needs of common interest between EURAD participants	SRA	Theme 2: radioactive waste characterisation, processing and storage (pre-disposal), and source term understanding for disposal P 9 -10 RD&D priorities and activities of common interest	Fourth generation (Gen IV) wastes. - Expected outcomes and impact: To understand the nature and quantities of wastes arising from a fourth generation of nuclear reactors, identify challenges to the disposal of such wastes and enable early feedback to reactor system designers in order to mitigate associated risks (J1.1.6/Low). - Cooperation and relevant past projects: ?	Identify during design phase of GenIV reactors challenges wrt. waste streams	Technological	L	Linked to HARPERS actions but not to specific objectives	5?	

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H2020 EURAD	Strategic Research Agenda. Scientific and technical domains and sub-domains and knowledge management needs of common interest between EURAD participants	SRA	Theme 2: radioactive waste characterisation, processing and storage (pre-disposal), and source term understanding for disposal p 11 Enabling KM, strategic studies and other cross cutting activities identified of common interest	Strengthened links between Implementers and Waste Producers: To enhance cooperation in the process of spent fuel and nuclear waste disposal solutions and to improve understanding of spent fuel arisings, including those from innovative fuel types (J3.7)	Strengthening links between implementers and waste producers	Harmonisation	H	Stakeholder engagement	2, 6	
H2020 EURAD	Strategic Research Agenda. Scientific and technical domains and sub-domains and knowledge management needs of common interest between EURAD participants	SRA	Theme 2: radioactive waste characterisation, processing and storage (pre-disposal), and source term understanding for disposal p 11 Enabling KM, strategic studies and other cross cutting activities identified of common interest	Inventory collation and forecasting: To ensure that all countries implementing a disposal facility develop a comprehensive inventory (J3.5).	To ensure that all countries implementing a disposal facility develop a comprehensive inventory	Harmonisation	L	Linked to HARPERS actions but not to specific objectives	3	
H2020 EURAD	Strategic Research Agenda. Scientific and technical domains and sub-domains and knowledge management needs of common interest between EURAD participants	SRA	Theme 2: radioactive waste characterisation, processing and storage (pre-disposal), and source term understanding for disposal p 11 Enabling KM, strategic studies and other cross cutting activities identified of common interest	Waste acceptance criteria: To develop good practice guides for the derivation of waste acceptance criteria and increase confidence in, and further refinement of, inventory uncertainty quantification methods, including sensitivity studies (J2.1.6).	To develop good practice guides for the derivation of WAC	Harmonisation	H	WAC are cornerstone of disposal. Harmonisation between countries would be highly beneficial. Fits HARPERS main objectives	6	

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H2020 EURAD	Strategic Research Agenda. Scientific and technical domains and sub-domains and knowledge management needs of common interest between EURAD participants	SRA	Theme 5: Geological disposal facility design and the practicalities of construction, operations and closure p 24-25 RD&D priorities and activities of common interest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developing cost-effective asset management strategies for use in the design. - Expected outcomes and impact: To enable definition of the requirements arising from the upkeep and improvement of assets in the facility design, including a preliminary asset management strategy (J2.5.8/Medium) - Cooperation and relevant past projects: ? 	Developing cost-effective asset management strategies for use in the design	Harmonisation	L	Linked to HARPERS actions but not to specific objectives	3, 4, 5	
H2020 EURAD	Strategic Research Agenda. Scientific and technical domains and sub-domains and knowledge management needs of common interest between EURAD participants	SRA	Theme 5: Geological disposal facility design and the practicalities of construction, operations and closure p 24-25 RD&D priorities and activities of common interest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assessment of the technical feasibility and lifecycle adaptation of a geological disposal concept for a specific site and specific nuclear waste type. - Expected outcomes and impact: Development of a common view on areas of significant safety impact with respect to technical feasibility of a geological disposal concept. Development of change control approaches to appropriately capture design adaptation and feedback into safety assessment (J2.5.5& 3.8/Low). - Cooperation and relevant past projects:? 	Assessment of the technical feasibility and lifecycle adaptation of a geological disposal concept for a specific site and specific nuclear waste type	Harmonisation	L	Linked to HARPERS actions but not to specific objectives	4, 5	
H2020 EURAD	Strategic Research Agenda. Scientific and technical domains and sub-domains and knowledge management needs of common interest between EURAD participants	SRA	Theme 5: Geological disposal facility design and the practicalities of construction, operations and closure p 24-25 Enabling KM, strategic studies and other cross cutting activities identified of common interest	Reversibility: To develop a common position across Europe, and to exchange good practices (J3.17).	To develop a common position across Europe, and to exchange good practices	Harmonisation Technology Regulatory	M	To achieve a common position on this topic, legal and regulatory issues need to be checked	6	
H2020 EURAD	Strategic Research Agenda. Scientific and technical domains and sub-domains and knowledge management needs of common interest between EURAD participants	SRA	Theme 7: performance assessment, safety case development and safety analysis P 32 RD&D priorities and activities of common interest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved understanding of the influence of pre-closure disturbances on long-term safety. - Expected outcomes and impact: To develop common approaches (including scenarios) for safety case adaptation and update during facility operations and closure (J2.1.1/Medium). - Cooperation and relevant past projects: ? 	Develop common approaches for safety case adaptation during facility operation	Harmonisation Regulatory	M	To achieve a common position on this topic, legal and regulatory issues need to be checked	6	
H2020 EURAD	Strategic Research Agenda. Scientific	SRA	Theme 7: performance	Further refinement of methods to make sensitivity and uncertainty analyses.	Develop common approaches to	Harmonisation Regulatory	M/L	To achieve common approaches on this topic,	6	

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	and technical domains and sub-domains and knowledge management needs of common interest between EURAD participants		assessment, safety case development and safety analysis P 32 RD&D priorities and activities of common interest	- Expected outcomes and impact: Develop common approaches to demonstrate operational and post-closure safety and overall facility lifecycle evolution. Improved uncertainty treatment (models and data) using evolution scenarios (i.e. improved system representation during different timescales and for complex scenarios such as those involving multiple strongly coupled processes) (J2.1.3/Medium). - Cooperation and relevant past projects: ?	demonstrate operational and post-closure safety and overall facility lifecycle evolution			legal and regulatory issues need to be checked		
H2020 EURAD	Documents of Interest published on EURAD website		Entire paper		Main topics: - Sustainable management of radioactive materials and waste: Explanation of radioactive waste classes; Integrated approach to radioactive materials and waste management; Current trends and influencing factors; - Recommendations and observations for effective on decommissioning; - Disposal for HLW treatments International progress towards Geological Disposal Facility (GDF); Explore National approaches Relevance of waste disposal to the sustainability of nuclear power	desire for harmonisation	M	Main topic of WP6	6	
H2020 EURAD SFC										
H2020 EURAD SFC	State-of-the-art report (D8.1)	Deliverable	SFC is an RD&D Work Package (WP) within EURAD. The results obtained within the WP will provide a rigorous scientific approach to developing the technical bases for continued safe and secure	Accurately determining the source term and evolution of spent fuel is fundamental to safety assessments	The conclusion can be valuable for HARPERS, when ready (2024) HARPERS should add to their measurement process our own proposal – use existing in core fuel management codes. We can add a part with evidence that it is more than good enough!	Economic and Technology (harmonisation)	H	There is clearly a need for harmonization with respect to fuel source terms, related to disposal (and long-term intermediate storage). Today the lack thereof causes unnecessary troubles (money and need to develop their own regulations and requirements) for both	5	They do include the in-core fuel management codes in the project! So, even more value for HARPERS

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			storage of spent nuclear fuel Ongoing project, ends 2024		Very important is if they manage to suggest or define the level of accuracy required in the data. This alone will bring a lot of value if all can agree on that basic requirement alone.			waste owners, authorities and disposal sites.		
H2020 EURAD SFC	State-of-the-art report (D8.1)	Deliverable	2.1 Observables and nuclides of interest	Due to the number of radionuclides that are present in spent nuclear fuel, spent fuel assemblies need to be characterised for their neutron and γ -ray emission properties and decay heat in view of the safety criteria for casks and canisters for transport, interim storage, and final disposal. In addition to the FPs and actinides, other dose-relevant and safety related radionuclides are generated, mainly by neutron activation of fuel/cladding impurities (e.g. ^{14}C , ^{36}Cl , ^{41}Ca , ^{59}Ni , ^{63}Ni , ^{93}Mo and ^{94}Nb). These nuclides are of importance for long-term safety assessments in waste disposal conditions up to about one million years. Criticality safety assessments for spent nuclear fuel management based on a BUC approach require a nuclide inventory prediction involving far more nuclides than in a conservative approach based on the inventory of fresh fuel.	Need for the identification of key radionuclides that shall be considered in the safety cases and environmental impact assessments for storage, transport and disposal.	Technological Environmental	M	Related to safety and environmental assessments	6	
H2020 EURAD SFC	State-of-the-art report (D8.1)	Deliverable	2.1 Observables and nuclides of interest	The IAEA lists the development of safeguards equipment to establish and maintain knowledge of spent fuel in shielding/storage/transport containers at all points in their life cycle as a top priority in their R&D needs [IAEA, 2018a]. Evidently, nuclear safety, security and safeguards require similar or complementary measures for documenting, measuring and monitoring spent fuel characteristics. Therefore, synergies inherent in overlapping methods or techniques should be identified to avoid redundancy or duplication of work and equipment [Niemeyer, 2016; Lindgren, 2019].	Possible need for the harmonization of requirements to avoid redundancy or duplication	Harmonisation	L	Related to observation than need or recommendation	6	
H2020 EURAD SFC	State-of-the-art report (D8.1)	Deliverable	2.3.Sources of bias effects and uncertainties	Independent of the methodology that is applied the final accuracy depends on input data which can be classified into nuclear data and fuel history data.	Need for the recommendations what uncertainties and how shall be considered in the assessments	Technological	M	Related to safety assessment	6	
H2020 EURAD SFC	State-of-the-art report (D8.1)	Deliverable	2.5.3.Verification of transport and storage casks	The growing number of casks increases the probability of loss of CoK (Continuity of Knowledge). A reverification of the contents by opening the cask is an extremely costly and time consuming procedure. Therefore, there is a strong interest in NDA techniques to verify casks.	Need for the recommendations in case of records/knowledge are lost.	Technological	M	Related to safety	6	

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H2020 EURAD SFC	State-of-the-art report (D8.1)	Deliverable	4. Accident scenarios	The choice of an appropriate range of scenarios and associated assessment cases is essential for the safety assessment of any nuclear facility (e.g. power plant, wet storage, dry storage, encapsulation facility, etc.) or specific activity/process (e.g. SNF transport, handling, etc.). Once identified, these scenarios should take into account existing and potential hazards arising from the facility/process, and also their interrelation and evolution over the lifetime of the facility or defined processes according to the safety case.	Need for the recommendations on bounding accidents/scenarios	Technological Environmental	M	Related to safety	6	For instance, the bounding design basis accidents for NPP is lost of coolant accident. Maybe such bounding accidents or “what if” scenarios can be identified for storage, disposal also.
H2020 EURAD SFC	Website https://igdtp.eu/activity/sfc-spent-fuel-characterisation-and-evolution-until-disposal/	Website	SFC is an RD&D Work Package (WP) within EURAD. The WP will develop and document an experimentally verified procedure to accurately determine the source term of irradiated spent fuels Ongoing project, ends 2024	Accurately determining the source term and evolution of spent fuel is fundamental to safety assessments	The conclusion can be valuable for HARPERS, when ready (2024) HARPERS should add to their measurement process our own proposal – use existing in-core fuel management codes. We can add a part with evidence that it is more than good enough! Very important is if they manage to suggest or define the level of accuracy required in the data. This alone will bring a lot of value if all can agree on that basic requirement alone.	Economic and Technology (harmonisation)	H	There is clearly a need for harmonization with respect to fuel source terms, related to disposal (and long term intermediate storage). Today the lack thereof cause unnecessary troubles (money and need to develop their own regulations and requirements) for both waste owners, authorities and disposal sites.	5	I disagree with their aim/objective completely! The need is not there. There are very good in core fuel management codes available commercially (more than 2) that easily gives enough accuracy.
H2020 EURAD UMAN										
H2020 EURAD UMAN	UMAN - Analysis and description of groups of different actors	Deliverable	1.2 Methodology	Such programmes [of countries with small radioactive waste inventories] typically consider the construction of a dedicated national geological repository unfeasible and work in pursuit of economical ways for disposing of small amounts of radioactive waste, either through the possibility of shared regional facilities, borehole disposal or through a focus on a long-term storage.	Need for shared best practice, services/facilities and harmonized RWM approach for optimization of RWM.	Economic / legal / harmonisation	M	Related to optimisation of economic resources and harmonisation of regulations / practices. However, mostly relevant for limited number of countries.	3, 4, 6	
H2020 EURAD UMAN	UMAN - Analysis and description of groups of different actors	Deliverable	4.2	An overview of all identified actors and their number of indications is given in Figure 3 and Table 4, including both phase-specific and generic answers of <i>WMOs</i> , <i>TSOs</i> , <i>REs</i> and one <i>TCC</i> . The number of	This deliverable summarizes the answer received to UMAN questionnaire related to the actors, their	Regulatory	H	Different actors involved in RWM may have different opinion regarding harmonisation, so it is important to have	3	

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				indications for each actor category, depicted on the vertical axis of the diagram, represents the sum of all indications made by each <i>WMO</i> , <i>TSO</i> , <i>RE</i> and one <i>TCC</i> for the considered actor categories across all themes in all phases (Tab. 4).	roles, impact and interest in different phases of a RMW programme. Answer institutions belong to <i>WMOs</i> , <i>TSOs</i> and <i>REs</i> . Based on the answer received all categories of actors were characterised with respect to their engagement into all phases of the RWM programme.			opinion of all categories of actors		
H2020 EURAD UMAN	UMAN - Analysis and description of groups of different actors	Deliverable	6. Recommendations for future EURAD activities	In order to improve the understanding and the transparency of these complex interactions among the identified actors, it might be of interest to apply a social network analysis to visualise these interactions graphically using a database as complete as possible.	Need for actors (involved in RWM) interactions visualisation through network analysis.	Regulatory, harmonisation	M	Potential to identify weak points in actors' interactions in order to reduce the uncertainties that cannot be reduced by RD&D activities.	6	
H2020 EURAD UMAN	UMAN - Analysis and description of groups of different actors	Deliverable	8. Conclusions	Grouping of the actors identified at national level by the responding organisations from 19 countries was challenging due to the specifics of their national RWM programmes (including their current implementation stage), political and administrative systems.	The observation suggests to investigate possibility of harmonisation of role of actors	Harmonisation	L	Related to harmonisation of RWM, but could be limited possibilities due to country- specific RWM implementation stage and regulation system.	6	
H2020 EURAD UMAN	UMAN - Analysis and description of groups of different actors	Deliverable	8. Conclusions	Further difficulties arise from the fact that the roles of the actors in the countries running RWM programmes and disposal facilities licensed under different political systems do not fully correspond to the responsibilities defined by the current international standards as the implementation of the latter is a long process.	Need for harmonisation of actors (involved in RWM) responsibilities with international standards.	Harmonisation	L	More relevant at the country level.	6	
H2020 EURAD UMAN	UMAN - Analysis and description of groups of different actors	Deliverable	8. Conclusions	The types and number of actors identified varied among the responding organisations, reflecting the different approaches employed in the national RWM programmes as well as the different national frameworks and thus political and administrative systems of the countries represented by these respondents.	The observation suggests to investigate possibility of harmonisation of the different national RWM frameworks.	Harmonisation	L	Related to harmonisation of RWM, but could be limited possibilities due to country- specific regulation system.	6	
H2020 EURAD UMAN	UMAN - Analysis and description of groups of different actors	Deliverable	8. Conclusions	The analysis of the replies of the responding organisations to the 1st UMAN questionnaire shows a need for the establishment of a more specific and detailed picture of the 'other actors' (i.e. the actors of categories different from <i>WMOs</i> , <i>TSOs</i> and <i>REs</i>), involved in the RWM programme.	Harmonisation of role of actors other than <i>WMO</i> , <i>TSO</i> and <i>RE</i> in the RWM.	Harmonisation	M	Related to harmonisation of RWM	6	
H2020 EURAD UMAN	UMAN - Analysis and description of groups of different actors	Deliverable	8. Conclusions	Further, heterogeneous communities of 'other actors' could be established, contributing to future EURAD activities.	Establishment of actors' community (other than <i>WMO</i> , <i>TSO</i> and <i>RE</i>) and involvement in RWM.	Regulatory, societal	M	Related to better communication between different actors in RWM.	6	

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H2020 INSIDER										
H2020 INSIDER	Metrology applications to D&D issues: issues at stake for INSIDER European project	Article	2.2 Metrological scheme 2.2.1 General considerations	While the metrological scheme for laboratory analyses is well established, based on Certified Reference Materials (CRM) and ILC, additional work remains to be done for on-site measurements in the case of D&D issues.	Harmonization of good practices and recommendations need for for on-site measurements.	Technological, regulatory	M	Related to implementation of advanced technologies and harmonisation of regulations/ practices	5, 6	
H2020 INSIDER	Metrology applications to D&D issues: issues at stake for INSIDER European project	Article	2.3 Metrology perspectives	The tools previously described and optimized in the framework of nuclear fuel cycle analysis should be used and adapted to these new problematics but also to regulatory and financial new requirements.	The INSIDER waste-led methodology needs to be adapted to regulatory requirements.	Regulatory	M	Related to implementation of advanced technologies and harmonisation of regulations/ practices	5	
H2020 INSIDER	Identification of Needs for Innovative Technologies (D2.4)	Deliverable	2.3 Gap analysis	Development of in-situ methods for alpha/beta emitters	Need for advanced technologies to improve RWM and D&D	Technological	L	Development rather than implementation	5	
H2020 INSIDER	Identification of Needs for Innovative Technologies (D2.4)	Deliverable	2.3 Gap analysis	NDA metrological tools with lower detection limits	Need for advanced technologies to improve RWM and D&D	Technological	L	Development rather than implementation	5	
H2020 INSIDER	Identification of Needs for Innovative Technologies (D2.4)	Deliverable	2.3 Gap analysis	Statistical or geostatistical software for spatial distribution of the activity and for the Scaling Factors analysis	Need for advanced technologies to improve RWM and D&D	Technological	M	Related to implementation of advanced technologies and harmonisation of regulations/ practices	5	
H2020 INSIDER	Identification of Needs for Innovative Technologies (D2.4)	Deliverable	2.3 Gap analysis	Optimisation of sampling and in particular determination of the representativeness of samples	Need for advanced technologies to improve RWM and D&D	Technological	M	Related to implementation of advanced technologies and harmonisation of regulations/ practices	5, 6	
H2020 INSIDER	Identification of Needs for Innovative Technologies (D2.4)	Deliverable	2.3 Gap analysis	Mobile high-sensitive measurement equipment	Need for advanced technologies to improve RWM and D&D	Technological	L	Development rather than implementation	5	
H2020 INSIDER	Good Practices in Waste Minimization in Decommissioning Project (D2.6)	Deliverable	8 Conclusion	$\langle \square \rangle$ηρωεπερ, ιτ ισ νεχεσσαρψ το γετ χομμον η ελλοωορλδμεασυρινη παλιδατιονσ φρομ λαβο ρατορψ το δεχομμισσιονινη σιτε σχαλε ανδ το ιμπροπε ραδιολογιχαλ ηελλοωορλδχαρτογραπη ψ ιν ορδερ το ρεδυχε σχεναριο υνχερταιντιεσ;	Need for validation of small representatives to whole decommissioning site and radiological cartography improvements	Technological	L	Development rather than implementation	5	
H2020 INSIDER	Good Practices in Waste Minimization in Decommissioning Project (D2.6)	Deliverable	8 Conclusion	Examples of solid waste decontamination results have shown that it is possible to change the classification of a contaminated metals, passing from LLW to VLLW and to release a vast amount of soils from regulatory control.	Driver to harmonise good decontamination practices in changing soils classification.	Harmonisation, economic, environmental	M	Related to harmonisation of regulations/ practices	6	
H2020 INSIDER	Good Practices in Waste Minimization in Decommissioning Project (D2.6)	Deliverable	8 Conclusion	as an example, under optimal operating conditions, studies have shown that the laser cutting technique induces lower aerosols than most other thermal cutting processes and also limits the production of slag	Driver to harmonise good segmentation practices by using laser cutting.	Harmonization, technological, environmental	M	Related to harmonisation of regulations/ practices	5, 6	
H2020 INSIDER	Good Practices in Waste Minimization	Deliverable	8 Conclusion	For solid waste, the different treatments, such as incineration, fusion/recycling or compaction allow a	Driver to harmonise good volume reduction practices.	Harmonization, technological,	M	Related to harmonisation of regulations/ practices	5, 6	

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	in Decommissioning Project (D2.6)			volume reduction in between 3 to 20, depending on the type of materials, of activity level and treatment used;		environmental, economic				
H2020 INSIDER	Good Practices in Waste Minimization in Decommissioning Project (D2.6)	Deliverable	8 Conclusion	In the case of liquid waste (aqueous and organic), treatment such as evaporation, precipitation/filtration or incineration, the volume reduction is higher than 10 (up to 150), after secondary waste conditioning. The decontaminated liquid or gaseous aerosols are released in the environment after control.	Driver to harmonise good volume reduction practices.	Harmonization, technological, environmental, economic	M	Related to harmonisation of regulations/ practices	5, 6	
H2020 INSIDER	Report on the state of the art (D3.1)	Deliverable	6 Conclusion	<...> Moreover, many of the generic sampling design techniques and state-of-the-art statistical techniques used in preliminary analyses and data processing are often considered as stand-alone methods. In many cases, an integrated and overall approach of pre-decommissioning characterization which notably consists in evaluating historical data, making on-site measurement campaigns, sampling and analysing, developing scaling factors and applying numerical codes, is missing.	Need for more harmonised and integrated approach in pre-decommissioning characterisation.	Technological, harmonisation	M	Related to harmonisation of regulations/ practices	6	
H2020 INSIDER	Recommendations (D7.15)	Deliverable	3.2 WP3 - Sampling strategy	As a consequence, this cannot be converted directly into a standard, even if, for very specific cases, the possibility to standardize some conclusion of the guideline proposed by INSIDER could be studied.	Need for standardization of some conclusion of the guideline proposed by INSIDER.	Technological, regulatory	M	Related to implementation of advanced technologies and harmonisation of regulations/ practices	5, 6	
H2020 INSIDER	Recommendations (D7.15)		3.3 WP4 - Reference materials and radiochemistry	The lack of international standards (reference material) for new methods and nuclides.	Need for standards for new methods and nuclides	Technological	L	Development rather than implementation	5	
H2020 INSIDER	Recommendations (D7.15)		3.3 WP4 - Reference materials and radiochemistry	The differences in regulations across the EU regarding decommissioning and nuclear waste minimization / recycling	Need for harmonized regulations to facilitate radwaste minimization / recycling	Regulatory, harmonisation	M	Related to circular economy and harmonisation of regulations/ practices	5, 6	
H2020 INSIDER	Recommendations (D7.15)		3.3 WP4 - Reference materials and radiochemistry	The lack of compliance legislation in decommissioning	Need for compliance legislation in decommissioning	Legal	M	Related to harmonisation of regulations/ legislation	6	
SNETP (INSIDER)	The European Project INSIDER (P2021)	Presentation	Slide No. 8 Conclusions & perspectives	Support to D&D Standards (sampling, measurements and validated methods, ...)	Project coordinator highlighted potential further needs\gaps related to standards.	Technological, regulatory	M	Related to implementation of advanced technologies and harmonisation of regulations/ standards	5, 6	
SNETP (INSIDER)	The European Project INSIDER (P2021)		Slide No. 8 Conclusions & perspectives	Decommissioning standardized practices, remediation issues	Project coordinator highlighted potential further needs\gaps related to standards.	Regulatory	M	Related to harmonisation of regulations/ standards	6	
SNETP (INSIDER)	The European Project INSIDER (P2021)		Slide No. 8 Conclusions & perspectives	Characterisation process contribution to circular economy	Project coordinator highlighted potential further needs\gaps related to circular economy.	Technological	M	Related to implementation of advanced technologies and circular economy	4, 5	

H2020 Metrodecom

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H2020 Metrodec m	http://empir.npl.co.uk/metrodec/m/	website	Homepage	Ninety-one power plants are being decommissioned in the EU; most of the remaining 129 reactors plus fuel cycle facilities will also be in decommissioning by 2030.	The extent of the decommissioning	All	H	Fundamental consideration to understand the extent of the issue	3, 4, 5, 6	
H2020 Metrodec m	http://empir.npl.co.uk/metrodec/m/	website	Homepage	Regulatory bodies and international organisations have therefore carried out detailed studies of technical needs in the field. The common themes that have been raised are: (1) improvements in capability, (2) harmonisation and quality assurance, and (3) sharing knowledge. The improvements in capability that are required include rapid, on site measurements, improving the accuracy and traceability of measurements of waste packages.	Technical needs by regulatory bodies and international organisations	All	H	This source is important to define needs for advanced technologies	5	
H2020 Metrodec m	http://empir.npl.co.uk/metrodec/m/	website	Impact	The project incorporates two major facilities: the waste-package sentencing system and the waste-repository measurement system. The immediate impact from these facilities will be accurate, traceable, regulatory-compliant assessments of radioactive waste for the nuclear sites where the facilities are located, but the use of these facilities for training is intended to disseminate best practice and traceability to all nuclear sites operating waste package measurement systems.	The importance of training and dissemination of best practice	Technological Regulatory Harmonisation	H	Training and dissemination are necessary for the harmonisation	3, 4, 5, 6	
H2020 Metrodec m	http://empir.npl.co.uk/metrodec/m/	website		This project will have an impact on standards being developed by the International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO); these standards are referred to by laboratories and measurement scientists throughout the nuclear industry and are also adopted in national standards. The technical findings will be fed back for incorporation in standards under development and new work items covering topics such as the use of sensor networks will be proposed to ISO/TC85/SC2/WG17. The work will contribute to national good practice guides, such as the proposed UK Nuclear Industry Code of Practice for site characterisation.	The importance of standards for a harmonised technical approach	Technological Harmonisation	H	To contribute to update of standards is crucial for harmonisation	5	
H2020 Metrodec m	http://empir.npl.co.uk/metrodec/m/	website	Blog – Remote characterisation in nuclear facilities	Aim: To develop in-situ methods for the rapid radionuclide characterisation of the different types of materials present on decommissioning sites. The methods will improve the remote mapping of contamination and doses inside nuclear facilities and thus enable the disposition of activity to be determined and characterised, so that decommissioning work can be planned. A system for real-time dose-rate mapping will be developed. The system will consist of a large number of cheap compact radiation detectors, linked wirelessly to a central computer. In addition to establishing a calibration method, software will be developed to create dose maps with a low uncertainty (due to the large number of detectors used).	The need of in-situ methods for rapid characterisation through remote mapping of contamination and doses	Technological	M	This source is important to define needs and opportunities for advanced technologies	5	

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H2020 Metrodecodem	http://empir.npl.co.uk/metrodecodem/	website	Blog – Radiochemical analysis procedures	The determination of alpha- and beta-particle emitting radionuclides in decommissioning materials is one of the critical points of material characterisation in this area, because they need to be radiochemically separated before measurement and the materials are difficult to process from the chemical point of view. In order to support the nuclear decommissioning, work package 1 involves the development radiochemical strategies for the analysis of some of these radionuclides (41Ca, 90Sr, 93Zr, uranium and plutonium isotopes) in materials which are of particular interest in this field, such as concrete or graphite. These procedures need to be robust and rapid so that they can be adapted easily for automated systems such as the NiVTM device or for small on-site laboratories.	The need of new rapid and robust procedures for determination of alpha and beta emitting radionuclides in concrete and graphite.	Technological	M	This source is important to define needs and opportunities for advanced technologies	5	
H2020 Metrodecodem	http://empir.npl.co.uk/metrodecodem/	website	Blog – ‘Pre-selection and free release measurement facility’ ‘Waste pre-selection and free release measurement facility’ ‘Free release measurement facility update’ ‘Free release measurement facility’	‘The facility for pre-selection and free release measurement of wastes for nuclear facilities will be installed, tested and calibrated on decommissioning site during the course of this project.’ ‘The facility will have scintillating detectors for pre-selection of wastes and germanium detectors for free release measurement. The facility will be surrounded by low activity concrete shielding to meet the limits given by national nuclear regulators for unconditional release of wastes from nuclear facilities in the environment.’ ‘The Free Release Measurement Facility, which is being validated in MetroDECOMII, was installed in CIEMAT, Madrid in the beginning of 2019.’ ‘The Free Release Measurement Facility (FRMF) based on the 4 HPGe detectors and low-level background concrete shielding and installed in Madrid at Spanish designated metrology institute CIEMAT has been calibrated using Monte Carlo codes MCNP and PENELOPE, and the calibration validated by measurement of reference materials and radionuclide sources standardized by European metrology institutes. (...) The mass activities measured at the facility and in laboratories have been determined and compared. Good agreement between has been achieved and maximum deviation between laboratory and on-site measurements did not exceed 10%.’	The need of a free release measurement facility to characterise all materials from shut-down nuclear facilities and decide if they have to be stored in a radioactive waste repository or sent to landfill.	Technological, Regulatory, Economic, Environmental	H	This source is important to define needs and opportunities for advanced technologies. It is also crucial for the potential reduction of radioactive waste volumes, for the circular economy and for the environment.	4, 5	
H2020 Metrodecodem	http://empir.npl.co.uk/metrodecodem/	website	Blog – Validation of a waste characterisation system for low and intermediate level radioactive waste	Expected outcome To develop a validate waste repository acceptance characterisation system for use on site with very low, low and intermediate level radioactive waste. The assay will include gamma scanning and active/passive neutron measurements (sensitive to fissile materials) to complete the characterisation of the waste items.	The need of a validate waste repository acceptance characterisation system for use on site with very low, low and intermediate level radioactive waste.	Technological	M	This source is important to define needs and opportunities for advanced technologies	5	

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					The new system based on gamma scanning and active/passive neutron measurements proposed by MetroDecomII					
H2020 Metrodecom	http://empir.npl.co.uk/metrodecom/	website	Blog - Air and water monitoring by on-line liquid scintillation	The regular monitoring of air and water samples in and around civil nuclear sites (both active and during the process of decommissioning) and waste repositories is of key importance, both in terms of ensuring that any possible contamination resulting from leaks or spills is detected in a timely fashion and to satisfy the regulatory and environmental demands of government bodies and regulators. Currently, the periodic manual sampling, analysis and reporting process is resource heavy in terms of both the cost and time (sometime weeks) required to obtain, analyse and collate the data arising from measurements of manually acquired samples. In order to improve monitoring schemes at these sites and move towards a supplemental 'on-line' measurement approach, LabLogic Systems have been engaged with the design, development and evaluation of an innovative radioactivity monitoring system, which was developed in conjunction with the US EPA originally and is known as 'Wilma'.	The need of fast and on-line air and water monitoring around civil nuclear sites (even during decommissioning) and waste repositories. A new system based on liquid scintillation proposed by MetroDecomII.	Technological	M	This source is important to define needs and opportunities for advanced technologies	5	
H2020 Metrodecom	http://empir.npl.co.uk/metrodecom/	website	Blog - Strain and temperature sensors	Distributed Strain and Temperature Sensors (DSTS) by optical fibres are quite promising methods for the long-term (a few decades typically) structure health monitoring. As responsible operators, Andra and EDF are evaluating the feasibility to deploy such systems in their respective facilities: prospective underground radioactive waste repositories in the one hand, and hydraulics facilities (dams, dikes, water pipe-lines) in the other hand.	The need of long-term structure health monitoring and the new system developed by Andra and EDF based on Distributed Strain and Temperature Sensors	Technological	M	This source is important to define needs and opportunities for advanced technologies	5	
H2020 Metrodecom	http://empir.npl.co.uk/metrodecom/	website	Blog - In-situ monitoring of radiocarbon emissions using laser spectroscopy	Current methods used for the detection of long-lived radioisotopes are mainly laboratory-based techniques, which cannot provide on-site monitoring capabilities. Optical techniques, such as laser spectroscopy, on the other hand, have inherent on-site monitoring capabilities, as it can provide compact, transportable, and reliable instrumentation, while still achieving very high sensitivity. Cavity ring-down spectroscopy is one of the most sensitive laser spectroscopic technique (...) The technique is routinely used in environmental and emission monitoring but has never been applied to the characterisation of nuclear waste outgassing. The development of the technique for the detection of radioisotopes of interest will provide a sensitive and compact way of monitoring the waste outgassing in	The need of on-site detection of long-lived radioisotopes and the new technique proposed and studied by MetroDecom based on cavity ring-down spectroscopy	Technological	M	This source is important to define needs and opportunities for advanced technologies	5	

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				waste repositories and during the decommissioning process.						
H2020 MetroDECO M II	Final Publishable Report for 16ENV09 MetroDECOM II In-situ metrology for decommissioning nuclear facilities	Final Report	1 Overview	Uptake and application of the novel methods and prototype instrumentation developed within the project will allow the user community to facilitate and accelerate the process of on-site radiological characterisation, ultimately leading to safer, cost efficient and environmentally friendly decommissioning of nuclear facilities.	Need for novel methods and instrumentation for RW characterisation	Technological, Economic, Environmental	M	Identified as a need	5	
H2020 MetroDECO M II	Final Publishable Report for 16ENV09 MetroDECOM II In-situ metrology for decommissioning nuclear facilities	Final Report	2 Need	The present project built on these bases and focussed on bringing the techniques into use on nuclear sites and developing of robust and efficient procedures and instrumentation for radiological characterisation of decommissioning wastes and materials.	Need for robust and efficient procedures and instrumentation for RW characterisation	Technological, Economic, Environmental	M	Identified as a need	5	
H2020 MetroDECO M II	Final Publishable Report for 16ENV09 MetroDECOM II In-situ metrology for decommissioning nuclear facilities	Final Report	3 Need	Regulatory bodies and international organisations have therefore carried out detailed studies of technical needs in the field. The common themes that have been raised were: (1) improvements in capability, (2) harmonisation and quality assurance, and (3) sharing knowledge. The improvements in capability that were required included rapid, on site measurements improving the accuracy and traceability of measurements of waste packages.	Need for: (1) improvements in capability, (2) harmonisation and quality assurance, and (3) sharing knowledge in the area of RW characterisation	Technological, Regulatory, Economic, Societal, Legal, Harmonisation	M	Identified as a need	3, 5, 6	
H2020 MetroDECO M II	Final Publishable Report for 16ENV09 MetroDECOM II In-situ metrology for decommissioning nuclear facilities	Final Report	3 Need	These needs were reflected in EU Council Directive 2011/70/EURATOM which focuses on encouraging technical co-operation to improve safe management of radioactive waste and highlights the importance of building public trust and confidence.	Need for encouraging of technical co-operation and public involvement	Regulatory, Societal, Legal, Harmonisation	M	Identified as a need	3, 6	
H2020 MetroDECO M II	Final Publishable Report for 16ENV09 MetroDECOM II In-situ metrology for decommissioning nuclear facilities	Final Report	5. Impact	Impact on industrial and other user communities The main impact of this project on the nuclear decommissioning community was through the delivery of methods, instrumentation and procedures developed to ensure that radioactive waste is accurately characterised and safely managed.	Observation of the impact on industrial and other user communities	Technological, Economic, Societal	L	Related to observation rather than need or recommendation	5	
H2020 MetroDECO M II	Final Publishable Report for 16ENV09 MetroDECOM II In-situ metrology for decommissioning nuclear facilities	Final Report	5. Impact	Impact on the metrology and scientific communities To address the measurement challenges in decommissioning (different radionuclides, different materials & activity levels), the project activities resulted in the development of novel advanced methods for radioactivity measurements, contributing to the establishment of harmonised, international measurement infrastructure to support nuclear decommissioning.	Observation of the impact on metrology and scientific communities	Technological, Regulatory, Harmonisation	L	Related to observation rather than need or recommendation	5, 6	
H2020 MetroDECO M II	Final Publishable Report for 16ENV09 MetroDECOM II	Final Report	5. Impact	Impact on relevant standards The project will have impact on standards being developed by the International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO). ISO standards are of essential importance for laboratories and measurement scientists	Observation of the impact on relevant standards	Technological, Regulatory, Legal, Harmonisation	L	Related to observation rather than need or recommendation	3, 6	

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	In-situ metrology for decommissioning nuclear facilities			throughout the nuclear industry and have been adopted in many countries as national standards.						
H2020 MetroDECO M II	Final Publishable Report for 16ENV09 MetroDECOM II In-situ metrology for decommissioning nuclear facilities	Final Report	5. Impact	Longer-term economic, social and environmental impacts The main long-term impact on the nuclear industry would be a reduction in the cost of disposal of waste.	Observation of the main long-term impact	Economic	L	Related to observation rather than need or recommendation	5	
H2020 MICADO										
H2020 MICADO	No official document yet Presentations held in 2021 for ERDO and PREDIS seminars				Missing waste characterization technology able to detect and quantify toxic chemicals in the waste drum and the presence of liquids.	Technological	H	It could strongly enhance legacy waste management	5	
H2020 MICADO	No official document yet Presentations held in 2021 for ERDO and PREDIS seminars				Missing waste characterization technology able to perform radiological characterization of non-uniform metallic / high-density matrixes, large containers & not cylindrical volumes.	Technological	M	It could significantly enhance legacy waste management	5	
H2020 MIND										
H2020 MIND	Final integration and evaluation report (31/05/2019) (D3.7)	Final Report	2	No specific recommendation in the report.	Harmonizing of molecular techniques and tools to analyse microbial communities in the context of radioactive disposal	Technological	M/L	May be relevant to advanced technologies	5	Document is focused on R&D/technical needs rather than harmonisation of practices, standards. Within MIND, work was conducted to evaluate different strategies for molecular techniques and tools but did not appear to develop standardised approaches.

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H2020 MIND	Final integration and evaluation report (31/05/2019) (D3.7)	Final Report	6	MIND has reached far beyond the EU borders, and attracted interest and enabled interactions with non-EU member states on these topics (e.g. Canada, Japan). The clear synergies with the other non-EU programs should be explored further with benefit for both parties involved. In the future, such knowledge management and international cooperation will be even more important. Guidelines and other recommendations issued by the international agencies, on how to deal for example with the microbiological issues in geological waste disposal, will not only be important for programmes being developed but would also serve as a fundamental memory to far advanced programmes, when the experts being authoring such guides now have retired or soon will retire	Guidelines and other recommendations issued by international agencies on how to deal with the microbiological issues in geological waste disposal	Regulatory Environmental	M	Possible relevance to harmonisation of regulations and guidelines, but not specifically a recommendation	6	
H2020 MIND	Implementers' Review Board Evaluation Report (21/05/2019) (D4.6)	Final Report	All	No specific recommendations or needs relating to harmonisation of regulations, practices and standards across Europe or sharing of facilities across Member States. Recommendations in the report are R&D related.	N/A	N/A	N/A	No specific recommendations relevant to WP3-6	N/A	Section 4 highlights joint in-situ activities such as long term in situ experiments. The report also highlights the role of underground rock laboratories.
H2020 PLEIADES										
H2020 PLEIADES	D1.1 Requirements for concept design	Roadmap	Introduction	Reduce costs by enabling better and more <u>standardized</u> costing, ...	Consider aspects related to costing, in addition to safety, when exploring harmonisation of practices regulation and standards. ISDC is not yet commonly used. Implementation of ISDC on a practical level at various facility/site types is still challenging.	<i>Economic /standardization</i>	H/M	After safety, cost is the main driver in decom & WM.	6	
H2020 PLEIADES	D1.1 Requirements for concept design	Roadmap	Gap analysis results & Outcomes of DigiDecom 2021 group discussions	Due to the lack of <u>standardization</u> in the nuclear industry for the use of 3D modeling and simulation based techniques users are typically constrained by the offerings of a specific technology provider. The majority of the used software is not specifically designed for the nuclear field. Here we can conclude that PLEIADES should be a platform that allows interoperability with standard data and programs that are already used in the market at a <u>standard</u> way. Harmonization of standards	Consider information tech. aspects (including those based on 3D/BIM technology) related to decom and WM project management when exploring harmonization of practices regulation and standards.	<i>Technological, regulatory, and harmonisation</i>	H	Digital transformation is regarded one of the most important opportunities for improving safety and reducing costs. Dependence on specific providers of information tech. platforms is a major impediment for harmonization of practices regulation and standards.	5, 6	

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H2020 PLEIADES	D1.1 Requirements for concept design	Roadmap	Conclusions	Needs: Safety and risk management: current safety demonstration practice Needs: Safety and risk management: Support for safety inspections	Safety demonstration and inspections would greatly benefit from cross boarder harmonisation of practices regulation and standards.	<i>Regulatory, societal, legal, environmental, and harmonisation</i>	H	Management of safety and risks is main priority in decom and WM.	6	
H2020 PLEIADES	D1.4 Nuclear decom specific ontology	Roadmap	Introduction	The establishment of a common ontology is one of the key points of international standardisation efforts. Without an agreement on the main concepts, it is not possible to exchange data ...	Use the PLAIEDES ontology as a key asset for supporting harmonisation of practices regulation and standards.	<i>Technological, regulatory, economic, societal, legal, environmental, and harmonisation</i>	H	Standardized representation of knowledge is a key first step for harmonisation across borders and varying national frameworks and technology platforms	5, 6	
H2020 PLEIADES	D1.4 Nuclear decom specific ontology	Roadmap	Introduction	In a highly regulated environment like the nuclear power industry, these (Requirements) consist mainly of direct regulations, but also of industry standards and waste management requirements ... Figure 8: Subclasses of Requirements	PLAIEDES and provide a structured map of drivers (requirements) to consider for harmonisation of practices regulation and standards.	<i>Technological, regulatory, economic, societal, legal, environmental, and harmonisation</i>	H	Considering the most important drivers structured in a standardised way will increase impact of HARPERS	5, 6	
H2020 SHARE										
H2020 SHARE	SHARE D4.2: Roadmap	Roadmap final deliverable	1.1 Safety & Radiological Protection	Management of occupational exposures occurring during the decommissioning of a nuclear facility could benefit from an increase in development and use of digital tools: real time dose rate measurements, 3D mapping, job briefing on risks and safety etc.	Exchange and dissemination of operational experience dedicated to end-users (radionuclides and other pollutants)	Economic Societal and environmental	L	Knowledge Management and Knowledge sharing		
H2020 SHARE	SHARE D4.2: Roadmap	Roadmap final deliverable	1.1 Safety & Radiological Protection	Guidance for dealing efficiently with mixed pollutants in waste, structures, building or soils.	Methods for the definition of WAC for mixed waste, based on the actual hazardous properties of the waste, should be made available	Regulatory Economic Harmonisation	H	WAC for mixed waste	3, 6	
H2020 SHARE	SHARE D4.2: Roadmap	Roadmap final deliverable	1.1 Safety & Radiological Protection	International basic safety standards provide a framework for clearance of solid radioactive materials, based on the 10 µSv.y-1 concept. Still, some radionuclides are not considered in these frameworks and values for liquid materials are not available	Framework for clearance of all types of radioactive materials should be completed in the years to come	Regulatory Economic Harmonisation Societal (ethics)	H	Regulatory framework evolution	3, 4, 6	
H2020 SHARE	SHARE D4.2: Roadmap	Roadmap final deliverable	1.2 Resources Management	Development of standardised education levels (e.g. certificates) and the exchanges by internships between different actors. These more general topics are supported by providing training for task specific skills and new training methods	Workforce competences development	Societal	L	Education & Training	6	To some extent covered by European Nuclear Education Network
H2020 SHARE	SHARE D4.2: Roadmap	Roadmap final deliverable	1.2 Resources Management	Development of cost estimation methodologies in coordination with the international organisations. Address the specificity of different facility types and the	Further cost estimation methodologies considering risk and uncertainty.	Harmonisation	M/L	Further cost estimations	3	To some extent covered by the IAEA and NEA

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				whole value chain of decommissioning including radioactive waste management, risks, and engineering.	Harmonised cost assessment indicators Public and transparent cost estimations					
H2020 SHARE	SHARE D4.2: Roadmap	Roadmap final deliverable	1.2 Resources Management	Public communication Common approach for addressing the general public	Integration of various stakeholder views, concerns and knowledge	Societal	M/L	Social issues	3, 4, 5, 6	
H2020 SHARE	SHARE D4.2: Roadmap	Roadmap final deliverable	1.3 Characterisation	Active demonstration of new technology to increase the technology readiness and demonstrate the maturity of new approaches Remote, integrated and automatic technologies for in situ waste characterisation and segregation	Increase the technology readiness and demonstrate the maturity of new technologies Development of reliable and affordable non-destructive characterisation methods that enables quality check against Waste Acceptance Criteria	Technological Economic Environmental	H	TRLs Standardisation	3,5	
H2020 SHARE	SHARE D4.2: Roadmap	Roadmap final deliverable	1.3 Characterisation	Sharing knowledge, good practices and technical information through their international networks and working groups, best practices and guidelines in different phase of a decommissioning programme with special focus in digitalisation, modelling and simulation	Sharing best practices and guidelines in different phase of a decommissioning programme with special focus in digitalisation, modelling and simulation	Technological Harmonisation Environmental	L/M	Best Practices digitalisation, modelling and simulation. Knowledge management	5	Partially cover by IAEA and NEA
H2020 SHARE	SHARE D4.2: Roadmap	Roadmap final deliverable	1.3 Characterisation	The enhance use of robotics including drones and sensors is highlighted from both standardisation and regulatory implications points of view	Robotics, standardisation	Technological Harmonisation Economic	H	Robotics	5	
H2020 SHARE	SHARE D4.2: Roadmap	Roadmap final deliverable	1.3 Characterisation	Regulatory differences regarding clearance criteria	Regulatory discrepancies prevent stakeholders from benchmarking the efficiency of decommissioning and waste management strategies between countries, making it difficult for them to identify the best available techniques	Harmonisation	H	Clearance criteria	3, 4, 6	
H2020 SHARE	SHARE D4.2: Roadmap	Roadmap final deliverable	1.4 Material & Waste Management	Development and benchmarking of technologies for recycle and reuse of materials (such as metals). Developments in this area would need to address both the technological (process) issues, the regulatory requirements for release and potentially societal engagement to enable recycling	Development and benchmarking of technologies for recycle and reuse of materials Regulatory and social aspects	Technology Economic Environmental Harmonisation Regulatory Social	H	Reuse and recycle in the nuclear sector Waste minimisation	4, 5, 6	

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H2020 SHARE	SHARE D4.2: Roadmap	Roadmap final deliverable	1.4 Material & Waste Management	The need to develop and demonstrate new innovative waste treatment technologies and decontamination processes to enable the circular economy	Waste optimisation and minimisation	Technological Economic	H	Reuse and recycle in the nuclear sector Waste minimisation	4,5	
H2020 SHARE	SHARE D4.2: Roadmap	Roadmap final deliverable	1.4 Material & Waste Management	Societal issues around the reusing and recycling of materials	Public acceptancy	Societal	L	Social issues	4	
H2020 SHARE	SHARE D4.2: Roadmap	Roadmap final deliverable	1.4 Material & Waste Management	Standardisation of clearance levels for recycle and Waste Acceptance Criteria (WAC) /waste routes for problematic wastes	Harmonisation of Frameworks for clearance	Regulatory	H	Regulatory framework Harmonisation	3, 4, 6	
H2020 SHARE	SHARE D4.2: Roadmap	Roadmap final deliverable	1.5 Dismantling & Decontamination	The key use of robotics and remote systems in dismantling applications is highlighted as a high urgent priority mainly to reduce the radioactive dose levels to which workers are exposed	Robotics and remote systems in dismantling applications is	Technological	H/M	Robotics and remote systems	5	Some projects are already on-going
H2020 SHARE	SHARE D4.2: Roadmap	Roadmap final deliverable	1.5 Dismantling & Decontamination	Modular and mobile system and the enhance in the use and in the interoperability of digital technologies to assist the workers' training and the modelling and simulation of dismantling alternative scenarios	Modular and mobile system. Interoperability Digital technologies	Technological	H/M	Digital technologies	5	Some projects are already on-going
				Access database that provides information on evaluated robotics for different tasks in decommissioning and the harmonisation of practices and demonstration approaches can further enhance the use of such technologies and provide advantages in safety and standardisation.	Robotics	Technological	H/M	Digital technologies- Best practices	5	
H2020 SHARE	SHARE D4.2: Roadmap	Roadmap final deliverable	1.5 Dismantling & Decontamination	Exchange and dissemination of operational experience in the field of dismantling and decontamination are needed to bring significant advantages for the selection and optimisation of a segmentation strategy and further enhance the efficiency and effectiveness	Best Practices	Technological	M	Best Practices Operational experience in the field of dismantling and decontamination	5	Partially covered by IAEA and NEA
H2020 SHARE	SHARE D4.2: Roadmap	Roadmap final deliverable	1.6 Environmental Remediation & Site Release	the need for improvements in the accuracy of predictive modelling to assess the migration of contaminants (in the soil and groundwater systems) and the need for dissemination and exchange of experience to improve the model building and long-time follow-up	Modelling migration of contaminants	Technological	L	Mainly dissemination and best practices	5	
H2020 SHARE	SHARE D4.2: Roadmap	Roadmap final deliverable	1.6 Environmental Remediation & Site Release	Development of guidance on the definition of final end-state or the future of the site.	Best practices	Technological Environmental Economic Societal	L	Best practices final end-state and future of the site	3, 6	Partially covered by IAEA
H2020 SHARE	SHARE D4.2: Roadmap	Roadmap final deliverable	1.6 Environmental Remediation & Site Release	Multi-criteria decision-making approaches are used to choose the best alternative among a set of many solutions for the assessment of cost, end state and environmental protection	Multi-criteria decision-making approaches	Technological Environmental Economic	L	Multi-criteria decision-making approaches for end-state.	3, 4, 5, 6	
H2020 THERAMIN										
H2020 THERAMIN	THERAMIN Project Synthesis Report D5.4	Deliverable	6.1	[Whilst] a few European countries may have the resources to thermally treat their own wastes, many other countries could benefit from cross-country collaboration and treatment of wastes outside their borders.	Many countries would benefit from international collaboration on thermal treatment as few have the resources or facilities for	Technological, regulatory, economic	H	Directly relevant to HARPERS work scope. Sharing resources avoids the duplication of effort to develop treatment facilities and is thus more	3, 6	

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					all required/desired treatment processes.			efficient as well as allowing the best treatment to be used for a waste stream rather than what is locally available. Common standards and regulations are desirable for the most effective sharing of resources and could help to promote wider adoption of thermal treatment.		
H2020 THERAMIN	THERAMIN Project Synthesis Report D5.4	Deliverable	6.2	Maintenance and development of the community of thermal treatment specialists.	Maintain and develop the community of thermal treatment specialists to support the continued deployment of this waste treatment method.	Technological, societal	L	Harmonisation of regulations and practices would ease international knowledge transfer and allow development of shared expertise. However, collaborative research, which is a more important enabler for addressing this need, falls outside the scope of HARPERS. Broadening expertise and awareness of the developments in a technical field raises the prospects for integrating these developments into waste management activities. Other EC programmes / projects (e.g., EURAD and PREDIS) are providing collaborative training as part of their knowledge management activities with this in mind; HARPERS WP7 activities have similar objectives.	3,6	
H2020 THERAMIN	THERAMIN Project Synthesis Report D5.4	Deliverable	6.2	Development of WAC for thermally treated products.	Development of waste acceptance criteria (WAC) for thermally treated products.	Technological, regulatory	M	Generic disposability criteria applicable to thermally treated wastes have already been developed, for application where desired. Some further work is required to achieve wider,	6	

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								multinational use of generic WAC. Commonly accepted generic WAC would promote harmonisation of regulations related to the treatment and disposability of wastes. This is a key driver underpinning ongoing PREDIS activities to develop guidance on formulating generic WAC.		
H2020 THERAMIN	THERAMIN Project Synthesis Report D5.4	Deliverable	6.2	Understanding of the long-term behaviour and chemical durability of thermally treated products Gathering of further information to support comparison of thermal treatment technologies against the baseline. Optimisation of thermally treated product composition to increase waste loadings and/or improve wasteform performance.	Further collaborative research is required into thermal treatment, including: comparison with other techniques, optimisation of treatment method, and characterisation of LLW/ILW wasteforms produced from a disposability perspective.	Technological	L	Further research would benefit from continuation of international collaborations, and a deeper common understanding of waste management issues would make harmonisation of waste treatment and regulations easier. However, collaborative research itself is beyond the scope of HARPERS.	5	There are several recommendations for further research into thermal treatment within the THERAMIN Project Synthesis Report; these have been combined into a single recommendation.
H2020 THERAMIN	THERAMIN Project Synthesis Report D5.4	Deliverable	6.2	Consideration of transport, container availability, requirements of the IAEA Transport Regulations and inter-Governmental agreements to enable waste transfers for treatment to be arranged.	Review of the legal and regulatory barriers to the international transport and transfer of waste for (thermal) treatment and identification of potential approaches to address these.	Legal, regulatory, technological	H	Directly relevant to HARPERS work scope. Difficulties in arranging international transport and obtaining the permission to do so are a barrier to shared waste processing. For shared waste management solutions to be effected, there needs to be confidence in the maturity and availability of waste treatment routes, to encourage waste owners / operators to consider them.	3, 6	

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H2020 THERAMIN	THERAMIN Project Synthesis Report D5.4	Deliverable	6.2	Potential licensing of technologies would need to be considered.	A route for effective & trusted international sharing of facilities and technology must be established.	Legal, regulatory	M	Shared waste processing, storage and disposal opportunities may require sharing of intellectual property. Licensing is a routine way to organise this.	3, 6	
H2020 THERAMIN	THERAMIN Project Synthesis Report D5.4	Deliverable	3.1	Technology owners matched waste streams from this list with existing rigs and facilities on which demonstration trials could be carried out.	Consideration of how to align wastes with treatment technologies in a manner acceptable to all stakeholders (noting that stakeholders may have differing views on the suitability of treatment options for certain wastes).	Technological, economic	M	A common understanding of the suitability of treatment options for different waste types is required to establish new shared waste processing opportunities.	3, 5	Issue not explicitly mentioned in report but known to have been an issue in the project.
IAEA CIDER										
IAEA CIDER	Advancing Implementation of Decommissioning and Environmental Remediation Programmes. CIDER Project: Baseline Report IAEA Nuclear Energy Series No. NW-T-1.10	Report	<i>1.1 Background</i>	<i>It is estimated that there are over 30 000 facilities worldwide that use radioactive material that will require eventual decommissioning.</i>	<i>Eventually 30 000 facilities worldwide will require decommissioning</i>	<i>All of them</i>	<i>H</i>	<i>Fundamental consideration for the project context</i>	3, 4, 5, 6	<i>This reference is not strictly relevant to the gap analysis but provides further motivation for the HARPERS project.</i>
IAEA CIDER	Advancing Implementation of Decommissioning and Environmental Remediation Programmes. CIDER Project: Baseline Report IAEA Nuclear Energy Series No. NW-T-1.10	Report	3.1.1. Absent, incomplete or ineffective national policy	The absence of a national policy may result in the regulatory authority not having a clear mandate, and consequential delays in D&ER may occur. This may also result in a lack of motivation among facility owners to initiate D&ER. If the policy is not sufficient or complete, there may be a tendency for operators to begin D&ER projects, but without having established a clear end point, leading to possible inefficient use of resources and with an increased potential that such projects are ultimately unsuccessful.	A lack of, or incomplete or ineffective, national policy may lead to unsuccessful D&ER projects.	Regulatory, Harmonization	H	By definition, harmonisation of regulations and standards will prevent the lack or the ineffectiveness of national regulations.	6	Solutions to overcome these constraints are summarized in TABLE 1. CONSTRAINTS AND SOLUTIONS RELATED TO NATIONAL POLICY AND LEGAL AND REGULATORY FRAMEWORK FOR D&ER.
IAEA CIDER	Advancing Implementation of Decommissioning and Environmental Remediation	Report	3.2.1. Lack of an adequate legal and regulatory framework	The CIDER survey results indicated that, in certain cases, legal and regulatory frameworks for D&ER are completely or partially absent (e.g. with no relevant regulations and without a regulatory authority	Lack of an adequate legal and regulatory framework may lead to unsuccessful D&ER projects.	Regulatory, Harmonization	H	By definition, harmonisation of regulations and standards will prevent the lack or the ineffectiveness	6	Suggestion to overcome the constraint is provided. It is suggested that

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	Programmes. CIDER Project: Baseline Report IAEA Nuclear Energy Series No. NW-T-1.10			responsible for D&ER). A potential for conflict between different regulatory bodies may also exist. The institution responsible for performing or regulating D&ER may also not be clearly defined. Each of these constraints may delay and challenge the implementation of a D&ER project.				of legal and regulatory framework.		primary legislation should be based on the following international standards: IAEA Safety Standards Series Nos GSR Part 1 (Rev. 1), Governmental, Legal and Regulatory Framework for Safety, and GSR Part 3, Radiation Protection and Safety of Radiation Sources: International Basic Safety Standards. Solutions to overcome these constrains are summarized in TABLE 1. CONSTRAINTS AND SOLUTIONS RELATED TO NATIONAL POLICY AND LEGAL AND REGULATORY FRAMEWORK FOR D&ER.
IAEA CIDER	Advancing Implementation of Decommissioning and Environmental Remediation Programmes. CIDER Project: Baseline Report IAEA Nuclear	Report	3.2.3. Lack of or incomplete D&ER regulations	National regulations and associated guidance for D&ER are intended to ensure the safety of the workforce, the public and the environment during and after the implementation of D&ER projects. Their content should be in accordance with the national legal system, together with international standards, and should reflect prove practice. [...] Where regulations, standards and guidelines are incomplete or missing D&ER projects may begin but subsequently fail owing to poor	D&ER regulations which are incomplete or non-compliant with the international standards may lead to D&ER project to fail or being subject to disputes between the regulator and the	Regulatory, Harmonization	H	By definition, harmonisation of regulations and standards will prevent the lack or the ineffectiveness of legal and regulatory framework.	4, 5, 6	Solutions to overcome these constrains are summarized in TABLE 1. CONSTRAINTS AND SOLUTIONS RELATED TO

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	Energy Series No. NW-T-1.10			coordination. Such projects may be poorly planned and managed, faced with an inconsistent regulatory approach or be subject to disputes between the regulator and the implementing organization.	implementing organization.					NATIONAL POLICY AND LEGAL AND REGULATORY FRAMEWORK FOR D&ER.
IAEA CIDER	Advancing Implementation of Decommissioning and Environmental Remediation Programmes. CIDER Project: Baseline Report IAEA Nuclear Energy Series No. NW-T-1.10	Report	4.1. LACK OF ACCESSIBILITY TO APPROPRIATE TECHNOLOGY	An important challenge to be faced is the transfer of technologies from States with more advanced programmes to those which are less advanced and the associated need to have access to qualified personnel to support their use and to provide regulatory oversight. Although it is clear from existing worldwide experience that D&ER projects can be implemented using currently available technologies, it is also evident that the development of new technologies could improve the performance of D&ER projects by implementing them more efficiently, being safer to the public and the environment and involving less cost.	Accessibility to the appropriate technology, new or existent, for specific D&ER activities can be a major constraint for many Member States.	Technological	H	The observation involves both potential development of new technologies (relevant to WP5) and transfer of technologies between different countries (relevant to WP3)	3, 5	
IAEA CIDER	Advancing Implementation of Decommissioning and Environmental Remediation Programmes. CIDER Project: Baseline Report IAEA Nuclear Energy Series No. NW-T-1.10	Report	4.2. LACK OF ENABLING INFRASTRUCTURE FOR TECHNOLOGY IMPLEMENTATION	Wherever possible, available infrastructure should be identified prior to selecting specific technologies and methodologies for the implementation of the D&ER projects. In cases where the necessary infrastructure is absent, use of mobile systems may be an alternative.	Where infrastructure and technologies are missing, use of mobile systems may be an alternative.	Technological	H	A mobile system may be included in cross-border services or, in general, be a system suitable for being shared between different countries.	3	
IAEA CIDER	Advancing Implementation of Decommissioning and Environmental Remediation Programmes. CIDER Project: Baseline Report IAEA Nuclear Energy Series No. NW-T-1.10	Report	5.1.2. Potential complementary funding sources	Involvement of international funding institutions may facilitate access to international expertise and international best practice. Their involvement can also lead to enhanced credibility in terms of increased openness and participation by local communities in D&ER activities.		Economic, Societal, Legal	H	This observation represents either an opportunity for tackle a D&ER project and driver for a better harmonization of the regulatory framework in different countries.	3, 4, 6	
IAEA CIDER	Advancing Implementation of Decommissioning and Environmental Remediation Programmes. CIDER Project: Baseline Report IAEA Nuclear Energy Series No. NW-T-1.10	Report	5.4. LACK OF ENABLING PROGRAMMATIC INFRASTRUCTURE	In situations where Member States' efforts to implement D&ER programmes face challenges, including limited financial resources, it is vital that the development of high-quality plans consider numerous factors and good project management practices.		Legal, Economic, Harmonization	M	This observation refers to "project management practices" which should reasonably be harmonized and compliant with the international best practices.	6	

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IAEA CIDER	Advancing Implementation of Decommissioning and Environmental Remediation Programmes. CIDER Project: Baseline Report IAEA Nuclear Energy Series No. NW-T-1.10	Report	6.1. LIMITED TECHNICAL KNOWLEDGE AND UNDERSTANDING OF THE ISSUES AND PROCESS	In general, the public has limited knowledge of nuclear and radiological concepts and, in addition, the highly technical nature of nuclear activities, and the history of secrecy often surrounding them in the past, may make stakeholders distrustful or even fearful. Where the overall life cycle of D&ER programmes is not understood, the licensing process may seem cumbersome, bureaucratic processes associated with these activities are often very complex and the opportunities for public involvement may not be evident at the outset. All these issues together can lead to a negative attitude among interested parties towards project implementation.	Limited knowledge of nuclear concepts can lead to a negative attitude among interested parties and the public towards D&ER projects implementation. It is important to improve public knowledge by providing relevant and timely information in an understandable way.	Societal	M	This is a general constraint which applies to several fields, including decommissioning of nuclear facilities.	6	
IAEA CIDER	Advancing Implementation of Decommissioning and Environmental Remediation Programmes. CIDER Project: Baseline Report IAEA Nuclear Energy Series No. NW-T-1.10	Report	6.7. LACK OF SUPPORT FROM NATIONAL AUTHORITIES	Governmental authorities may give low priority to the implementation of D&ER programmes in comparison to other issues (e.g. covering basic needs of the nuclear industry in maintenance and repairing services and tools for nuclear power plants in operation, spent fuel and radioactive waste management, basic needs of the people such as social payments, and food and medicine supplies). This is especially the case when the budget is limited and there has to be more focus on short term temporary solutions instead of long term sustainable ones. Furthermore, D&ER programmes may not be recognized as being directly linked to priority areas (e.g. improving the quality of life).	Governmental authorities may give low priority to the implementation of D&ER programmes in comparison to other issues which are directly recognized as related to areas that improves the quality of life by the public.	Societal, Economic	H	This is a barrier for implementing D&ER programmes. Harmonization of regulations and practices may minimize the issue.	6	
IAEA CIDER	Advancing Implementation of Decommissioning and Environmental Remediation Programmes. CIDER Project: Baseline Report IAEA Nuclear Energy Series No. NW-T-1.10	Report	6.8. CHANGING THE ADMINISTRATIVE PROCEDURE AND LEGAL FRAMEWORK RELATED TO D&ER PROGRAMMES	D&ER projects may continue over several years or even decades. Consequently, legal, regulatory and financial frameworks (and also people employed by the organizations responsible for these aspects) may change during project implementation. This will lead to changes in the D&ER implementation plan that can cause an increase in needed funds, cause the schedule to slip and make it more difficult to retain qualified personnel.		Regulatory, Economic	M	This is a barrier for implementing D&ER programmes. Harmonization of regulations and practices may minimize the issue.	6	
IAEA IDN										
IAEA IDN	Training and Human Resource Considerations for Nuclear Facility Decommissioning (2022)	Final Report	5.3 & 5.4	Knowledge management A systematic approach is required for identifying areas where there is a risk of loss of information of importance to decommissioning, and to implement mitigating actions, including:... Management of information in various databases and systems, and from knowledge-based plant information systems; [Footnote: For example, digital twins of plants or parts of it, the use of VR, AR and other technical assistance systems can be used not only for engineering,	Need for knowledge-based plant information systems to support decommissioning (engineering and training of personnel), such as digital twins, virtual reality, augmented reality	Technological Economic	M	Linked to advanced technologies but not necessarily related to harmonisation of practices	5	

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				<p>but also for training and education. Combinations with semantic systems may be necessary to allow integration of information from these different sources into the knowledge management system.]</p> <p>Knowledge and information management systems can be used to help facilitate the timely availability and accessibility of appropriate knowledge and information in the right form. Knowledge centred plant information systems have also been developed to facilitate this and were the focus of an international conference in 2016 [29]. Aspects of virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR) and 3-D modelling have been demonstrated in a number of international meetings [30] and training activities [31]. However, personnel may need training in the appropriate use of knowledge and information management systems .</p>						
IAEA IDN	Training and Human Resource Considerations for Nuclear Facility Decommissioning (2022)	Final Report	7.3 & 7.4	<p>Digitalized training and facilities. There is a specific need for personnel to learn about safety requirements relevant to decommissioning, and to keep up to date with them. There is also a requirement for personnel, including contractors, to maintain training records as evidence that necessary levels of competence have been attained.</p> <p>Increasingly, such safety training is undertaken using digital tools, e.g. using training packages uploaded on computers and/or made accessible on-line on the web. As interactive technology develops, and with the increasing use of multimedia and VR, the term technology based training (TBT) is now being used.</p> <p>There are many organizations providing such services, including educational entities. In some Member States, there are specialized training facilities allowing VR and AR training for decommissioning.</p> <p>The development of training facilities and collaborating centres has become increasingly important due to the scope, extent and duration of training requirements for decommissioning. Typically, the facilities have included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Classroom facilities and equipment for lectures and training; — 3-D models and digital platforms enabling VR; — Realistic mock-ups to train people and test equipment. <p>Although training facilities and collaborating centres require significant investment, they represent good value for money, since they can be used before and during decommissioning activities throughout the decommissioning programme. Moreover, they enable organizations to mitigate specific risks through the testing and updating of scenarios and equipment.</p>	Need for digitalized training and collaborating centres using digital tools, 3-D models and physical mock-ups to support decommissioning programmes	Technological Economic Environmental/ Safety	M	Linked to advanced technologies but not necessarily related to harmonisation of practices	5	

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IAEA IDN	Decommissioning at Multifacility Site: An Integrated Approach	Final Report	4, 5.3	No specific recommendations or needs relating to harmonisation of regulations, practices and standards across Europe or sharing of facilities across Member States. However, highlights issues such as: Planning and regulation of multifacility sites with some facilities that are operational and some being decommissioned Selection of appropriate decommissioning and demolition techniques for facilities and contaminated land	N/A	N/A	L	No specific recommendations relevant to WP3-6	3, 4, 5, 6	
IAEA IDN	Managing the Decommissioning and Remediation of Damaged Nuclear Facilities Final Report of the Collaborative Project DAROD	Final Report	3.3. APPLICABILITY AND MODIFICATION OF NUCLEAR AND NON-NUCLEAR REGULATIONS AND STANDARDS	In most cases, legislation is generally in place for nuclear facilities that are operating normally (including being in a safe shutdown state), but specific regulations and a revised regulatory approach may be required to address the unique requirements of a DNF. The ease with which the required changes can be achieved may depend upon the nature of the regulatory system that is in place. For example, a regulatory system that is highly prescriptive may find it more difficult to make the changes in comparison to a regulatory system based on goal setting principles.	General recommendation for change in regulations and regulatory approach in case of Damaged Nuclear Facilities	regulatory	L	It is applicable only for DNF	6	
IAEA IDN	Managing the Decommissioning and Remediation of Damaged Nuclear Facilities Final Report of the Collaborative Project DAROD	Final Report	3.4. SAFEGUARDS AND NUCLEAR MATERIALS CONTROL PRACTICES	Realistic and practical requirements for the accountancy of nuclear material after an accident are needed, and these requirements will need to be agreed to with the safeguards authority.	General recommendation safeguards and nuclear materials control practices in case of Damaged Nuclear Facilities	regulatory	L	It is applicable in case of DNF	6	Maybe a standardised approach could be useful?
IAEA IDN	Managing the Decommissioning and Remediation of Damaged Nuclear Facilities Final Report of the Collaborative Project DAROD	Final Report	3.5. APPLICABILITY OF THE CLEARANCE CONCEPT FOR MATERIALS	The clearance concept as applied to DNFs raises a number of issues, not the least of which is that different jurisdictions have different policies in terms of clearance levels. For DNFs, an added complication can arise as a result of political and public opinion regarding waste materials, a complication that may prevent the use of approved standard clearance levels that are already in place. This complication arose in the cases of both Chernobyl and Fukushima Daiichi.	Clearance levels are different in different Countries. Even if they are available, additional issues can arise in case of a DNF as result of political and public opinion regarding waste materials	regulatory, societal, environmental, harmonisation	H	Linked with HARPERS WP4	4	How clearance approaches/recycling/reuse can fit with a DNF?
IAEA IDN	Managing the Decommissioning and Remediation of Damaged Nuclear Facilities Final Report of the Collaborative Project DAROD	Final Report	4.2. PHYSICAL, RADIOLOGICAL AND HAZARDS CHARACTERIZATION 4.2.2. Summary of key points	Experience gained from major accidents indicates that available characterization technologies may not be capable of undertaking the required analyses because the levels of radioactivity are significantly higher than those encountered during normal situations. Therefore, the deployment and/or development of advanced or non-standard characterization techniques may	Need for development of advanced or non-standard characterization techniques in case of DNF	Technological	M	It fits in the scope of HARPERS WP5 but is related to a specific need for DNF	5	

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				need to be considered.						
IAEA IDN	Managing the Decommissioning and Remediation of Damaged Nuclear Facilities Final Report of the Collaborative Project DAROD	Final Report	4.2. PHYSICAL, RADIOLOGICAL AND HAZARDS CHARACTERIZATION 4.2.2. Summary of key points	In the case of assessing the physical damage to a nuclear facility, a wide variety of physical characterization techniques may be required to obtain required and important information about the status of the facility. In some instances, the ability to access critical areas may not be possible or impractical. Under these circumstances, the use of advanced remote handling techniques may need to be employed.	Need of advanced remote handling Techniques for physical and radiological characterization of DNF	Technological	H	It fits in the scope of HARPERS WP5.	5	
IAEA IDN	Managing the Decommissioning and Remediation of Damaged Nuclear Facilities Final Report of the Collaborative Project DAROD	Final Report	4.5. METHODOLOGY USED TO SPECIFY, PROVIDE OR REPLACE SAFETY SYSTEMS 4.5.1. Introduction	Lack of or limited guidance or precedence for defining the safety assessment strategy or methodology that should be used in defining the required safety systems for a DNF. For example, whether a risk based or deterministic approach should be used.	Lack of guidance/experiences for defining the safety assessment strategy/methodology for a DNF	harmonisation	L	It is a very case specific issue	6	Harmonisation of Safety Assessment approaches in case of DNF
IAEA IDN	Managing the Decommissioning and Remediation of Damaged Nuclear Facilities Final Report of the Collaborative Project DAROD	Final Report	4.7. MANAGEMENT AND MONITORING OF ENVIRONMENTAL CONTAMINATION 4.7.1. Introduction	The nature and type of uncertainty that can often be found in the case of DNFs and legacy facilities may necessitate a more comprehensive and detailed understanding of groundwater and groundwater flow patterns compared to a situation where the source term is better understood, e.g., with facilities unaffected by accidents. Advanced characterization techniques to collect the necessary input data may need to be used in conjunction with sophisticated modelling and analysis tools. Such tools could include regularly updated 3-dimensional models of the site with the capability to provide, for example, simulations of groundwater flows;	Need of advanced characterization technologies, 3D models and simulation tools for groundwater flows	<i>Technological</i>	H	It fits in the scope of HARPERS WP5.	5	
IAEA IDN	Managing the Decommissioning and Remediation of Damaged Nuclear Facilities Final Report of the Collaborative Project DAROD	Final Report	4.10. MANAGEMENT OF DAMAGED FUEL AND FUEL DEBRIS 4.10.2. Summary of key points	For the management of fuel and fuel debris, special R&D initiatives may be required that take into consideration the unique features of each facility, as well as any recent developments in remotely controlled devices and simulation tools.	Need for R&D activities for the management of fuel and fuel debris	<i>Technological</i>	M	It fits in the scope of HARPERS WP5 but is related to a specific need for DNF	5	
IAEA IDN	Managing the Decommissioning and Remediation of Damaged Nuclear Facilities Final Report of the Collaborative Project DAROD	Final Report	4.11. REMOTE TECHNOLOGY FOR REMEDIATION AND DECOMMISSIONING 4.11.2. Summary of key points	In considering the subject of remote handling in the case studies, it becomes apparent that the tools needed for the specific conditions found in DNFs are not likely to be an off-the-shelf item, and therefore not be immediately or readily available. In addition, there may be a lack of proven technology for the required applications. Furthermore, the case studies reveal that it is necessary to train the operators of remote handling equipment in the actual facilities where such	Lack of proven technologies for remote handling Need for training of the operators of remote handling equipment	Technological	H	It fits in the scope of HARPERS WP5	5	

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				equipment is to be used in order to achieve the highest possible levels of system performance, reliability, productivity, and safety. On-site training has the added benefit that it can be more easily tailored to address site specific difficulties arising from, for example, access to damaged structures, and it allows time for the implementation of special tooling.						
IAEA IDN	Managing the Decommissioning and Remediation of Damaged Nuclear Facilities Final Report of the Collaborative Project DAROD	Final Report	4.12. DECONTAMINATION TECHNOLOGY 4.12.1. Introduction	The challenges associated with undertaking decontamination work in a post-emergency environment may be similar to those encountered during the decommissioning of facilities that have undergone a normal planned final shutdown, especially in terms of those areas that are highly contaminated and for which there are access issues. In both cases, high levels of radiation and contamination may necessitate decontamination techniques not normally used during an operational phase, and the development of these decontamination techniques may require R&D initiatives.	Need for R&D activities for decontamination techniques for areas with high levels of radiation and contamination	Technological	H	It fits in the scope of HARPERS WP5	5	
IAEA - IDN	Industrial Involvement to Support a National Nuclear Power Programme No. NG-T-3.4	report	1.1 Background	Countries embarking on the use of nuclear power need to plan for the development of appropriate local industrial involvement that is able to support the national nuclear power programme and related projects.	none	Legal, technological	not relevant		3, 6	-
IAEA - IDN	Industrial Involvement to Support a National Nuclear Power Programme No. NG-T-3.4	report	2.4. RADIOACTIVE WASTE MANAGEMENT FACILITIES	Each State has its own nuclear waste management policy, and its national regulations also influence the approach taken. Waste disposal facilities are designed and constructed in a manner that is consistent with their risks.	Lack of harmonisation, since each State can develop its own nuclear regulations or to adopt regulations from other national NRBs and IAEA safety standards	Legal, regulatory, societal	L	The publication applies to the planning and implementation of industrial involvement activities related to the introduction or reestablishment of a national nuclear power programme.	6	
IAEA - IDN	Industrial Involvement to Support a National Nuclear Power Programme No. NG-T-3.4	Report	3.3.4.4. Physical protection and security services	Security of nuclear facilities is an important criterion for site selection and for establishing plant configuration and plant operational procedures, as well as for safeguarding nuclear material. Each State carries full responsibility for nuclear security.	none	legal	N/A	Guidance provided here, describing good practice, represents expert opinion but does not constitute recommendations made on the basis of a consensus of MS.	N/A	
IAEA - IDN	Industrial Involvement to Support a National Nuclear Power Programme No. NG-T-3.4	Report	4.2. AVAILABLE NATIONAL INDUSTRY AND EXTENT OF NATIONAL PARTICIPATION	A Member State can find itself unable to take advantage of all the economic, industrial and technological opportunities a nuclear power plant programme can offer.	none	legal, technological	L		N/A	
IAEA - IDN	Industrial Involvement to Support a National Nuclear Power	report	4.8.3. Radioactive waste handling	The contract that the operating organization has with its fuel suppliers generally does not include the return of used fuel to the supplier (although this may change in the future).	none	legal & regulatory	L		6	

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	Programme No. NG-T-3.4			the operating organization will need, as a condition of its licence, to provide for the temporary storage of used fuel, as well as have plans for either disposal or reprocessing after the fuel has cooled sufficiently						
IAEA IDN	Decommissioning of Particle Accelerators No. NW-T-2.9	IAEA Nuclear Energy Series	5.2. FACTORS INFLUENCING THE DECOMMISSIONING STRATEGY	National policies and legal and regulatory framework: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Compliance with national policies for decommissioning. — Existence of a legal framework that details the regulatory functions and infrastructure, as well as regulatory requirements and the defined standards, to be applied to decommissioning. — Well established and understood national authorization/licensing processes to ensure regulation of the particle accelerators from the initial design stage, throughout the entire operational life cycle, through to a regulatory regime relevant for the planning and conduct of decommissioning. 	Needs of regulatory framework to define decommissioning strategy	Regulatory	H	Needs connected to WP6 scope	6	
IAEA IDN	Decommissioning of Particle Accelerators No. NW-T-2.9	IAEA Nuclear Energy Series	6. REUSE AND REDEVELOPMENT OF REDUNDANT FACILITIES AND SPARE PARTS	Large quantities of metal, concrete and other slightly radioactive items from particle accelerator decommissioning could result in high waste management costs in cases where a regulatory provision for clearance is not in place. <p>...</p> <p>Once a definite decision for reuse of a facility is agreed, it is important to carry out as accurate a characterization as possible to ensure suitability to meet the needs for this reuse, taking note of relevant compliance issues such as regulations and licence requirements for the new use.</p> <p>...</p> <p>There could also be a problem with the type of metallic waste generated after melting because it could fall outside the normal acceptance criteria for cast blocks, such that smelters and steel mills could refuse to accept it and it could be prevented from further dilution with other clean virgin metals. In those States where clearance is not implemented, the reuse of equipment and the facility might be possible only in radiological environments.</p>	Problems related to clearance	Technological and regulatory	H	Linked to clearance level to harmonise for reuse and recycle	4	
IAEA IDN	Decommissioning of Particle Accelerators No. NW-T-2.9	IAEA Nuclear Energy Series	7.1. COST ESTIMATES	Opportunities to sell recycled materials need not be overlooked as a potential income source.	Economic benefits from reuse and recycling	Economic	M	Side effects of main objectives of the Project	4	
IAEA IDN	Decommissioning of Particle Accelerators No. NW-T-2.9	IAEA Nuclear Energy Series	8.1. GENERAL ASPECTS OF RADIOACTIVE WASTE TREATMENT AND MANAGEMENT IN	If further decontamination makes the waste suitable for recycling, this can have a positive impact on the decommissioning project. Lead and copper have a ready resale value from recycling. Even for steel and high grade steel, decontamination is more expensive than recycling the material. It is therefore essential to	Cost–benefit analysis to evaluate the option of reuse and recycle	Economic	M	Side effects of main objectives of the Project	4	

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			DECOMMISSIONING PROJECTS	evaluate a cost-benefit analysis, comparing the costs of further decontamination with the benefits of clearance to recycling. This exercise is best carried out at an early stage of planning for waste and material management.						
IAEA IDN	Status and Trends in Spent Fuel and Radioactive Waste Management No. NW-T-1.14 (Rev. 1)	IAEA Nuclear Energy Series	4.7. PLANNING AND INTEGRATION	Often the unavailability or the limitation of a disposal option and costs are good drivers to promote the minimization of radioactive waste or recycling of radioactive material, but sometimes, such as in France, the economic trade-off between direct disposal of the waste and waste treatment to reduce disposal volumes or to enable recycling can be difficult. For countries that are just embarking on a nuclear power programme or national waste management system, there is an opportunity to build in integration right from the start. The availability of existing infrastructure and resources needs to be considered in the planning. This may include collaboration or sharing of services with other countries, especially if there are suitable existing services in one of the countries that can be made available to other countries, rather than each country developing its own infrastructure. This may ultimately lead to the benefit of a much more efficient and cost effective radioactive waste management system in individual countries as well as globally.	Costs estimation to evaluate recycling and sharing of services/infrastructure with different countries	Technological and economic	M	Related to Harpers scope	3, 4	
IAEA IDN	Status and Trends in Spent Fuel and Radioactive Waste Management No. NW-T-1.14 (Rev. 1)	IAEA Nuclear Energy Series	4.8. MINIMIZATION IN THE MANAGEMENT OF RADIOACTIVE WASTE	There can be limited possibilities for recycling or reuse of radioactive material, especially if it is supposed to be done nationally. Reuse of radioactive material means that an item will be used again, either to perform the same function or a different function. It needs be noted that there are different national approaches, depending on how the radioactive waste is defined. For example, in some countries, radioactive waste is considered only as the material is going to disposal. There are several other criteria to consider in minimization, such as radiation protection and public acceptance. These can weaken the advantage of waste minimization because of doses to workers during waste processing. The opportunity for recycling of materials from a nuclear facility can also be restricted or reduced because of opposition from the public. This means that for minimization in different phases of spent fuel and radioactive waste management there are different factors that need to be considered, as follows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Regulatory and licensing issues: compliance of the option with the applicable regulation; ● Technical and operational issues: availability of technology and facilities to process waste; ● Safety and ALARA issues; 	Problems related to reuse and recycle	Technological, regulatory, economic, societal	H	Related to Harpers scope	4	

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				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic and schedule issues: costs, duration of implementation of solutions, compatibility with agenda of waste generation; • Public acceptance and stakeholder issues 						
IAEA IDN	Status and Trends in Spent Fuel and Radioactive Waste Management No. NW-T-1.14 (Rev. 1)	IAEA Nuclear Energy Series	5.6.2. Return to supplier, reuse and recycle	There are various recycling methods available, such as recovery of the sealed source. Recycling reduces the amount of radioactive material that needs to be produced; however, at the same time it needs to be taken into account that these actions have to be cost effective and technically feasible.	Aspects to take in count to reuse and recycle	Technological, economic	H	Related to Harpers scope	4	
IAEA IDN	Status and Trends in Spent Fuel and Radioactive Waste Management No. NW-T-1.14 (Rev. 1)	IAEA Nuclear Energy Series	7.5. MANAGEMENT OF VERY LOW LEVEL WASTE	In several countries, it is possible to partially avoid the production of radioactive waste, by the implementation of recycling of radioactive material. Again, adequate characterization is a major consideration, and there have to be clear regulatory processes.	Regulatory aspects connected to reuse and recycle	Regulatory	H	Related to Harpers scope	4	
IAEA IDN	Status and Trends in Spent Fuel and Radioactive Waste Management No. NW-T-1.14 (Rev. 1)	IAEA Nuclear Energy Series	8.1.2. Facilities	Some countries, such as the UK, have been successful in diverting waste from their national LLW repository through a combination of recycling of material and diverting very low activity waste to other facilities, such as designated industrial landfills.	Need to increase available storage and disposal capacities	Technological and regulatory	M	Needs related to minimization of waste	4	
IAEA IDN	Status and Trends in Spent Fuel and Radioactive Waste Management No. NW-T-1.14 (Rev. 1)	IAEA Nuclear Energy Series	9. CONCLUSIONS	Therefore, the availability of disposal routes, in particular for VLLW, will become more and more important. In parallel, as disposal of any waste is not the most preferred option and as disposal facilities for radioactive waste and/or spent fuel are rare assets, there is the challenge of promoting and implementing waste minimization techniques or recycling after decontamination, in an overall optimization approach.	Needs related to reuse and recycle	Technological	M	Needs related to minimization of waste	4	
IAEA - IDN	Decontamination Approaches during Outages in Nuclear Power Plants — Experiences and Lessons Learned (TECDOC 1946)	TECDOC Series	3.2. NATIONAL VS LOCAL CONSIDERATIONS	<p>The level at which decisions about decontamination are taken depends on the local context: number of NPPs, nuclear programmes and infrastructure, ownership of the plants, etc.</p> <p>In a Member State with many NPPs under a common ownership (e.g. in France) there is a national policy and infrastructure covering most decontamination aspects e.g. a waste minimization policy, low-level waste (LLW) and very low-level waste (VLLW) disposal sites, a nation-wide regulatory system, a number of decontamination companies experienced in nuclear decontamination and active Research & Development (R&D) programmes. Within the mandatory boundaries of this infrastructure and an allocated budget, the operator of a given NPP will decide on the technical factors related to plant-specific features, such as dealing with materials, layout, radiation and contamination levels, and on renovation of the site infrastructure</p>	Waste minimisation policy depends on national and local considerations. No standard and harmonised approaches are present	regulatory, economic, societal, harmonisation	H	Linked to the objectives of HARPERS WP4: waste minimisation is a fundamental principle in the Circular Economy approach	4	

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				<p>and re-configuration of the site for decontamination purposes.</p> <p>There are also Member States (e.g. the USA) where national infrastructures and resources are widely available, but there is no national policy established for aspects relevant to decontamination e.g. on waste minimization: these decisions are taken at the utility corporate level, typically based on financial considerations (with the NPP organization being responsible for technical implementation depending on plant-specific features and the local market).</p> <p>.....</p> <p>The case of a country with one or two NPPs and/or modest nuclear power programmes is different: it is unlikely that resources and infrastructure are centralized, which implies that many more decisions about decontamination are taken locally. This may include, among others, decisions about the establishment of onsite RAW management facilities and additional (possibly long-term) storage capacity for RAW generated by decontamination. The operator can then decide on how the waste minimization principle is interpreted (subject to regulatory review).</p>						
IAEA NEFW										
IAEA-NEFW	Closing the Loop: IAEA Promotes Reuse and Recycling of Sealed Radioactive Sources	News Item	web page	<p>Sealed radioactive sources are used every day in equipment to treat cancer, sterilise blood and make food safe to eat. But with circular economy and sustainability in mind, manufacturers and users are looking for ways to reuse and recycle the sources and radioactive devices, and so reduce waste too.</p> <p>The IAEA has brought together decision makers, users, regulators, manufacturers, suppliers and waste management specialists to share their strategies and experiences. The initiative will lead to the publication of a technical document on the reuse and recycling of disused sealed radioactive sources (DSRS).</p>	Reuse and recycling of disused sealed radioactive sources (DSRS).	Environmental, economic, regulatory	H	Goes directly to circular economy/sustainability concerns. Also mentions cross-border recycling.	3, 4, 6	
IAEA NEFW	Management of Spent Fuel from Nuclear Power Reactors: Proceedings of an international conference Vienna, 19 -22 June 2006	Conference Proceedings	5.2. Safety standards	<p>The developments taking place in the combined use of spent fuel casks for storage and transport and possibly even for disposal will require a new approach. The design standards for long term storage casks and those for transport casks need to be harmonized.</p>	Needs for harmonisation of storage and transport cask design standards.	Technological, Harmonisation	H	Direct need presented for harmonisation within the scope of HARPERS	3, 5, 6	

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	Management of Spent Fuel from Nuclear Power Reactors: Proceedings of an international conference Vienna, 19 -22 June 2006		GLOBAL NUCLEAR ENERGY PARTNERSHIP DISCUSSION	Also, I believe that for a partnership like the one envisaged by the USA to succeed there must be a clear commitment to an international nuclear safety regime. This is very important for the USA because, with the growing harmonization of safety standards, we perceive that the USA sometimes goes in a different direction. Even the units used for radiation safety purposes in the USA are different from those used in other parts of the world. So I believe that partnership needs an international nuclear safety regime, whatever form that regime takes, with harmonization as a precondition.	Need for a harmonised international safety regime.	Harmonisation	M	Overarching harmonisation need presented.	6	
	Management of Spent Fuel from Nuclear Power Reactors: Proceedings of an international conference Vienna, 19 -22 June 2006		Regional disposal site	There is a need to link the use of these regional waste repositories to the development of shared safety and security standards. To achieve this, the standards drawn up by the IAEA could form a foundation for a harmonization and ongoing development exercise, if necessary, in line with the best existing practices, based on the model for possible developments on a European scale, as demonstrated by the WENRA regulators' initiative. A research programme could thus be launched along these lines.	Need to link regional repositories to development of harmonised, shared safety and security standards based on best existing practices.	Harmonisation, legal	H	Describes pathway for harmonising repository safety and security standards.	6	
	Management of Spent Fuel from Nuclear Power Reactors: Proceedings of an international conference Vienna, 19 -22 June 2006		7.5. Competent authority approval processes	There is a growing recognition that harmonization of the structure of cask safety cases and CA guidance material for applicants would be of benefit to the industry and would contribute to a more efficient and effective CA approval and validation process	Need for harmonisation of cask safety case structure.	Harmonisation, regulatory, technological	H	Describes harmonisation need.	3, 6	
	Management of Spent Fuel from Nuclear Power Reactors: Proceedings of an international conference Vienna, 19 -22 June 2006		STORAGE TERM LIMITS Discussion	Session 3 illustrates the need for international harmonization. For example, as said, we are freely using the expression 'long term storage' although it has not been defined and has different meanings for different people.	Need for international harmonisation of definitions.	Harmonisation	M	Describes harmonisation need.	6	
	Management of Spent Fuel from Nuclear Power Reactors: Proceedings of an international conference Vienna, 19 -22 June 2006		CLOSING ADDRESS	The worldwide application of the IAEA Transport Regulations was shown to be a good example of an effective framework that provides for a harmonized international regulatory infrastructure.	Application of IAEA Transport Regulations is described as an example of an effective framework providing for harmonized international regulatory infrastructure.	Harmonisation	M	Describes pathway for harmonisation of regulations.	6	
	Management of Spent Fuel from Nuclear Power Reactors:		INTERNATIONAL SAFETY REGIME	The IAEA should continue to strengthen its efforts to establish a complete system of international safety standards; the good example of the Transport Regulations could be used as a model. Particular efforts	A recommendation is given for IAEA to continue work on international safety standards.	Harmonisation	L	IAEA safety standards are put forth as starting framework.		

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	Proceedings of an international conference Vienna, 19 -22 June 2006			should be made to review the existing draft and planned standards on the safety of spent fuel management for completeness.						
	Management of Spent Fuel from Nuclear Power Reactors: Proceedings of an international conference Vienna, 19 -22 June 2006		INTERNATIONAL SAFETY REGIME	States might also consider making use of IAEA appraisal services in order to calibrate their national legal/regulatory frameworks and their national practices against international standards.	A recommendation for states to use IAEA to assess their national legal/regulatory frameworks and national practices against international standards.	Regulatory, Legal, Harmonisation	M	Benchmarking exercise for national legal/regulatory frameworks and national practices against international standards.	6	
	Management of Spent Fuel from Nuclear Power Reactors: Proceedings of an international conference Vienna, 19 -22 June 2006		MULTINATIONAL APPROACHES RELEVANT TO SPENT FUEL MANAGEMENT	The storage of spent fuel is a suitable candidate for a multilateral approach, primarily at the regional level. Small countries with only a few nuclear power plants would benefit economically from large joint facilities. The storage of special nuclear materials in a few safe and secure facilities would also enhance safeguards and physical protection. However, the final disposal of spent fuel and high-level radioactive waste is the best candidate for a multilateral approach. It would offer major economic benefits and substantial non-proliferation benefits in spite of the legal, political and public acceptance challenges to be expected in most countries. The transfer of nuclear waste from the exporting country to the host country of an interim storage facility or of a final repository would be done under bilateral or multilateral agreements at the commercial and governmental levels, in accordance with the Joint Convention on the Safety of Spent Fuel Management and on the Safety of Radioactive Waste Management.	Describes benefits of cross-border cooperation/agreement for nuclear waste management.	Technological, Regulatory, Economic, Societal, Legal, Harmonisation	H	Directly refers to topics where harmonisation would be of potentially great benefit.	3, 6	
	Management of Spent Fuel from Nuclear Power Reactors: Proceedings of an international conference Vienna, 19 -22 June 2006		LICENSING ASPECTS OF SPENT FUEL STORAGE AS A FUNCTION OF TIMESCALES	A generally agreed definition of long-term storage does not exist however. Typically, the period of concern covers a range from 30 to more than 100 years. Some regulatory authorities face challenges as initially the SF storage facilities were considered as short term solutions. This is the case of several Eastern European countries, where it was expected that the SF would be sent for reprocessing to the former Soviet Union. Because of the political changes of the last two decades this option is no longer available under the original conditions and the SF storage period in existing facilities outside the Russian Federation has to be extended. Other regulatory issues are linked to the licensing of changes in the storage technology, such as those due to increases in storage capacity. A nuclear regulatory body may also be faced with other challenges during the	Regulatory challenges related to SF storage are outlined and some examples given.	Regulatory, technological	L	Regulatory challenges are described.	5, 6	

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				licensing process when a new long-term storage facility is planned or under construction. All the above-mentioned licensing aspects have to be clearly defined and assessed from the point of view of national regulations, taking into account the safety functions of specific storage technologies. The objective of this paper is to demonstrate the recommended licensing approach by which the regulatory body is able to maintain the safety of SF storage facilities for the operating period, taking into account the long-term effects on SF and storage facility components. The licensing approach should also provide an interface to the next step in SF management, that is direct SF disposal or reprocessing. The scope of the paper covers the regulatory challenges in the process of issuing operational licenses for both wet and dry storage facilities for SF from power reactors in different timescales.						
	Management of Spent Fuel from Nuclear Power Reactors: Proceedings of an international conference Vienna, 19 -22 June 2006		SPENT FUEL STORAGE AS A FUNCTION OF TIMESCALES 6. Conclusions	Extension of SF storage timescales creates new challenges for national regulatory bodies. These challenges can be addressed by: (a) The clear definition of regulatory requirements and guidelines including, not only quantitative criteria for safe long term SF storage related to the safety functions of storage components, but also programmes of maintenance, testing, surveillance and inspections and ageing management programmes.	see above	see above	see above	see above	5, 6	
	Management of Spent Fuel from Nuclear Power Reactors: Proceedings of an international conference Vienna, 19 -22 June 2006		STORAGE TERM LIMITS	While the panel was not structured or intended to provide recommendations, the following points were repeatedly stressed during the presentations and dialogue: [...] e) Establishing monitoring and maintenance requirements for the long term is a challenge;	Regulatory challenges related to maintenance and monitoring.	Regulatory, technological	Low	Regulatory challenge, but interesting for harmonisation as well	5, 6	
ITER										
ITER	www.iter.org	website	https://www.iter.org/newsline/97/1328 https://www.iter.org/newsline/50/564 https://www.iter.org/mach/HotCell https://www.iter.org/newsline/-/2500	No	Only general information about RWM and decommissioning of ITER are provided (see the links in the first column)		L	There are no specific information relating to RWM and decommissioning.	3, 4, 5, 6	The website contains general information about ITER.
NEA CDLM										

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NEA CDLM <i>NOTE: The CDLM was established in 2018. The document mentioned above is a report generated by the NEA CPD which had a similar scope, and which is mentioned as a reference on the Homepage of the CDLM.</i>	Regulating the Decommissioning of Nuclear Facilities [OECD 2008] #6401	Report	Section 2.4.3. (p. 18)	“The relatively new activity of nuclear plant D&D raises the question of whether to seek harmonisation of regulatory standards and procedures or to maintain a flexible regulatory approach. The emerging view seems to be that it is more important to harmonise on general principles [...] rather than on the details of standards and procedures. A more flexible approach allows authorities to take account of site-specific circumstances and to tailor requirements to the planned use of the site. Flexibility also allows implementers to be innovative in developing approaches and solutions to increase safety or efficiency [...]. Furthermore, the flexibility to set regulatory requirements on a case-by-case basis may facilitate accommodation of local issues that arise for the stakeholder consultation [...]. Ultimately, good communication is more important than common criteria.”	Harmonisation may also be barrier for flexibility and innovations.	Regulatory, Technological	M	Critical remark on harmonisation. Argument may be investigated and assessed.	5,6	
NEA CDLM <i>NOTE: The CDLM was established in 2018. The document mentioned above is a report generated by the NEA CPD which had a similar scope, and which is mentioned as a reference on the Homepage of the CDLM.</i>	Regulating the Decommissioning of Nuclear Facilities [OECD 2008] #6401	Report	Section 2.4.3 (p. 18)	“[...] there may be situations, with several adjacent nuclear countries for example, when there may be some benefit in seeking to harmonise criteria such as clearance levels for release of material from regulatory control in order to facilitate transboundary movement.”	Benefits from harmonisations in case of adjacent nuclear countries.	Regulatory	L	Focus on clearance to simplify transboundary shipments, no consideration of recycling/reuse for waste minimisations.	6	

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NEA CDLM NOTE: The CDLM was established in 2018. The document mentioned above is a report generated by the NEA CPD which had a similar scope, and which is mentioned as a reference on the Homepage of the CDLM.	Recycling and Reuse of Materials Arising from the Decommissioning of Nuclear Facilities #7310	Report	Chapter 3 (p.26)	“The responses to the 2015 CPD questionnaire and the experience of the task group deployed to review the 20 years of progress since the 1996 report published its recommendations lead to the conclusion that despite the recommendations of the 1996 report, the CPD feels that clearance levels remain insufficiently developed, and the harmonisation of release criteria between countries has not developed sufficiently to be used for a general adoption of recycling and reuse of materials from decommissioning projects.”	Harmonisation of release criteria between countries to simplify/enable cross-border transfers of material(s) for the purpose of recycling/reuse	Regulatory challenge w. r. t. the minimisation of wastes	L	General, regulatory impediment w. r. t. waste minimisation by recycling	6	
NEA CDLM NOTE: The CDLM was established in 2018. The document mentioned above is a report generated by the NEA CPD which had a similar scope, and which is mentioned as a reference on the Homepage of the CDLM.	Recycling and Reuse of Materials Arising from the Decommissioning of Nuclear Facilities #7310	Report	Chapter 7	“While the transfer of waste remains prohibited between countries, substantial quantities of materials, particularly scrap metals and concrete, are routinely available to member countries for recycling or reuse as a result of the decommissioning and dismantling of nuclear facilities. Several international guidelines exist for how clearance and release of these materials should be regulated, and many countries that have developed specific criteria for recycling or reuse have achieved high levels of success. Nevertheless, harmonisation of regulations among countries has not evolved significantly in the past 20 years, which may continue to be a challenge to future recycling and reuse efforts as well as general acceptance.”	This observation provides a statement on the current practice w. r. t. the transfer of material across borders for the purpose of recycling/reuse. It concludes that there hasn't been significant progress during the past 20 years w. r. t. to the harmonisation of regulations among countries.	Challenge w. r. t. to the minimisation of wastes	L	General, regulatory impediment w. r. t. waste minimisation by recycling	6	
NEA CDLM NOTE: The CDLM was established in 2018. The	Recycling and Reuse of Materials Arising from the Decommissioning of Nuclear Facilities	Report	Chapter 7	“The IAEA and European Commission have developed high-level guidance and criteria that provide a framework for national-level policies and procedures. For unconditional clearance, most countries use the	Need for an international consensus guidance for a more stringent use of conditional clearance, which might be beneficial	Regulatory impediment	L	General, regulatory impediment w. r. t. waste minimisation by recycling	6	

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document mentioned above is a report generated by the NEA CPD which had a similar scope, and which is mentioned as a reference on the Homepage of the CDLM.	#7310			general limits introduced in these documents with minimal to no further restrictions. For conditional clearance, no international consensus guidance exists, and national legislation and site-specific regulations are routinely imposed by authorities for release of any material."	for re-using and recycling purposes.					
NEA CDLM NOTE: The CDLM was established in 2018. The document mentioned above is a report generated by the NEA CPD which had a similar scope, and which is mentioned as a reference on the Homepage of the CDLM.	Recycling and Reuse of Materials Arising from the Decommissioning of Nuclear Facilities #7310	Report	Chapter 7	"The continued evolution of radiation detection instrumentation, with increased measurement sensitivity, provides greater certainty of achieving conditional and unconditional clearance standards. However, very conservative clearance standards may pose challenges even to state-of-the-art Instrumentation. The establishment of regulatory requirements for clearance should take such practical aspects into account.	State-of-the-art instruments may have better detection capabilities (e. g. lower detection limits) which can enable a conditional/unconditional clearance. However, conservative clearance standards can still be a challenge.	Regulatory/technical impediment	M	Conservative clearance levels may require new detection systems with sufficient detection capabilities (WP5) or a consideration of practical aspects within the regulatory requirements (WP6)	5, 6	
NEA CDLM NOTE: The CDLM was established in 2018. The document mentioned above is a report generated by the NEA CPD which had a similar scope, and which is mentioned as a reference on the Homepage of the CDLM.	Preparing for Decommissioning During Operation and After Final Shutdown #7374	Report	Section 7.2. (p. 62)	Within their activities and observations, the task group has identified several areas in the context of the transition of a facility from operation to decommissioning that would merit further attention and where the international community would benefit from further study via international experience sharing. Among the topics are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • knowledge management: keep, transfer and maintain; • training and qualifications; • communications; 	Further development/improvement of key aspects in decommissioning	Technological, Economic	L	Broad range of topics, very generic	3, 4	

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by the NEA CPD which had a similar scope, and which is mentioned as a reference on the Homepage of the CDLM.				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • human performance and demonstration of continuous improvement; • integrated management and organisational change from the stakeholders' perspective; • safety culture; • programme and project management; • supply chain management and the development of contracting models. 						
NEA CDLM NOTE: The CDLM was established in 2018. The document mentioned above is a report generated by the NEA CPD which had a similar scope, and which is mentioned as a reference on the Homepage of the CDLM.	Cost Benchmarking for Nuclear Power Plant Decommissioning #7460	Final Report	Chapter 4 (p. 24)	The nuclear industry has numerous commercial, cultural, security and risk concerns that act as barriers to sharing cost information with others. Today there is essentially only internal cost benchmarking within organisations, and this is not adding the overall value sought from cost benchmarking. The nuclear industry often describes his reluctance to share data as a fundamental barrier to even engaging in the first, potential steps required to start implementing cost benchmarking across the industry.	Barrier: No incentive for industry engagement	Economic	M	Cost efficiency is typically considered as a driving factor. However, costs/costing can only be addressed in a generic level as it is project specific.	3	
NEA CDLM NOTE: The CDLM was established in 2018. The document mentioned above is a report generated by the NEA CPD which had a similar scope, and which is	Cost Benchmarking for Nuclear Power Plant Decommissioning #7460	Final Report	Chapter 4 (p. 24)	Actual cost information that can add value when it is made available to others is a crucial aspect of the cost benchmarking process. In other words, it is important to have information on actual costs for projects and activities that have been completed. This might also include records of estimates made at recognised project stages, useful when examining the effect of project and engineering maturity on estimates. Actual cost data needs to be accompanied by a description of the project or activity scope that it represents. This description must describe boundary conditions sufficiently well in order to allow reliance on the cost information definition in the preparation of other estimates, decisions and approaches to proposed decommissioning work and services. [...]	Barrier: Absence of actual cost data	Economic	M	Improvement of cost efficiency is typically considered as a driving factor. However, costs/costing can only be addressed in a generic level as it is project specific.	3	

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mentioned as a reference on the Homepage of the CDLM.				There is a general absence of industry shared, actual cost data from NPP decommissioning to support external cost benchmarking. This absence of shared information generally results from few such NPP decommissioning projects having been fully completed. While some project and multi-national data are captured and managed in specific cases (e.g. within the EU Nuclear Decommissioning Assistance Programme [NDAP]), where such actual cost data exists, its collection and sharing is not widespread.						
NEA CDLM NOTE: The CDLM was established in 2018. The document mentioned above is a report generated by the NEA CPD which had a similar scope, and which is mentioned as a reference on the Homepage of the CDLM.	Cost Benchmarking for Nuclear Power Plant Decommissioning #7460	Final Report	Chapter 5 (p. 42)	The relatively large number of NPPs internationally, as well as the considerable costs and long time frames envisaged in NPP decommissioning, suggest that benchmarking approaches for decommissioning costs deserves much greater attention. Other industries have led the way in demonstrating how cost benchmarking can provide valuable insights for managing costs and improving project delivery. Implementing such a service for NPP decommissioning, or for decommissioning more generally, will require international collaboration across the industry. The recommendations outlined in this report offer a way forward to proceed with a more detailed discussion and evaluation of options to develop and implement cost benchmarking for the decommissioning of nuclear power plants.	International collaboration across the industry needed to strengthen benchmarking approaches	Economic	M	Cost efficiency is typically considered as a driving factor. However, costs/costing can only be addressed in a generic level as it is project specific.	3	
NEA CDLM NOTE: The CDLM was established in 2018. The document mentioned above is a report generated by the NEA CPD which had a similar scope, and which is mentioned as a	Cost Benchmarking for Nuclear Power Plant Decommissioning #7460	Final Report		Currently, no organisation or governance has been established or designated to collect and share data in the nuclear sector. And yet any such structure and process must be managed in a way that will meet and satisfy potential stakeholder concerns. It is also necessary to encourage engagement by showing real value and benefits at the different stakeholder levels. Other industries have developed an organisation, governance and facilitation to both enable management of the perceived risks and add value, and there is sufficient evidence to indicate that the nuclear industry can learn and benefit from this experience	Barrier: No investment in organisation or facilitation	Economic, (Technological)	M	Cost efficiency is typically considered as a driving factor. However, costs/costing can only be addressed in a generic level as it is project specific.	3	This aspect does not only have to cover economic aspects but could also be applied to the exchange of technological information. The IAEA has established the IDN for the exchange of decommissioning related

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reference on the Homepage of the CDLM.										information. This approach could serve as a template
NEA RWMC										
NEA RWMC	Nuclear Site Remediation and Restoration during Decommissioning of Nuclear Installations #7192	Report	4.2	All this gathered experience leads to the identification of some recommendations for the optimisation of current remediation projects and for reducing the remediation cost in future decommissioning projects. Prevention Minimisation (contamination spread and remedy work) Characterisation Decision-making/remedial planning Monitoring and assessment Regulation Relations with stakeholders	Cost reduction and optimisation for current and future remediation projects.	Economic Regulatory Environmental	M	Recommendations for the optimisation of projects.	4, 6	
NEA RWMC	Nuclear Site Remediation and Restoration during Decommissioning of Nuclear Installations #7192	Report	4.3	Knowledge sharing and working with international partners. Remediation is a complex technical subject and therefore to allow adoption of best practice and innovation it is important to have appropriate levels of, and mechanisms for, knowledge sharing and experience sharing between problem holders and solution donors. It is very important for stakeholders to achieve a common understanding of all the main issues involved in remediation. The responsibility for disseminating this information rests with the site operator, however international organisations can play a key role in this regard.	Harmonisation of regulations interconnected with knowledge sharing	Harmonisation Environmental	M	Common understanding of all the main issues involved in remediation.	3, 6	
NEA RWMC	Nuclear Site Remediation and Restoration during Decommissioning of Nuclear Installations #7192	Report	4.3.2	Existing networks	Mapping and description of established networks	Harmonisation	M	Stakeholders networking	3	
NEA RWMC	Nuclear Site Remediation and Restoration during Decommissioning of Nuclear Installations #7192	Report	Table 3.2	Summary of experience The case studies were analysed to identify good practices and difficulties and these are summarised in Table 3.2.	Good practices description summarised for Stakeholder engagement Problem definition Remedial investigation (Characterisation and Assessment) Remedial planning Remedial action/Implementation Project closeout Institutional control	Technological Regulatory Environmental	M	Good practices added value	4	

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NEA RWMC	Fostering a Durable Relationship Between a Waste Management Facility and its Host Community #7264	Report	5	This report examines the added value that may arise from the decision-making and implementation process. Implementing any radioactive waste management facility has the potential to benefit the community in terms of prosperity, but in the best of cases, increased stability and cohesiveness are also gained, which represent added cultural value. Other cultural benefits that may be accrued are an enhanced educational level in the host community because of the influx of highly skilled workers. Not least important, when host communities demand training and participate in monitoring site development and operations, they are building their capacity to act as guardians and therefore ensure another layer of defence in depth.	Considerable added value in social acceptance subject.	Societal	M	Possibly important subject not directly aligned to HARPERS aim.	3	
NEA RWMC	Fostering a Durable Relationship Between a Waste Management Facility and its Host Community #7264	Report	3.2	<p>The cultural value is found in arrangements that reflect and strengthen a given society's knowledge, tastes, aspirations, ethical views, or beliefs. It lies in all that is meant to help to transmit an honoured legacy, to communicate symbolic meaning, or to carry forward and realise ideals.</p> <p>The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) has defined culture as "the set of distinctive spiritual, material, intellectual and emotional features of society or a social group, encompassing, in addition to art and literature, lifestyles, ways of living together, value systems, traditions and beliefs".² In this way, culture may be assimilated to shared meaning and practices. Culture is not a fixed-for-ever set of features, and facility designers must give attention to what may help culture to develop further.</p> <p>Four design features were found by the FSC to provide opportunities for how designers and communities can instil meaning into a radioactive waste management facility and site. Table 3 summarises these features and their characteristics, the value they may add to the community and strategies for achieving them.</p>	The cultural factor may impact harmonisation efforts. Applying recognized techniques facilitates harmonisation allowing common benefit.	Societal	M	Possibly important subject not directly aligned to HARPERS aim.	3	
NEA RWMC	Storage of Radioactive Waste and Spent Fuel #7406	Report	Chapter 5.	As proven by more than 50 years of operation, the storage of spent fuel and radioactive waste can be both safe and secure. Storage fulfils the ethical goal of keeping future radioactive waste management options open, provided that facilities are continuously monitored and maintained. For countries that are new to civil nuclear power generation, developing a programme for storage of radioactive waste and spent fuel must ensure passive safety, multiple barrier	WAC harmonisation as a tool for safe operation.	Regulatory Harmonisation	M	Harmonisation of waste acceptance criteria (WAC) for safe storage	3, 6	

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				containment, robustness with adequate storage capacity and effective storage facility maintenance. Appropriately established waste acceptance criteria (WAC) for storage are the basis to verify the compliance of waste packages with a storage licence. Maintenance, monitoring and periodic inspection of the installation and the waste packages should be undertaken to ensure that the storage facilities, and the stored radioactive waste and spent fuel, are in accordance with the storage licence.						
NEA RWMC	Storage of Radioactive Waste and Spent Fuel #7406	Report	Table 2.2.	Financial arrangements in selected countries Belgium, Canada, Finland, Hungary, Italy, Russia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom, United States	Financial arrangements description	Economic	M	Financial arrangements as an impacting factor for regulations development and regulations harmonisation.	6	
NEA RWMC	Storage of Radioactive Waste and Spent Fuel #7406	Report	Chapter 3.	Some NEA member countries have developed their storage WAC based on the foreseeable conditions as identified in the facility safety case (e.g. the United Kingdom), some also with the future disposal requirements or management strategies taken into account (e.g. Sweden). In planning the storage conditions, compatibility with handling, transport and storage requirements (including suitability for retrieval and transport following the anticipated storage period) are often considered. To ensure that waste packages meet the defined acceptance criteria upon receipt, most countries implement processes and procedures such as auditing, inspection and conformance verification. Taking the United Kingdom as an example, the UK Radioactive Waste Management (RWM) defines conditions for acceptance (CfA, equivalent to WAC) for all stored waste, which are underpinned by a safety case, and confirms acceptance through disposability assessment. Only when the waste is rendered passively safe and meets the defined waste specifications will RWM issue a letter of compliance. RWM also undertakes technical audits of their waste packaging and storage operations to confirm their continual consistency with their future disposable waste packages. Unlike the United Kingdom, some countries have defined WAC in their regulations or regulators are involved in drafting WAC. In these countries, WAC need approvals from the regulators or specific requirements for waste conditioning, waste forms and packages may be defined in the facility licensing documents (e.g. Finland, Poland and Sweden). In Russia, WAC are not separately specified for storage, but for the entire RW management process (i.e. storage included). Their series of RW management requirements, namely NP-058-14;	Waste acceptance criteria for storage	Regulatory Harmonisation	M		3, 6	

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				NP-019-15; NP-020-15 and NP-035-02, require the nuclear facilities to have the necessary organisational and technical measures to ensure safe RW storage.						
NEA RWMC	Optimising Management of Low-level Radioactive Materials and Waste from Decommissioning #7245	Report	Chapter 4	As more nuclear facilities enter decommissioning around the world, it is important that the management of (very) low-level radioactivity (or [V])LLW is optimised since it represents the vast majority (by volume) of radioactive waste generated during decommissioning and dismantling. A number of factors have been identified as influencing the ability of a site or facility to optimise its (V)LLW management, and these include strategy and planning, safety and the environment, characterisation, enabling infrastructure, stakeholder involvement, and financial and economic aspects.	(V)LLW management optimisation	Economic	M	Factors influencing the ability of a site or facility to optimise its (V)LLW management	4	
NEA RWMC	Optimising Management of Low-level Radioactive Materials and Waste from Decommissioning #7245	Report	Chapter 5.	During the development of this publication, and in the meetings of the Nuclear Energy Agency (NEA) Working Party on Decommissioning and Dismantling (WPDD), a number of areas were identified for potential future work. The benefits of harmonising clearance levels between countries has also been recognised, as has potential improvements to available instrumentation that demonstrates that established clearance levels have been achieved.	Identification of potential future work. Benefits of harmonising clearance levels	Economic Harmonisation	H	Harmonising clearance levels subject	3, 4, 6	
NEA RWMC	Stakeholder Confidence in Radioactive Waste Management #7606	Report	Chapter 2	The concept of “added value” refers to an understanding that the societal benefit of a radioactive waste management facility is in part determined by its features and benefits beyond serving its core function, which is the safe management or disposal of used nuclear fuel or radioactive waste. Added value does not substitute for compensation measures, but compensation measures may lead to added value.	Understanding the societal benefit of a radioactive waste management	societal	M	Added value approach	3, 4, 6	
NEA RWMC	Stakeholder Confidence in Radioactive Waste Management #7606	Report	Chapter 12.	The question of whether or not the regulator should be regarded as a stakeholder was raised early within the FSC. In some countries, the suggestion of pursuing a given agenda that is sometimes associated with the term “stakeholder” renders the term unacceptable, because the regulator’s role is seen as neutrally applying rules and standards. However, the majority view is that regulators have a role to play and therefore, can be considered a stakeholder. For the FSC and the RWMC Regulators’ Forum, the regulator is a stakeholder.	Regulator as a stakeholder	Regulatory	M	Regulator’s role as applying rules and standards	6	
NEI (Nuclear Energy Institute)										
NEI	www.nei.org	Website	https://nei.org/fundamentals/nuclear-waste https://www.nei.org/resources/fact-	No	Only general information about RWM and decommissioning of US NPPs are provided (see		L	There are no specific information relating to RWM and decommissioning.	3, 4, 5, 6	The website contains general

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			sheets/decommissioning-nuclear-power-plants https://nei.org/resources/statistics/decommissioning-status-for-shutdown-us-plants		the links in the first column).			Status of US NPPs may be usable.		information about US NPPs.
NUCLEAREUROPE										
NUCLEAR EUROPE	DEEP GEOLOGICAL REPOSITORY	Background Paper	5.	<p>“In general, radioactive waste and SF management are a national matter. Each Member State is responsible for considering the options in accordance with its own legal framework. Although Member States are required by EU law to report regularly on their inventories, they are free to choose their own approaches and to use their own methods and tools based on specific national circumstances and conditions.</p> <p>For the moment such a national focus is still highly prevalent. There is a common political basis (or shared objective) which is to consider that the present generation must resolve waste management issues without placing any undue burden on future generations. However, many of the national programs plan to postpone their decision on final disposal or SF reprocessing far into the future. Some countries, with small volumes of radioactive waste, are looking into the possibility of either developing a common international repository or making use of a larger repository in another Member State. But these options are only expected to become available in a relatively distant future.</p> <p>The development of any DGR project is crucial, not only for the management of national waste inventories, but also in order to support consistencies between political objectives and effective short-term policies.”</p>	<p>Need DGR project</p> <p>Develop a common international repository or allow making use of a larger repository in another Member State.</p>	Technological, regulatory, economic, societal, legal, and environmental	M		6	
NUCLEAR EUROPE	RADIOACTIVE WASTE AND SPENT FUEL	Background Paper	2. CLASSIFICATION OF RADIOACTIVE WASTE	Each country has its own radioactive waste classification, ranging from the lowest category, which can be, depending on the country, either Very Low-Level Waste (VLLW) or Low-Level Waste (LLW), to the highest category which is High-Level Waste (HLW) including Spent Fuel.	Harmonise radioactive waste classification	Legal, Harmonisation Regulatory	M		6	
NUCLEAR EUROPE	CLEARANCE OF MATERIALS	Position Paper	9. EU Harmonization	Many countries have based their clearance regulation (or part of it) on guidance documents by the International Atomic Energy Agency and/or European Atomic Energy Community. Nevertheless, clearance options are implemented according to various circumstances, based on country-specific evaluations. For example, sometimes clearance	Implement harmonized clearance conditions between MS to allow a better circulation within EU country.	Technological, regulatory, economic, environmental	H		3, 4, 6	

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				<p>may not be possible due to current regulatory restrictions (such as in France). In practice, different clearance conditions may be implemented within the different countries, while manufactured products or materials may circulate within any EU country. The result is that conditions for release may appear to be defined at a national level, while part of the materials or products in use in the country may satisfy other requirements for use in another country.</p> <p>This de facto emphasizes the fact that, at least at European level, the clearance framework should be consistent, and the current different national regulations should be harmonized.</p> <p>As far as products (such as recycled metals) are often exchanged world-wide, a common approach to clearance and release should also be developed at an international level.</p>	Define a consistent clearance framework and harmonise the current different national regulations.					
PREDIS										
PREDIS	Deliverable 2.2 Gap Analysis 31.5.2021 version Final	Deliverable	6.3.3 Solid Organic Waste Gap Analysis (WP6)	<p>A systematic assessment of the durability and the stability of the selected conditioned wastes is required. According to WAC (if available, not obvious for the geopolymer binder), the key parameters influencing the stability and durability under representative disposal conditions will be identified. Since most of the partners carry out this evaluation under their 'national' requirements, and in many cases using different conditioned wastes (as for example the expected composition of the solution and the prevailing redox conditions can be different from one repository to another), which makes an overall evaluation of the benefit of the technologies and the immobilisation processes difficult. Therefore, a common approach is needed by defining a reference protocol and experimental conditions.</p>	Outlines a need for a common approach for defining reference protocol and experimental conditions on assessment of the durability and stability of conditioned waste.	Harmonisation, Technological	M	Standardization of test protocols for determining conditioning matrix performance could lead to increased used of specific conditioning technologies.	3, 5, 6	
PREDIS	Deliverable 2.2 Gap Analysis 31.5.2021 version Final	Deliverable	Appendix 4: WP4-Related Gap Analysis Results	finding routes for cleared metal waste, e.g., national limits permit release but scrap metal handlers refuse receipt	Highlights a need for increased acceptance of cleared wastes.	technological, economic, societal, environmental	H	Increased acceptance of cleared wastes could lead to increased recycling and reuse opportunities.	4	
PREDIS	Deliverable 2.2 Gap Analysis 31.5.2021 version Final	Deliverable	Appendix 4: WP4-Related Gap Analysis Results	mobile waste treatment	Increased availability of tools for application in radioactive waste management. May provide lowered cost barrier and cross-border services.	technological, regulatory, economic, societal, environmental, harmonisation	H	Harmonised approval of mobile monitoring systems could lead to increased cross-border use and commercial opportunities.	3, 5	

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PREDIS	Deliverable 2.2 Gap Analysis 31.5.2021 version Final	Deliverable	Appendix 5: WP5-Related Gap Analysis Results	clearance of very lightly contaminated liquids	Highlights a need/desire for easier clearance of very lightly contaminated liquids.	technological, regulatory, economic, societal, environmental	M	Increased acceptance of cleared wastes could lead to more optimised waste management.	6	
PREDIS	Deliverable 2.2 Gap Analysis 31.5.2021 version Final	Deliverable	Appendix 5: WP5-Related Gap Analysis Results	establishing geopolymer material standards (for use in waste conditioning)	Highlights a need for establishing geopolymer material standards.	Harmonisation, Technological	H	Having geopolymer material standards could lead to increased acceptance of geopolymer-based conditioning technologies.	3, 4, 5	4 only to the extent that such materials can be locally sourced and/or make use of recycled materials
PREDIS	Deliverable 2.2 Gap Analysis 31.5.2021 version Final	Deliverable	Appendix 6: WP6-Related Gap Analysis Results	sustainability and wider environmental impact of solid organic waste treatment and conditioning	Indicates need for considering sustainability and environmental impact in solid organic waste treatment and conditioning.	Technological, Environmental,	M	Self-explanatory.	4	
PREDIS	Deliverable 2.2 Gap Analysis 31.5.2021 version Final	Deliverable	Appendix 6: WP6-Related Gap Analysis Results	harmonisation of treatment and conditioning methods with waste acceptance criteria	Waste acceptance criteria are not harmonised.	Harmonisation, Technological	M	Harmonisation of treatment and conditioning methods with waste acceptance criteria could lead to increased use of specific conditioning technologies.	3, 5, 6	
PREDIS	Deliverable 2.2 Gap Analysis 31.5.2021 version Final	Deliverable	Appendix 7: WP7-Related Gap Analysis Results	mobile monitoring systems	Advanced tools for application in radioactive waste management.	Technological, Harmonisation	M	Standardisation of mobile monitoring systems could lead to increased use and commercial opportunities.	3, 5	
PREDIS	Milestone M2.3 Baseline Strategic Research Agenda 20.08.2021 version 1	SRA	5.1.1.1 Planning	Understanding the characteristics and quantities of wastes from Gen IV reactors. While these reactors should produce less radioactive wastes than current reactors, the wastes will have different properties and challenges compared with current wastes [8]. A specific example is the use of lead coolant in Baseline Strategic Research Agenda Page 19/30 Advanced Lead Fast Reactors, which requires a waste management strategy to be developed for use.	Describes research needs regarding GEN IV reactors from waste management point of view.	Technological, regulatory, economic, harmonisation	M	Not a direct harmonisation need, but a challenge regarding waste management for Gen IV reactors. Harmonisation of regulations regarding waste management for such technologies could lead to increased deployment.	3, 5, 6	
PREDIS	Milestone M2.3 Baseline Strategic Research Agenda 20.08.2021 version 1	SRA	5.1.1.2.1	There is a need to gain a better understanding of certain waste inventories that exist, which are currently either not well characterised or are known to pose issues for current treatment and conditioning technologies and disposal routes (legacy and problematic wastes). A better understanding of the characteristics of these wastes and how they will behave in a disposal environment is required to support the development of options for treatment and disposal and to understand if	Describes R&D needs regarding characterisation of uncertain/unknown waste inventories.	Technological, economic	M	Better characterisation could serve as a catalyst or would be a prerequisite for the application of potential cross-border services, creation of sustainable/circular economy options or use of some advanced	3, 4, 5, 6	

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				bespoke solutions requiring specific R&D is required. Particular wastes highlighted in existing SRAs include graphite wastes, mixed wastes, organic wastes, tritiated wastes [3], and small inventories of fuel from research reactors [4].				technologies. Such implementations would be made easier by regulatory harmonisation.		
PREDIS	Milestone M2.3 Baseline Strategic Research Agenda 20.08.2021 version 1	SRA	5.1.1.2.5	Identifying good practice in the assessment, recording and management of inventory data is raised in several existing SRAs [12], [4], [8], [11]. This includes use of targeted, fit-for-purpose assays [8], use of radionuclide vectors, characterising wasteforms, addressing uncertainties in radionuclide properties databases [11], remote and in-situ technologies [3], measurement and modelling [4].	Describes a need to identify good practices regarding assessment, recording and management of waste inventory data.	Technological, economic, harmonisation	M	Identifying good practices in inventory management could be a first step toward standardisation/harmonisation of such practices and could lead to implementation of potential cross-border services, creation of sustainable/circular economy options or use of some advanced technologies down the road. Such implementations would be made easier by regulatory harmonisation.	3, 4, 5, 6	
PREDIS	Milestone M2.3 Baseline Strategic Research Agenda 20.08.2021 version 1	SRA	5.1.1.3 Classification	Classification relates to the categorisation of waste types based on their properties. Specific issues within existing SRAs that relate to classification are outlined below. Baseline Strategic Research Agenda Page 21/30 As discussed in Section 5.1.1.2.3, understanding the non-radiological properties and inventory of radioactive waste is important for predisposal management. In addition to this, developing a common system for the classification of wastes based on physico-chemical properties would support better management of these wastes [4].	Describes a need for a common system for waste classification.	technological, economic, harmonisation, legal	M	Developing a common system for waste classification is a preliminary standardisation/harmonisation action. Could lead to implementation of potential cross-border services, creation of sustainable/circular economy options or use of some advanced technologies down the road. Such implementations would be made easier by regulatory harmonisation.	3, 4, 5, 6	
PREDIS	Milestone M2.3 Baseline Strategic Research Agenda 20.08.2021 version 1	SRA	5.1.2.1.2 Understanding best practice in decontamination technologies	Understanding best practice in decontamination technologies is highlighted in [3], covering the different technologies (chemical, mechanical, thermal, other) and their efficiency, avoiding use of large amounts of additives and reducing secondary waste. Applying local decontamination, waste and effluent treatment units is also needed, which requires development of intensified processes for use in modular and mobile plants. Application of remote operations and robotics is also	Describes a need to identify good practices regarding decontamination technologies. Directly connects this identification to modularisation, remote robotic operations and	technological, economic, environmental, harmonisation	H	Identifying best practices in decontamination techniques/technologies could be a first step toward standardisation/harmonisation of such practices. This identification is directly connected to	3, 4, 5, 6	

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				needed. Assay technologies are required to verify the composition of materials that have undergone decontamination, to allow them to be routed for reuse or recycle.	recycling and reuse opportunities.			development of modular/mobile units, recycling and reuse opportunities and deployment of remote robotic operations.		
PREDIS	Milestone M2.3 Baseline Strategic Research Agenda 20.08.2021 version 1	SRA	5.1.2.2 Conditioning	Existing SRAs identify the need for development of novel conditioning technologies to address a range of problematic wastes (including ion exchange resins, tritiated wastes, wastes containing high levels of I-129, sealed sources, plutonium residues and bitumen sludges) [8]. This includes development of new materials for use as conditioning matrices (e.g. geopolymers) [4] to address safety, technical and economic aspects. The benefit of collaborative R&D and sharing of best practice to support these areas is highlighted [8].	Describes a need for development of novel conditioning techniques using new materials.	technological, economic, harmonisation	M	Eventual deployment of any novel conditioning technologies employing new materials would be aided by harmonisation of standards and regulations.	3, 4, 5, 6	
PREDIS	Milestone M2.3 Baseline Strategic Research Agenda 20.08.2021 version 1	SRA	5.1.2.3 Packaging <i>similar prospect identified under 5.1.3.2 Management of items under long-term storage</i>	Knowledge exchange on good practice for the management of waste packages that have become damaged or degraded prior to disposal. This includes developing criteria to determine whether aged wastes require re-processing and/or re-packaging [8] and how to carry out this re-work.	Describes a need to share best practices regarding management of damaged or degraded waste packages	technological, economic, harmonisation	M	Sharing of best practices and developing reprocessing/repackaging criteria is a preliminary standardisation/harmonisation action. Could lead to implementation of potential cross-border services or use of some advanced technologies down the road. Such implementations would be made easier by regulatory harmonisation.	3, 5, 6	
PREDIS	Milestone M2.3 Baseline Strategic Research Agenda 20.08.2021 version 1	SRA	5.2.1 Disposability Assessment <i>similar prospect identified under 5.2.1.5 Common approach to disposability assessments and records management to support small inventory member states</i>	While disposal operations and the long-term performance of a repository are not within the remit of the PREDIS SRA, disposability assessment is relevant to pre-disposal activities. This is because we need to understand the types of parameters that need to be better controlled and characterised during pre-disposal operations in order not to adversely affect the waste's long-term disposal performance. With this focus in mind, the main areas highlighted within existing SRAs for future R&D and knowledge management are: [...] Common approach to disposability assessments and records management to support small inventory member states (linked to pre-disposal planning and decisions) [...]	Describes a need for a common approach to disposability assessments and records management linked to pre-disposal planning and decisions.	harmonisation, legal	M	Developing a common approach to disposability assessments and records management is a preliminary standardisation/harmonisation action. Could lead to implementation of potential cross-border services, i.e., shared repository or providing disposal and safety assessments. Such implementations would be made easier by regulatory harmonisation.	3, 6	

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PREDIS	Milestone M2.3 Baseline Strategic Research Agenda 20.08.2021 version 1	SRA	5.2.2 Waste Acceptance Criteria	Areas relating to Waste Acceptance Criteria identified within existing SRAs and project reports are: • Development of good practice guides for the derivation of WAC, accounting for waste characteristics and uncertainties, the disposal concept, and local site conditions [8]	Describes need for development of good practice guidance related to derivation of waste acceptance criteria	harmonisation, legal	M	Developing good practice guidance is a preliminary standardisation/harmonisation act. May serve as impetus for establishing cross-border (treatment/conditioning) services.	3, 6	
SCK CEN D&D										
SCK CEN D&D	Report on international experiences on communication related to decommissioning of NPP: Synthesizing lessons learned for communication of D&D from existing projects and a dedicated workshop	Deliverable of the project 87; BENG18700	Introduction	Scientific and grey literature (e.g. project reports and technical documents) show that the only chance to find a legitimate solution for decommissioning programs is the establishment of a complementary socio-technical decision-making model that applies participatory practices and engages with stakeholders... A decommissioning program that is fair and has good acceptance, but has a poor process, is unlikely to be implemented by the convenors of a process e.g. operator, while a decommissioning program that has good process, but poor acceptance, is likely to be met with public or stakeholder scepticism, dispute or boycott	Development of a process, tools and methods for participatory practices and stakeholder engagement in decommissioning, already during the Environmental Impact Assessment	Societal, legal	H	Need for engagement is recognised but still challenging	6	
SCK CEN D&D	Report on international experiences on communication related to decommissioning of NPP: Synthesizing lessons learned for communication of D&D from existing projects and a dedicated workshop	Deliverable of the project 87; BENG18700	Societal challenges in decommissioning programs	The range of non-technical factors that influence the overall decommissioning program include economy, employment and infrastructure; costs, funding, and financing; regulatory and institutional aspects; stakeholder perception and participation; project implementation related risks; co-contamination issues; future land use; stewardship issues	Investigation on non-technical factors influencing overall decommissioning program	societal	M	Every decommissioning is a socio-technical process and not only technical	6	
			Societal challenges in decommissioning programs	Societal challenges that hinder progress in decommissioning programmes and possible actions to be undertaken to overcome these challenges	Evidence and theory based research on societal challenges that hinder progress in decommissioning programmes and possible actions to be undertaken to overcome these challenges	societal	H	On-going and planned decommissioning process are based on assumptions	6	
SCK CEN D&D	Report on international experiences on communication related to	Deliverable of the project 87; BENG18700	Societal challenges in decommissioning programs	Lack of support by the governmental authorities to implement decommissioning process and changing the administrative procedure and legal framework related to decommissioning programmes	Empirical investigation on views, expectations, attitudes, opinions related to decommissioning	Socio-political	M	Decommissioning involves many levels of authorities. Authorities might change through the d. process.	6	

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	decommissioning of NPP: Synthesizing lessons learned for communication of D&D from existing projects and a dedicated workshop									
SCK CEN D&D	Report on international experiences on communication related to decommissioning of NPP: Synthesizing lessons learned for communication of D&D from existing projects and a dedicated workshop	Deliverable of the project 87; BENG18700	Challenges and good practices in communication: experiences from D&D projects worldwide	Internal communication or communication with employees	Develop evidence based, theory based and strategic communication with employees before and during decommissioning	social	H	Decommissioning programs often report challenges with employees	6	
SCK CEN D&D	Report on international experiences on communication related to decommissioning of NPP: Synthesizing lessons learned for communication of D&D from existing projects and a dedicated workshop	Deliverable of the project 87; BENG18700	Challenges and good practices in communication: experiences from D&D projects worldwide	Local communities directly or indirectly linked to decommissioning programs may have many concerns, among others: lack of communication regarding the closure of nuclear facilities from government and industry to work on an integrated strategy; no say in the decision related to shut down or extension of the operational lifetime and lack of local community engagement; insufficient attention to socioeconomic impacts to host communities and neighbouring areas; impact on direct, indirect and induced jobs; loss of competences; loss of taxation and revenues to co-finance local public services; and lack of governmental decisions regarding waste management	Develop evidence based, theory based and strategic communication with local communities before and during decommissioning	social	M	Decommissioning programs have impact on the local community	6	
SCK CEN D&D	Report on international experiences on communication related to decommissioning of NPP: Synthesizing lessons learned for communication of D&D from existing projects and a dedicated workshop	Deliverable of the project 87; BENG18700	Challenges and good practices in communication: experiences from D&D projects worldwide	Mass media are an important source of information not only for external, but also internal stakeholders. Since mass media can contribute to increased awareness, changed perceptions and informed decision-making they can be seen as a communication channel, but also as a stakeholder. Unfortunately, mass media are barely interested in complex scientific technologies and therefore, they seldom report on decommissioning of nuclear installations. Opposite to this, media are more interested about specific events (e.g. accident during the decommissioning process), rather than long-term processes behind complex decisions (e.g. dismantling of the contaminated zone which could take many years).	Media reporting about decommissioning processes and its influence on public opinion	social	M	Media are important source of information and rarely report on decommissioning programs. Public is not informed.	6	

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SHARE SSH	Strategic Research Agenda for the SHARE platform for social sciences and humanities research relating to ionising radiation	SRA	RL1	Factors (social, economic, psychological) influencing individual strategies to cope with perceived risks, and expectations regarding radiological protection and the use of ionising radiation. Priority areas are the following: decommissioning and radioactive waste management;	Gaining insight in the various factors that impact perceptions and decision-making processes of different individual stakeholders regarding radioactive waste management and decommissioning.	Societal	H	While harmonization of regulations and policies might make sense from a focused and rational perspective, a range of historical, psychological, social, economic factors influence stakeholders' perspectives and strategies regarding RWM and decommissioning. Understanding the factors influencing the perspectives of decision-makers is paramount to understand potential barriers and facilitators in the harmonization of regulatory and policy frameworks.	3, 6	
SHARE SSH	Strategic Research Agenda for the SHARE platform for social sciences and humanities research relating to ionising radiation	SRA	RL1	Additional topics: How knowledge regarding complex technologies (e.g. the most recent and planned new generations of nuclear reactors; nuclear waste disposal technologies, etc...) is constituted and travels between and across stakeholder groups, and is being shaped and reshaped in that process.	Understanding the knowledges different stakeholder groups have regarding specific technologies, and in particular the ways in which these knowledges differ in and through the processes of knowledge creation and transfer.	Societal	H	Complex and/or novel nuclear technologies are known and understood differently among different stakeholder groups, depending on their position towards the technology (e.g. creators, users, regulators, beneficiaries, neighbours), or professional and cultural backgrounds. What a technology is and does, hence is not homogeneous, but differs from one stakeholder group to another. Identifying and understanding these different knowledges, but also how these are formed and changed across different contexts is thus key in the light of aligning practices, standards and/or regulations.	3, 4, 5, 6	
SHARE SSH	Strategic Research Agenda for the SHARE platform for	SRA	RL2	The care for holism can hereby be understood as the care for governance that takes into account all relevant	Researching and facilitating a holistic governance approach for	Societal	H	In order to accommodate to various stakeholders' priorities, concerns, and	6	

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	social sciences and humanities research relating to ionising radiation			<p>facts, values, interests, scientific developments, hopes, hypotheses, beliefs and concerns, with the aim to generate synergetic insights that have the potential to be trusted by those involved in, and affected by, ionising radiation exposure situations. Aspects of concern include, but are not limited to, (i) integration of scientific, technical, social and political aspects in the decision-making processes; and (ii) raising public awareness of these aspects and integrating them into knowledge building.</p> <p>Relevant cross-cutting topics include: Ethics of governance and aspects of 'good' governance (holistic, participatory, deliberative, sustainability thinking, capacity building, sense for cooperation, transparency, reflexivity, accountability, robustness, adaptability, traceability, ...).</p> <p>2.2. Analysis of existing policy and regulation related to governance of ionising radiation exposure situations: a. Public involvement in policies and decision making processes related to ionising radiation. b. Knowledge management (incl. transparency) and decision-making mechanisms (incl. institutional recreancy, interests and power relationships). c. Science as policy advice (role and working of scientific institutions and advisory councils, facilitation and mediation of the science-policy interface, uptake and implementation of advice into policy, research funding policies, etc.).</p> <p>2.3. Facilitating a cooperation between institutional (formal) and non-institutional (social) actors. 2.4. Assessing values and expectations that come with the integration of SSH in ionising radiation research and policies.</p> <p>CLOSELY RELATED: How stakeholder engagement shapes the development of knowledge, technologies and policies, institutional practices and relations between stakeholders.</p>	RWM and decommissioning, extending beyond a purely techno-scientific approach, and allowing for the integration of various stakeholder views, concerns and knowledges.			interests in RWM and decommissioning processes, a holistic governance approach should be developed and applied. In terms of harmonization of practices, standards and regulations, this entails that decisions should not reflect a single prioritization (e.g. a gain in time efficiency), but rather that procedures are developed, studied and applied which allow for a variety of interests to be identified and integrated in the decisions taken.		
SHARE SSH	Strategic Research Agenda for the	SRA	RL 2	Additional topics relevant to waste management:	Identify the rationales for and national differences	Societal	H	If harmonization of RWM processes would also	3, 4, 5, 6	

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	SHARE platform for social sciences and humanities research relating to ionising radiation			The ethics of compensation for radiological risks and comparison of approaches in different countries.	regarding compensations and compensation regimes provided for RWM processes.			entail a stronger cross-border collaboration, and potentially the use of shared facilities, this requires a thorough understanding of historically different ways of approaching the issue of siting RWM facilities, and more particularly the issue of compensation for those directly affected by this siting. Furthermore, besides regulatory challenges, a shared facility opens up important questions regarding the potential risks and benefits for different stakeholders, and hence the underpinning ethical principles (e.g. who would benefit from the facility, where would it be situated, and would there be an increase in risk for certain stakeholders, at what timescales?).		
SHARE SSH	Strategic Research Agenda for the SHARE platform for social sciences and humanities research relating to ionising radiation	SRA	RL2	Additional topics relevant to nuclear facilities: Integrating research of economic/financial aspects of nuclear facilities planning/ operation/ lifetime extension/ decommissioning. For example clarification of anticipated vs. real costs for the nuclear back-end.	A holistic approach to nuclear governance also requires the integration of economic/financial knowledge, which currently is often lacking or not transparent.	Economic, Societal	H	A key issue in decision-making on nuclear processes and practices is the financial/economic aspects (costs, gains) related to the decision at hand. Currently, such information is often lacking, scattered, incomplete or not sufficiently transparent, meaning that it is difficult to integrate in a holistic approach to decision-making. Moreover, regarding cross-country collaboration and harmonization, such information also needs to	3, 4, 5, 6	

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								be integrative and comparable.		
SHARE SSH	Strategic Research Agenda for the SHARE platform for social sciences and humanities research relating to ionising radiation	SRA	RL 3	Enhancing the reflexive awareness of actors involved in technical R&D about the societal implications of nuclear technology applications and radiological exposure situations.	Making nuclear researchers aware of the broader societal implications of their work.	Societal	H	When introducing new, innovative technologies, both foreseen and unforeseen broader societal impacts can be expected. When considering a stronger harmonization, and researching the technological developments facilitating such harmonization, it is paramount to also reflect on the wider implications of such innovations, beyond the direct techno-scientific effects on RWM/decommissioning.	5	
SHARE SSH	Strategic Research Agenda for the SHARE platform for social sciences and humanities research relating to ionising radiation	SRA	RL5	Risk communication needs to be “evidence-based (e.g., based on the qualitative and quantitative empirical data, surveys, experiments), theory-based (e.g., drawing from empirically-supported theories of health behaviour, information processing, risk perception and risk communication) and strategic (e.g., based on formats and methods that have been proven to reach its preconceived objectives)”. This area covers issues related to communication of risk, how exchange or sharing of risk related data, information and knowledge between and among different parties (such as regulators, experts, consumers, media, general public) can be provided. It also covers studies and practices of communicating promotional health information. [...] Research line 5 aims at developing research to support communication about ionising radiation between different stakeholders and citizen-centred risk communication, in order to clarify choices and options in a variety of exposure situations. It also seeks to empower citizens and other stakeholders to make more informed decisions.	Communication approaches, tools, and effects are crucial aspects in nuclear, as they connect various stakeholders, places and ideas, hence they should be thoroughly studied, understood and applied.	Societal	H	Communication is a key aspect of harmonization, in various ways. It is an important factor for understanding how different ideas, concepts, concerns, perspectives, etc. travel among various places and stakeholder groups. Communication strategies, tools, and approaches moreover can (un)intentionally imply very significant alterations to the messages communicated, requiring careful consideration in the context of the often sensitive or controversial topics characterizing the nuclear field. A historic understanding on how topics like decommissioning and RWM have been communicated about in different contexts is hence vital for understanding current approaches to	3, 4, 5, 6	

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								these fields, and how future communication could have an effect on harmonisation efforts in these fields. A specific aspect to be considered as well are the different vocabularies and terminologies used by various stakeholder groups, hence creating various realities of RWM and decommissioning. Moreover, in the light of cross-country collaboration and harmonization, it is also crucial to understand the various national and cultural differences at play in this context.		
SHARE SSH	Strategic Research Agenda for the SHARE platform for social sciences and humanities research relating to ionising radiation	SRA	RL6	Analysis of the impact of evolving technologies, knowledge, and communication technologies on radiological protection culture. [...] Analysis of the role and benefits of building and enhancing radiological protection culture [...] Developments associated with building, maintaining, enhancing and transmitting radiological protection culture	Developing, implementing and/or strengthening radiation protection culture through evidence-based research.	Societal	H	Radiation protection culture is “a concept of composite nature, characterized by a set of perceptions, values, attitudes, beliefs and expectations related to radiation risk; an assembly of knowledge, know-how, regulations, skills, experience, and practices related to radiological protection; and a dynamic building process based on multistakeholder interactions, including regulatory bodies and all concerned parties”. It is of high importance for the protection of workers and the broader population in various nuclear contexts. In terms of harmonization, and especially the development of new technologies and cross-border collaboration, it is	5, 6	

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								important to learn how radiation protection cultures can be formed for new situations, how they differ among various settings (also e.g. due to various national regulations), and what steps can be taken to develop and implement a radiation protection culture which provides optimal safety in a dynamic situation.		
SITEX										
SITEX. Network	SITEX II - Developing a common understanding on the interpretation and implementation of safety requirements.	Deliverable	Appendix 1 <i>Optimisation of protection for deep geological repository</i> §E. Key messages	The optimisation of radiological protection is a process which consists in the identification and use of safety criteria/attributes necessary to select the best protective technical options under the prevailing circumstances. Prevailing circumstances can bound the optimisation process to various extents, such as by limiting the available options and/or by defining additional conditions (e.g. retrievability). However, prevailing circumstances may not unacceptably impair safety. Prior to the options comparison exercise starting, common understanding and commitment shall be reached among all concerned organisations, in particular between the implementer and the regulator, on which factors shall be taken into consideration in the optimisation process.	Important to develop a common understanding of what is the optimisation process (from the ALARA point of view).	regulatory	H	Optimisation is a fundamental principle of the regulatory framework associated to waste management.	6	
SITEX. Network	SITEX II - Developing a common understanding on the interpretation and implementation of safety requirements.	Deliverable	Appendix 1 <i>Optimisation of protection for deep geological repository</i> §E. Key messages	Optimisation of long term safety can be achieved in practice by incorporating in the stepwise evolution of the safety case an ongoing questioning on the performance and the robustness of the disposal system and its components. Both operational and long term protection have to be optimised from early phases and across the full lifecycle of the geological disposal, and balanced as a whole. Application of Best Available Technologies has been acknowledged as one of the items to be considered in the optimisation process; in other words, the optimisation process itself is not limited to only BAT application, it is broader. The “optimum” is considered to be reached once the benefit in protection has become small with regard to the resources needed. <i>Optimisation</i> of protection does not mean <i>minimisation</i> of radiological impacts as the best option is not necessarily the one with the lowest dose.	Important to develop a common understanding of how to implement the optimization process and when the optimum is considered as reached.	Technological, regulatory, economic, societal	H	Optimisation is a fundamental principle of the regulatory framework associated to waste management.	3, 6	

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SITEX. Network	SITEX II - Developing a common understanding on the interpretation and implementation of safety requirements.	Deliverable	Appendix 2 <i>Waste Acceptance Criteria for Deep Geological Repository</i> §E. Key messages	Defining Waste Acceptance Criteria (WAC) is a stepwise iterative process, it shall be duly planned and adequate milestones identified prior it starts. Roles and responsibilities have to be precisely defined throughout the continuous and iterative process of defining WAC, allowing for thorough understanding of the criteria and their use by each interested party. Preliminary WAC should be available as soon as possible including the intention for minimizing the need for any future intervention. Their updating should be done through an iterative process carried out in parallel and in conjunction with the development of disposal facility design and safety assessment. Elaboration of preliminary WAC needs to take into account all the interdependent steps identified or assumed for the management of these wastes until final disposal, and their interdependencies.	Important to develop a common understanding of how WAC are defined. A EU joint list of WAC could be developed for key waste types.	Technological, regulatory, economic, harmonisation	H	WAC are key to improve cross border collaboration on RWM.	3, 4, 6	
SITEX. Network	SITEX II - Developing a common understanding on the interpretation and implementation of safety requirements.	Deliverable	Appendix 2 <i>Waste Acceptance Criteria for Deep Geological Repository</i> §E. Key messages	While defining limits and parameter values, particular attention should be paid how to check compliance of waste with these limits and values. Traceability of departures from WAC and non-conformity treatment is important and the lessons learned are a key task within the objective of continuous quality and safety demonstration improvement. WAC may include different parameters, eventually with different limit values to be checked at different steps in the management process of the waste.	Important to develop a common understanding of how WAC are controlled and how non conformities are reported and documented. Moving towards harmonization of the types of controls and ways for reporting non-conformities could be beneficial.	Technological, regulatory, economic, harmonisation	H	WAC are key to improve cross border collaboration on RWM.	3, 4, 5, 6	
SITEX. Network	SITEX II - Developing a common understanding on the interpretation and implementation of safety requirements.	Deliverable	Appendix 3 <i>Site characterisation program for deep geological repository</i> §E. Key messages	The site characterization program should establish baseline conditions for the site and environment in its undisturbed condition; support the understanding of the normal evolution; identify any events and processes associated with the site that might disturb the normal evolution of the DGR system; support the understanding of the effect on safety of any features, events and processes associated with the DGR.	Parameters which are considered for site characterization and the related FEP identification could benefit from some harmonization / common understanding (which parameters are measured, why, how to develop FEP lists...). For instance considering the possibility of joint repositories between MS.	Technological, regulatory, environmental	M	Compared to other topics seems less "important". However, seen the possibility of developing joint repositories, a Medium score is proposed.	3, 6	
SITEX. Network	SITEX II - Developing a common understanding on the interpretation and implementation of safety requirements.	Deliverable	Appendix 4 <i>Operational issues with regards to post closure safety</i> §H. Operational safety scenarios	Key arguments developed in the Safety Case for DGR are shaped into the development of scenarios: normal operation (including concurrent activities of mining and nuclear operations or <i>co-activity</i>), incidental and accidental situations.	A common understanding about key scenarios to consider in repository safety evaluations would be interesting (as it is done for instance for Nuclear Reactors (e.g. LOCA scenarios, LOOP ...)).	regulatory, societal, environmental	H	Compared to other topics seems less "important". However, seen the recent licenses given for construction / operation of DGR a score H is given.	3, 6	

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SITEX. Network	SITEX II - Developing a common understanding on the interpretation and implementation of safety requirements.	Deliverable	Appendix 4 <i>Operational issues with regards to post closure safety</i> §M. Operating limits and conditions	For any nuclear facility, the establishment and substantiation of operating limits and conditions (OLCs) and their sustainability over the operational time is one of the key aspects of the demonstration that the facility shows a high level of safety. For a DGR, this challenge is deepened by the peculiarities of the facility, like the operational phase duration and the links between operational and long term safety.	A common understanding about how to define OLCs for radioactive waste repositories seems interesting, notably because of the possibility of joint repositories between MS.	regulatory, societal, environmental	M	Seems of lower priority compared to the topic about scenarios to consider in repository safety evaluations	3, 6	
SITEX. Network	SITEX II - Developing a common understanding on the interpretation and implementation of safety requirements.	Deliverable	Appendix 4 <i>Operational issues with regards to post closure safety</i> §G and K. Closing strategy and monitoring and surveillance	<p>The operational aspects of the SC should also show the strategy the operator aims at developing for the final closure of the DGR. Several different ones may be provided, spanning from direct closure of emplacement cells right after waste has been disposed to massive closure works performed once every single waste package has been transferred to their final emplacement. These strategies are obviously deeply correlated with reversibility and flexibility issues.</p> <p>Monitoring (and/or surveillance, depending on national programmes' wording) strategies and implementation are of particular importance. In fact, they are critical both for operational safety (enforcement of OLCs, maintenance, regulatory oversight, emergency management, etc.) and long term safety (evolution of EBS, identification of barrier degradations, etc.). But most of all, monitoring should allow to check continuously whether any event during operation may impact the facility and the safety envelope.</p>	Developing a joint understanding about the decision making process leading to the closure of a DGR is important. Monitoring will play a central role in this process (based on which monitored data will the decision to close a repository will rely on?). Deciding to close a repository is also a choice with an important societal dimension which should be considered in the decision making process.	Technological, regulatory, societal, environmental			3, 5, 6	
SNETP										
SNETP	SNETP STRATEGIC RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA July 2021	SRA	Executive Summary	Decommissioning and Waste management covers the management, treatment and disposal of waste arising from operations across the nuclear fuel cycle. Importantly, it also considers waste minimisation and recycling of non-fuel materials. The focus should be on the identification of best practices from the international community and the development of innovative technologies and methods that will reduce decommissioning costs and timescale, thereby also improving safety and enhancing environmental performance.	outlines desired focus of decommissioning and waste management activities	potentially all	low	high-level statement	3, 4, 5, 6	
SNETP	SNETP STRATEGIC RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA July 2021	SRA	Executive Summary	<p>DECOMMISSIONING, DISMANTLING & WASTE MANAGEMENT</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minimisation of waste production by design, material selection, operational measures, efficient dismantling technologies, and development of advanced waste treatment and conditioning technologies; • Development of characterization techniques for waste inventory assessment and plant and facility assessment; 	describes desired focus of decommissioning and waste management activities in more detail	potentially all	med	provides good information on development areas, but does not indicate harmonisation needs	3, 4, 5, 6	

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				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development of new technologies and approaches to deliver decommissioning safer, cheaper, faster and sustainable, to enhance waste treatment processes, and to minimize waste arising, through design, operation and decommissioning. 						
SNETP	SNETP STRATEGIC RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA July 2021	SRA	Executive Summary	<p>HARMONISATION</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enable wide and general use of non-nuclear industry standard components and equipment (manufactured according to ISO, EN, etc.) in nuclear facilities, in particular for SSCs of lower safety class (SC3), without any additional nuclear specific requirements, providing (a) the components and equipment have a proven record of high quality and functionality, (b) they are subject to additional qualification tests to meet environmental and seismic requirements as appropriate and (c) they undergo a dedication process that provides reasonable assurance that they deliver their intended safety function; Allow the use of safety related SSCs produced according to alternative nuclear codes and standards, meaning nuclear codes and standards that are different to the ones that are normally used in the country that hosts the nuclear facility; Common licensing rules and procedures of new technologies; Common Regulations and standards at the EU level. 	describes harmonisation needs and actions	potentially all	low	refers to nuclear new build, not back-end considerations	3, 4, 5, 6	
SNETP	SNETP STRATEGIC RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA July 2021	SRA	Introduction	With a strong, positive regulatory framework in place, there is huge potential to decrease build time and cost of new nuclear projects. Recent projects on modernisation and harmonisation of the nuclear supply chain have shown that streamlined requirements on vendors, combined with the benefits of series build, can rapidly increase the speed of new-builds while decreasing costs and maintaining safety;	describes benefits of harmonisation relative to enlightened regulatory framework	regulatory, economical, societal, harmonisation	low	refers to nuclear new builds	3, 6	
SNETP	SNETP STRATEGIC RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA July 2021	SRA	2.3.1 Challenges and planning assumptions for nuclear energy	nuclear energy systems need to comply with both a safety and performance vision and to continually improve in the delivery of both of these. Examples include: Increased sustainability: optimisation of resource use and minimisation of nuclear waste; Minimization of environmental impact: minimizing discharges, waste management, fuel cycle.	describes needs for nuclear energy systems	economic, environmental	medium	back-end needs indicated	4	
SNETP	SNETP STRATEGIC RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA July 2021	SRA	2.3.1 Challenges and planning assumptions for nuclear energy	Licensing is potentially a challenge for SMRs, as design certification, construction and operation licence costs are not necessarily less than for large reactors. SMR standardization of licensing and of regulatory requirements are needed in order to use their full potential,	indicates potential licensing challenges for SMRs and need for standardisation of regulatory requirements	regulatory, harmonisation	med	refers to SMR commissioning, depends on extent to which back-end considerations are involved	6	

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			2.3.1 Challenges and planning assumptions for nuclear energy	From the technological viewpoint, the nuclear sector shall continue its learning curve by adapting new technologies (e.g. artificial intelligence, big data, data analytics, advanced simulation), new materials, and new fabrication routes to the safety requirements and reinforcement of the supply chain across Europe thanks to agile standardisation of tools and harmonisation of practices.	describes areas where nuclear sector will adapt new technologies	technological, harmonisation	medium	does not describe specific harmonisation issues	5, 6	
SNETP	SNETP STRATEGIC RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA July 2021	SRA	2.3.1 Challenges and planning assumptions for nuclear energy	Decommissioning and dismantling: New characterisation, cleaning and cutting technologies are being developed, as well as new waste forms commensurate with the level of activity, the chemical or physical nature of the waste, and the local or national regulations. Technologies such as digitalisation, simulation, augmented reality or advanced robotics will mature and offer new opportunities.	Indicates new technologies being developed for decommissioning and dismantling.	technological, regulatory	medium	does not describe specific harmonisation issues	5, 6	
SNETP	SNETP STRATEGIC RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA July 2021	SRA	3.2.3 R&D Topics NDT Qualification	Harmonisation on the design of practical trials, data collection, data fusion and production of test pieces for qualification of ISI procedures and personnel;	describes R&D need on NDT qualification for ISI in terms of harmonisation	technological, harmonisation	low	not a back-end consideration	5	
SNETP	SNETP STRATEGIC RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA July 2021	SRA	3.3 Next Generation of Nuclear Fission Reactors 3.3.1 Objectives and Motivation	To achieve major steps in terms of sustainability (reduced high-level waste production, better use of resources and higher thermal efficiencies), to open the way for high-temperature non-electricity applications, and to achieve flexibility in terms of adaptation to mix with a substantial contribution of intermittent/variable sources, new types of reactors based on other coolant technologies should be envisaged, combined with more advanced fuel cycles. Fast spectrum reactors with closed fuel cycles will allow a significant reduction in high-level nuclear waste radiotoxicity and volume. The use of fast reactors in a closed fuel cycle approach will allow a large decrease in natural resource (uranium) consumption, transmutation of high-level waste	describes objectives for next gen reactors	technological, environmental	medium	refers to high-level waste reduction	4, 5	
WENRA										
WENRA	WENRA Strategy 2019-2023	SRA	3.4 SMR 3.4.2 State-of-the-art and Challenges	Main challenges to (advanced) SMR deployment in Europe are lack of a licensing framework specifically applicable to advanced SMR technologies.	describes challenges to SMR deployment in Europe which includes "lack of a licensing framework specifically applicable to advanced SMR technologies."	technological, regulatory	medium	depends on whether the identified challenge involves back-end considerations	5, 6	

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WENRA	WENRA Strategy 2019-2023	SRA	6.2 Harmonisation 6.2.1 Objectives and Motivation	<p>As stated in Nuclear Illustrative Programme (EC, 2017), the construction of new nuclear units will be necessary in the future in Europe to satisfy the energy objectives of the European Commission (EC). This program encourages vendors and suppliers to engage in an initiative to standardize their components and codes to a higher degree in order to ensure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. a faster procurement process; b. higher compatibility and more transparent and higher safety standards; c. increased capacity of operators to control technology and knowledge management. <p>Among them, the most challenging task is harmonization of safety standards. Because nuclear safety is a national responsibility, national regulators are independent and we face 29 different sets of safety rules in EU. It is not widely appreciated yet, that the independence of judgement does not exclude cooperation in preparing or harmonizing safety standards. Below we mention some initial efforts, but they are by far not enough and further cooperation between regulators should be encouraged.</p> <p>This is especially important for Generation IV innovative reactors. LWR standards have been developed over many years from practical experience and therefore they are at least conceptually coherent between different countries. This is certainly not the case for advanced reactors. There is a risk, that regulations concerning advanced reactors will be so different that the EU market will be split into several regions requiring different designs. This might be an important barrier in deploying Generation IV reactors in Europe.</p>	directly addresses harmonisation and standardisation	technological, regulatory	medium	refers mainly to nuclear new builds, but does stress the importance of cooperation in harmonising safety standards	5, 6	